

SoildiverAgro

Soil biodiversity enhancement in European agroecosystems to promote their stability and resilience by external inputs reduction and crop performance increase

D5.1- HANDBOOK ON WP5 SETTING UP, PROTOCOLS FOR SAMPLING, SAMPLE PROCEDURE AND ANALYSIS

Universidade de Vigo

D5.1. HANDBOOK ON WP5 SETTING UP, PROTOCOLS FOR SAMPLING, SAMPLE PROCEDURE AND ANALYSIS

Summary

The WP5 aims to determine the relationship that exists between soil biodiversity and other variables such as the crop production or emission of greenhouse gases. The first step in carrying out this work package is to establish a series of standardized procedures for experimental set up, sampling, processing of these samples, data collection and characterization, and data analysis.

This deliverable presents, in the form of an appendix, a handbook of methods to carry out all the analyzes that will allow establishing the soil and crops characteristics of the different pedoclimatic regions. Therefore, the protocols agreed by the project members are included. The aspects considered in this handbook of methods are:

- Experimental design
- Crop growth and quality properties. This part includes the development of the crops, the yield, the incidence of diseases, and the nutritional evaluation of cereals, legumes and vegetables. Types of sampling of the soils (oriented to determine dry bulk density, biodiversity or physicochemical characteristics).
- Earthworm sampling.
- Physical characterization of the soil including determination of dry bulk density, coarse fragments, water holding capacity, humidity, soil hydraulic conductivity, particle size distribution and aggregates.
- Chemical characterization of the soil including determination of pH, salinity, and content of organic matter, organic and inorganic carbon, total and inorganic nitrogen, available phosphorus, potassium, calcium, magnesium, boron, effective exchange capacity, cations (iron, manganese, copper, zinc and molybdenum), and pesticides.
- Biological analyzes that include biodiversity measures (of worms, nematodes and microorganisms), using techniques such as DNA extraction and purification, or fatty acid analysis.
- Soil greenhouse gas emission.

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1 Introduction

Taking into account that, through this WP (WP5) it is intended to determine the capacity of edaphic biodiversity to solve current economic, environmental and agronomic problems, it is essential to establish a reference framework to carry out the pertinent experimental design, sampling and analyzes. Thus, through this book "**HANDBOOK ON WP5 SETTING UP, PROTOCOLS FOR SAMPLING, SAMPLE PROCEDURE AND ANALYSIS**" included in **Annex I**, the members of the SoildiverAgro project tried to standardize the methods that will be used to design field experiments, follow crop performance, and sample/characterize the soils and crops of 15 case studies in 6 different pedoclimatic regions throughout Europe. The methods included in the handbook cover techniques for experimental design, follow crop performance (growth, yield, pest incidence, and nutritional quality of vegetables, among others), soil sampling and determination of chemical properties (pH, salinity, organic matter, available cations, etc.), physical (bulk density, texture, water holding capacity, among others) and biological (nematodes, earthworms, microorganisms, etc). Moreover, method for soil greenhouse gases emission analysis is also included.

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2 Annex 1: Handbook

**HANDBOOK ON CASE STUDIES SET
UP, PROTOCOLS FOR SAMPLING,
SAMPLE PROCEDURE AND ANALYSIS**

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PREFACE

During the development of the SoildiverAgro Project, it is intended to analyse samples (of soils and crops) from all over Europe, so it is necessary to define a series of standardized methodologies that allow obtaining comparable results. This book covers all the methods that will be used in Work Package 5 (WP5). Each chapter of the handbook includes a first section with a slight explanation of the property to be determined, followed by a list with the necessary materials, a step-by-step explanation of the procedure in question, the calculations necessary to obtain the desired property, and a series of important tips or points to improve the procedure. Each chapter also includes a specific bibliography section.

This volume is divided into eight sections. The first one is focused on the elaboration of an experimental design and the collection of technical data from the experimental plots for the economic assessment, and compare the results of the actual crop system with the one that is going to be tested. The second section focuses on the methods used for soil sampling. The third part focuses on crop growth and yield, and on the incidence of pest diseases. The fourth section focuses on the methods that allow characterizing the crop quality of cereals and legumes (specific grain weight, flour yield and moisture, nitrogen, protein, starch and ash content) and vegetables (weight size and distribution, flesh firmness, and starch of potatoes). The fifth part is centred in the analysis of soil biodiversity, and includes earthworm, nematode and microbial diversity. The sixth section considers the methods to characterize soil chemical fertility (pH, salinity, and total nitrogen among other variables) and the pollutants present in the soil (pesticides). The seventh part includes methods related to the soil structure, water availability and carbon sequestration. Finally, section eight is dedicated to the characterization of soil greenhouse emissions (N₂O, CO₂ and CH₄).

Numerous people from various countries have participated in the realization of this handbook, and the editors want to express their special thanks to all of them.

THE EDITORS

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Soildiver *Agro*

A stylized illustration of a landscape. It features two green trees with brown trunks on the right side. Below the trees are several curved, overlapping bands of green, representing a field or hills. The colors of the bands range from light green to dark green.

1. CASE STUDIES SETUP AND EXPERIMENTAL MANAGEMENT

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Before performing any field experiment or demonstration experience, it is vital to properly define the experimental design, always aligned with the objectives of the study. SoildiverAgro WP5 has been designed to provide sound and robust scientific understanding of the impacts of sustainable management practices and cropping systems on the improvement in soil biodiversity and how this is related to crop production (yield and quality) and other ecosystem services such as soil quality and carbon sequestration in different pedoclimatic regions. This should be followed by increases in farm yields and economic revenues for farmers with associated enhanced sustainability. In particular, this WP5 aims to evaluate how cropping systems that foster soil biodiversity can:

- effectively enhance genetic and functional microbial diversity, with decreases in soil-borne diseases
- effectively increase the diversity of biological regulators (nematodes) and ecosystem engineers (earthworms)
- increase crop growth and yield and reduce the incidence of pests/diseases
- improve crop quality and nutritional characteristics
- improve soil fertility retaining nutrients in the soil, preventing them from leaching and increasing the plant cover and thus reducing soil erosion
- improve soil structure and quality, increase soil C sequestration, foster natural soil functioning and promote the formation of stable aggregates that improve water infiltration, root penetration and water-holding capacity of the soil
- optimise use of agrochemical and tillage
- reduce GHG emissions

Hence, a previous robust definition of the field trial is essential to be able to generate accurate data to assess if these objectives are achieved. It is essential to establish field plots where different experiences are going to be tested with a surface representative of the cropping system for which results could be extrapolated. Moreover, replication is needed to assess the proper verification of the observations, which need to be consistent in the different repetitions. This is because soil is highly heterogeneous, and the spatial variability has to be included in the experimental layout, so that soil and crop samples represent the mean value for a treatment in a specific variable. For this purpose, within WP5 we have decided to implement complete randomized experimental design, randomized complete block design or block experimental design, depending on the characteristics of the farm where the study is going to be performed. Once the distribution of treatments is designed, it is essential to decide the size of the plots, the frequency of samplings and the proper timing for them, the number of soil and crop samples collected in each sampling, the procedure to collect the samples and the pre-treatment of samples needed to preserve them for the specific analyses. These issues are important to generate data in which we can rely on, and we can extract conclusions and disseminate the main findings amongst the interested stakeholders.

In the following chapters we provide an overview of how the experiments have been designed within WP5, with special attention on spatial distribution of the plots, size, samplings and number of samples. Depending on the specific soil or crop property to be analysed, the sampling procedure and number of samples can vary, depending on the particularities of that property.

1.1. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Soils are highly heterogeneous biomaterials. Soil sampling is conducted to collect the most representative samples and characterize the nutrient status of a field as accurately and inexpensively as possible (Masoom et al 2016).

Experimental design is important in any scientific study. Sampling design involves the selection of the most efficient method for choosing the samples that will be used to estimate the properties of the sampling area. The definition of the population to be sampled is central to the initial formulation of the research study (Pennock, 2004). Variability in a soil lies in soil spatial heterogeneity and accuracy of quantification. When spatial variation in soil is not taken into consideration, typical soil sampling can result in a substantial departure from the true mean value of a soil variable, even if the soil analysis itself is highly accurate (Tan, 2005). With the sampling design it is possible to determine how specific elements will be selected from the population, and these sampled elements form the sample population.

In this chapter we propose two procedures for experimental design that can be applied in the case studies selected in the project.

PROCEDURE

In the comparison of treatments in soil science experiments, a well-chosen experimental design is of crucial importance for making appropriate (optimal) statistical inference at low costs. Below the two most common alternatives applied in the project case studies are shown:

1.

If a complete randomized experimental design, a randomized complete block design or a split-plot design is going to be carried out (Figure 1.1.1.):

Three soil samplings at the same phenological stage will have to be performed during three consecutive crop cycles. The control treatment (the one already performed in the farm as a routine basis; CT) represents the field variability before the start of any new treatment on the farm.

Figure 1.1.1. Example of a randomized experimental design. CT: control treatment; T1: treatment 1; T2: treatment 2.

CALCULATIONS

None calculations are applied in this protocol.

2.

If a block experimental design (not randomized) is going to be carried out (Figure 1.1.2), control treatment (the one already performed in the farm as a routine basis; CT) does not represent field variability since each treatment is located in different areas of the field, and some variations will be present in soil owing to different location. So, initial conditions in each block have to be taken into account. In case an initial sampling is not possible or to avoid an extra year of soil sampling, 25% of each block can be used as internal control for the first year. So, during first sampling, soil has to be collected from the treatment plot and from the internal control to have representation of the initial conditions. For the next years, this surface (25 % of the total surface) will not be taken into account. Therefore, since the second year 100% of the block surface will be used with the treatments, CT1 and CT2 will not be sampled because they will have a crop cycle less than the whole block (see Figure 1.1.2.).

Figure 1.1.2. Example of block experimental design. CT: control treatment; T1: treatment 1; T2: treatment 2.

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1.2. COLLECTION OF TECHNICAL DATA FROM EXPERIMENTAL PLOTS FOR THE ECONOMIC ASSESSMENT

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Within SoildiverAgro's WP6 (Environmental and socioeconomic assessment of soil biodiversity management and conservation), sub-task 6.2.2 focus on the farm level economic analysis of soil biodiversity enhancement practices. Sub-task 6.2.2 aims to assess the impact of the soil biodiversity enhancing management practices proposed in the project on crop profitability, economic risk and on resource use efficiency and productivity under various pedoclimatic conditions, paying special attention to the reduction in the use of mineral fertilizers and pesticides going along with the tested practices. Consequently, the basis for such analysis will be the crop experimental activities of the project (WP5).

The assessment in sub-task 6.2.2 will be based on the calculation of different economic ratios and indices using both primary data generated in the experimental activities of the project and collected from farmers and agricultural technical advisors, and secondary data (from previous studies on crop production costs, agricultural statistical databases, etc.).

The collected data will be used to establish, for each crop, a technical-economic characterisation of the standard crop production processes and farming practices in terms of production, input use, production costs, dynamics of the production process, etc. Such characterisation will serve as a benchmark for comparison with the experimental plots where the different sustainable farming practices will be tested.

In this respect, the fundamental criteria to be applied will be two. First, the productive process will be defined on the basis of the natural crop cycle, to be able to obtain the income and production costs associated with each production activity in a more direct and realistic manner. Second, each crop's production cycle/process will be considered in isolation, even if the farms have more than one crop or productive process. Therefore, based on these methodological criteria, the production cycle must be understood as a double process, both agronomic and economic.

Consequently, the technical-economic characterization of the crops' production processes requires collecting detailed information on the different crop operations along the productive cycle. To obtain such information, crop operations will be organised on a monthly basis, starting right after harvesting and ending in the harvesting of the following crop season, and per type of operations (ploughing, irrigation, fertilisation, weed and pest control, pruning, harvesting, etc.). Each farming operation can imply the use of labour and machinery, consumption of water and energy or the use of different materials. This raises the need to collect both technical and economic information to compile all the farming operations implemented along the temporal sequence of the productive cycle. Such information will be expressed either in physical units to characterize input use (hours, m³, litres, kilograms, etc.) or in monetary units to quantify the associated cost.

Data to be collected on each crop's production process will therefore include: (1) quantity of production; (2) use of inputs such as fertilisers, herbicides and other agrochemicals, energy and irrigation water (type of input, quantity applied, hours/number of applications, price of inputs); (3) farm machinery used (type of machinery, crop operations, hours of use, fuel consumption, cost, etc.); and (4) labour (crop operations, working hours/days per operation, costs, etc.).

However, only technical information will be collected from experimental plots, while economic information (such as wages, cost of inputs, O&M costs of machinery or irrigation technologies, etc.) will be obtained from both farmers and secondary sources of information.

The data collected will be standardized to define a standard characterization of the production process for each crop, in order to allow for comparison between the different farming practices tested. Each production process will be characterized in terms of the standard productive process, defined by the different crop operations on a monthly basis. For the standardization of production costs, input market prices and average market product prices will be used. Market crop prices will be calculated as the average yearly price for each crop calculated using data from official agricultural database. The standardization of costs allows to reduce biases and variabilities resulting from differences in the prices of inputs and eases the analysis of water use and the comparison of different irrigation strategies. The technical and economic characterization of standard crop production processes will be the basis for the definition of the cost structure for each crop, following the methodology and cost items considered in the standards set for the European Farm Accountancy Data Network.

Technical data from the experimental plots will be collected using an Excel spreadsheet developed by UPCT and will be compatible with the technical-economic characteristics of the standard production processes identified.

PROCEDURE

The spreadsheet to be used for the collection of technical data for the farm level economic assessment (see Table below) includes both general information and data for each farming operation performed. The general information to be filled is the following:

- Identification of the experimental treatment: one spreadsheet must be used for each treatment in the experimental design, including all repetitions of the experimental treatment;
- Number of repetitions of the experimental treatment;
- Area considered (in m²): area of the treatment that the spreadsheet provides information about and area of each repetition in the treatment;
- Crop: main crop or rotation crop;
- Crop density.

One row must be used for each farming operation performed. It is very important that all the information provided be given for the whole experimental treatment area (with the exception of crop yields). For example, do not provide values per hectare or per m² but values for the area considered.

The information to be provided for each farming operation (row) is the following:

- Date in which the farming operation was performed;
- Description of the farming operation: for example, fertilization, application of biostimulants, tillage, etc.;
- Type of farm machinery used;
- Products applied to the crop in that farming operation:
 - Name of product/s applied (e.g. seeds, fertilizer, herbicide, pesticide, etc.), indicating the full commercial name of the product and a brief explanation of the motive to apply it (pest to combat, nutritional requirement to satisfy, etc.);
 - Applied dosage of each product (litres, kilograms, etc. for the whole experimental treatment area);
- Water applied in each irrigation application (m³ of irrigation water for the whole experimental treatment area);
- Electric power consumed in each irrigation application (kWh for the whole experimental treatment area);
- Labour use in each farming operation:
 - Number of workers participating in each farming operation, including machinery drivers;
 - Time of use of machinery in each farming operation (hours driven by drivers in each experimental treatment);
 - Working time of non-driving labourers (hours worked by all workers, except machinery drivers, in each experimental treatment);
- Crop production in the case of harvest operations (kilograms for each repetition of the experimental treatment).

REMARKS

- The spreadsheet should be filled regularly to reduce the risk of missing data or incorrect data.
- Use one row for each farming operation performed and fill all the items applicable.
- Refer all data to the whole experimental treatment area. Do not convert to per hectare values.

2. SOIL SAMPLING

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

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Soil sampling and analysis is a reliable method to determine important characteristics of agricultural fields including biological, chemical, environmental, and physical properties. Soil testing is basically a three-step process: (i) the collection of a representative sample from a field or section, (ii) proper analysis of that sample to determine a selection of soil characteristics, and (iii) keeping record of the data for future data-mining. In order to standardize the methods for sampling, sample processing, data acquisition and data storage/sharing across different partners (Table 2.1.), procedures, workflows or protocols have to be selected, if needed developed or adapted, and eventually carefully noted and distributed. The following sections, each containing detailed descriptions of one or several actions belonging to the sampling event conducted for WP5 “Impacts of soil biodiversity on crop production and other ecosystem services” of the EU-H2020 SoildiverAgro project (EU-H2020 project 817819), constitute a Handbook.

Table 2.1. List of the partners in charge for the soil sampling event per case study.

PEDOCLIMATIC ZONES & PARTNERS IN CHARGE FOR THE SOIL SAMPLING EVENT						
PEDOCLIMATIC ZONE	COUNTRY	CASE STUDY	PARTNER IN CHARGE	OTHER INVOLVED	PARTNER(S)	
Mediterranean South (MDS)	Spain	1, 2	UPCT	ASAJA, FYNECO		
Lusitanian (LUS)	Spain	3, 4, 5	UVIGO	INORDE, RGG, SYM		
Atlantic Central (ATC)	Belgium	6, 7, 8, 9	EV-ILVO	PSKW, INAGRO, POMO		
Continental (CON)	Germany	10, 11	TI	FAR		
Nemoral (NEM)	Estonia	12	EULS	MTÜPK		
Boreal (BOR)	Finland	13, 14, 15	LUKE	TT, MTJ, PETLA		

WP5 has been designed to provide sound and robust scientific understanding of the impacts of sustainable management practices and cropping systems on the improvement in soil biodiversity, and how this is related to crop production (yield and quality) and other ecosystem services such as soil fertility and carbon sequestration in different pedoclimatic regions. This WP5 also aims to produce industrial innovation by testing of new plant growth promoting products based on formulations of soil microorganisms in order to reduce fertilizer application in crops and promote crop growth and development by development of soil microorganisms.

WP5 includes 15 field case studies (Figure 2.1) where different cropping systems and management practices will be tested to check their effects on soil biodiversity enhancement, crop growth, development and health, and the delivery of ecosystem services. The cropping systems and/or management practices included are related with: the use of soil mycorrhiza and plant growth promoting bacteria (PGPB) including the development and testing of new commercial products; management of soil organisms (e.g. fungivores); the application of suitable crop rotations, multiple cropping and intercropping; the development of pest alert systems; the use of nutrient catch crops; the use of trap crops for pest control; the use of by-products as soil ameliorants; and the application of adequate tillage systems.

Figure 2.1. Location of the 15 case studies in the different European pedoclimatic areas together with the cropping systems and/or management practices tested on each case study.

As general rule, the soil samplings will be carried out according to a selected phenological stage of the crop:

- a) For wheat. Flag leaf stage: flag leaf fully unrolled, ligule just visible.
- b) For potato. Crop cover complete: about 90% of plants meet between rows, regardless of the weather and following the experimental design and applied agricultural practices in every case study.
- c) For rape. Beginning of stem elongation: no internodes (“rosette”).
- d) For pea. Visibly extended internodes.
- e) For cabbage. Heads begin to form: the two youngest leaves do not unfold.
- f) For leek. Leaf bases begin to thicken or extend.
- g) For turnip. Leaf rosette has reached 30% of the expected diameter typical for the variety.
- h) For broccoli. Leaf rosette has reached 30% of the expected diameter typical for the variety.
- g) For bean/soybean. Nine or more side shoots visible.

In each case study (Figure 2.1.), 3 soil samplings will be carried out, once a year during three crop cycles. A maximum of three treatments per case study are recommended, with four field replications (four plots per treatment). One mandatory treatment will be the conventional management historically performed by the farmer in the farm. The other two treatments are selected with the objective of increasing soil biodiversity. One composite soil sample will be collected from each plot each year. This will bring the total number of soil samples to be sampled up to 720: 3 treatments x 4 plots x 15 case studies x 4 soil samplings. In those exceptional cases in which more than three treatments are investigated, the increase of number of samples should be clarified with the partners responsible for data acquisition.

The necessary data will be gathered by analysing soil samples taken from the 15 case studies (Figure 2.1), which are conventional and organic management systems in different European croplands. This is accompanied by filling in a ‘Soil Sample Information Sheet’ with cooperation of the owner of the case study (Annex 2.1). This information sheet assembles data about the geographical location of the field, crop phenological state, agricultural management system, treatments applied, weather conditions, and soil characteristics such as soil topography, colour, temperature and moisture. Soil temperature and moisture are measured using soil moisture and temperature sensors, which are inserted in the soil up to the depth of the probe, and the values are written down.

The ‘WP5 Sampling Scheme’ adapted from WP3 (Annex 2.2) provides a practical overview of the whole procedure including the soil sampling itself, the number of samples to be taken and the pre-processing steps like transport, storage and distribution of the necessary subsamples to the different partners responsible for the analysis of a set of data.

Each farmer who is not beneficiary of the project and provides a farm as SoildiverAgro case study should fill in a ‘consent template’ (Annex 2.3). This consent letter is not applicable to case studies whose owners are beneficiaries of the project, since they have already signed the Consortium Agreement. This document gives a brief description of the aim of the SoildiverAgro-project. It also provides a clarification on the purpose of the farmer’s participation including benefits, rights linked to his/her participation and time involvement; in addition of indicating to the farmer that none reimbursement will be paid for her/his participation in the project. Finally, it includes an explanation about the use, storage and, protection of the data. By signing the document, the farmer declares to agree upon the sampling on his/her field(s) and upon the use and distribution of the data linked to the sample(s). Of course, it remains the intention not to publish any personal information or information that can connect the data directly to the farmer as clearly mentioned in the ‘consent template’.

ANNEX 2.1 SOIL SAMPLE INFORMATION SHEET

Soil Sampling Information Sheet (WP5)		
	Sampler	Farmer
Name		
Institute/farm		
Address		
City		
Country		
Tel.		
Cell phone		
email address		
Important: take photographs		Community of Practitioner: <input type="checkbox"/> Form consent signed: <input type="checkbox"/>
Field trial general information		
Case study number		
Pedoclimatic region		
Augur diameter for soil sampling		
Core depth		
Number of cores		
Bulk density soil sample depth(s)		
Monitoring GHG emissions?	Yes: <input type="checkbox"/>	No: <input type="checkbox"/> Comment: <input type="text"/>
Earthworm pit dimensions for earthworm sampling		

Guidelines for soil description (FAO, 2006)

Hierarchy of major landforms

1st level	2nd level	Gradient (%)	Relief intensity (m km ⁻¹)	Potential drainage density
L level land	LP plain	< 10	< 50	0-25
	LL plateau	< 10	< 50	0-25
	LD depression	< 10	< 50	16-25
	LV valley floor	< 10	< 50	6-15
S sloping land	SE medium-gradient escarpment zone	10-30	50-100	< 6
	SH medium-gradient hill	10-30	100-150	0-15
	SM medium-gradient mountain	15-30	150-300	0-15
	SP dissected plain	10-30	50-100	0-15
	SV medium-gradient valley	10-30	100-150	6-15
T steep land	TE high-gradient escarpment zone	> 30	150-300	< 6
	TH high-gradient hill	> 30	150-300	0-15
	TM high-gradient mountain	> 30	> 300	0-15
	TV high-gradient valley	> 30	> 150	6-15

Slope gradient classes

Class	Description	%
01	Flat	0-0.2
02	Level	0.2-0.5
03	Nearly level	0.5-1.0
04	Very gently sloping	1.0-2.0
05	Gently sloping	2-5
06	Sloping	5-10
07	Strongly sloping	10-15
08	Moderately steep	15-30
09	Steep	30-60
10	Very steep	> 60

Continuation Annex 2. 1. Soil sample information sheet.

Field trial details Year 1/Year 2/Year 3/ Year 4 (to fill in each year)										
	Treatment 1- information			Treatment 2- information			Treatment 3- information			
Location										
GPS coordinates										
Ag. management system (encircle or fill in)	Conventional	Organic	Other:...	Conventional	Organic	Other:...	Conventional	Organic	Other:...	
Plot surface (ha)	Number of years:...			Number of years:...			Number of years:...			
Topography (see tables attached this table, columns AB-AK in this Excel sheet*)	Landform:									
	Plot 1:	Plot 2:		Plot 1:	Plot 2:		Plot 1:	Plot 2:		
	Plot 3:	Plot 4:		Plot 3:	Plot 4:		Plot 3:	Plot 4:		
	Slope gradient:									
Plot 1:	Plot 2:		Plot 1:	Plot 2:		Plot 1:	Plot 2:			
Plot 3:	Plot 4:		Plot 3:	Plot 4:		Plot 3:	Plot 4:			
	Orientation									
	Plot 1:	Plot 2:		Plot 1:	Plot 2:		Plot 1:	Plot 2:		
Plot 3:	Plot 4:		Plot 3:	Plot 4:		Plot 3:	Plot 4:			
Sampling event in year (fill in)	Date:	start time:	end time:	Date:	start time:	end time:	Date:	start time:	end time:	
Timing for soil sample	Plot 1:	Plot 2:		Plot 1:	Plot 2:		Plot 1:	Plot 2:		
	Plot 3:	Plot 4:		Plot 3:	Plot 4:		Plot 3:	Plot 4:		
Plot										
Date of sowing or planting										
Date of flowering										
Phenological state during sampling										
Date of harvest										
Plot yield (kg)										
Fertiliser applied	Plot 1:	Plot 2:		Plot 1:	Plot 2:		Plot 1:	Plot 2:		
	Plot 3:	Plot 4:		Plot 3:	Plot 4:		Plot 3:	Plot 4:		
Munsell Soil Color Charts (dry soil)	Plot 1:	Plot 2:		Plot 1:	Plot 2:		Plot 1:	Plot 2:		
	Plot 3:	Plot 4:		Plot 3:	Plot 4:		Plot 3:	Plot 4:		
Munsell Soil Color Charts (wet soil)	Plot 1:	Plot 2:		Plot 1:	Plot 2:		Plot 1:	Plot 2:		
	Plot 3:	Plot 4:		Plot 3:	Plot 4:		Plot 3:	Plot 4:		
Weather conditions (encircle or fill in)	sunny	cloudy	rainy	windy	other:...	sunny	cloudy	rainy	windy	other:...
Air temperature (encircle)	<0°C	0-10	10-20	20-30	>30	<0°C	0-10	10-20	20-30	>30
Soil humidity										
Soil temperature										

ANNEX 2.2 OVERVIEW OF THE SAMPLING EVENT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

WP5 sampling scheme

15/07/2020

Figure adapted from WP3 (Lieven Waeyenberge, ILVO).

ANNEX 2.3. CONSENT TEMPLATE

About SoildiverAgro project: The aim of SoildiverAgro (H2020 project 817819) is to adopt new management practices and cropping systems that enhance soil genetic and functional biodiversity to reduce the use of external inputs while increasing crop production and quality, the delivery of ecosystem services and the EU agricultural stability and resilience.

Purpose of your participation: You are invited to participate in our research study on soil biodiversity status (bacterial, fungal, nematodes and earthworms) in agricultural soils in Europe under the SoildiverAgro project. You will be requested to participate providing authorization for soil and crop sampling in your fields, analyse them and provide us historical data on soil management practices and crop production such as date in which the farming operation was performed, description of the farming operation, type of farm machinery used, products applied to the crop in that farming operation, water applied in each irrigation application, electric power consumed in each irrigation application, labour use in each farming operation and crop production in the case of harvest operations.

Time involvement: This research study may take up to approximately five years after your participation.

Risks and benefits: The risks associated with this study are none. We cannot and do not guarantee or promise that you will receive any benefits from this study. Your decision whether or not to participate in this study will not affect your participation in other SoildiverAgro events and activities.

Payment: You will not receive any reimbursement as payment for your participation.

Rights: Your participation is voluntary and you have the right to refuse to participate and to withdraw your participation, samples or data at any time without any consequences. You have the right to refuse to answer particular questions. Your name and contact data will be always retained confidential, will never be made public, findable or accessible, and you will never be identified or linked to the samples or data. You will be always the owner of data and samples collected. The data will be made accessible to you in a personal communication and/or report.

Use of data/samples: The materials and data collected will become part of studies that may be presented at scientific or professional meetings or published in scientific or professional journals for communication and dissemination purposes of SoildiverAgro project. Personal Data shall be processed only for those administrative, operational, accounting, research and monitoring purposes that are necessary for the safe and reliable implementation of SoildiverAgro, without prejudice to the individual rights under the relevant laws.

Data storage, protection, retention and destruction: Data will be stored securely on private personal hard drives with access key and the private institutional SoildiverAgro DPV to prevent breaches of confidentiality during the period of the project and beyond the lifetime of this project. The University of Vigo protects the DPV from viruses and data piracy and makes periodic back-ups. In the event of the unlikely incidental findings, you will be communicated to decide if you aim to withdraw your data. Personal Data shall be retained until the data derived from sampling, surveys, questionnaires or interviews are scientifically processed and published, and shall be destroyed after a period of 18 months after publication. By default, Personal Data shall be destroyed after a period of 36 months after the finalisation of the SoildiverAgro project.

Contact information: If you have any questions, concerns or complaints about this research, its procedures, risks and benefits, contact the Project Coordinator (Dr. David Fernández Calviño; davidfc@uvigo.es; +34 988 36 8888).

Independent contact: If you are not satisfied with how this study is being conducted, or if you have any concerns, complaints, or general questions about the research or your rights as a participant, please contact Mr Anxo Moreira, Universidade de Vigo (otri9@uvigo.es, +34 986 81 2236) to speak to someone independent of the research team.

Data Protection Officer: Dr. Ana Garriga Domínguez (University of Vigo): dpd@uvigo.es; +34 988 36 8834.

2.1. SAMPLING FOR BULK DENSITY

Lieven Waeyenberge ¹ and Raul Zornoza ²

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Soil bulk density refers to the weight (mass) of soil per unit of volume and is generally expressed in g per cm³. The weight of a soil sample can be determined easily, while collecting a certain volume of soil is less obvious. Thus, to be able to measure the soil bulk density (see section 7.1) of an agricultural field accurately, soil samples should be taken with care.

The sampling procedure selected here is the one using cylindrical cores. Basically, the cylinder is pressed or hammered into the soil. The cylinder is removed gently, thereby extracting a sample of known volume.

The use of a cylindrical core enables the sampler to take a known volume of soil. Previous studies have demonstrated that the type of cylindrical cores does not significantly influence the bulk density measurements. The key factor is that the sampler must remove the core used in such a way that the core remains completely filled with soil.

PROCEDURE

1.

Prepare a flat surface at the first selected sampling spot by scraping away the upper layer with a shovel or spatula.

2.

Press the ring completely into the soil, preferably till 1 cm below the prepared surface. This can be done manually or mechanically using a hammer and a piece of flat wooden plank placed on top of the ring to protect the hammer from the sharp edges of the ring.

3.

Remove the ring with the help of a spatula or shovel. Be sure to avoid that soil falls down from the ring.

4.

Remove excessive soil with a knife until the upper and lower surface of the soil in the cylinder is flat.

5.

Close both sides of the ring if you are going to transport the soil within the ring. If you are going to use the same ring for several samples or you do not have the lids to close the rings, transfer the soil of a ring to a plastic bag and code it properly. Close the bag with a twist tie.

6.

Dig out the same spot till a depth of 15 cm, press the same or another ring (depending on whether you emptied and cleaned the already used ring or not) into the prepared surface manually or mechanically using the core sampler, and repeat steps 3 till 5.

7.

Repeat the whole procedure (Steps 1-6) on an additional 4 spots well spread over the selected field (approximate area of 1 ha).

8.

In the lab: store the soil samples at room temperature.

The sampling procedure can also be viewed in the following video on YouTube:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JQav_fx69aU

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Metal rings with known volume, preferably with removable lids at both ends
- Sampling bags and twist tie
- Marker
- Spatula and/or shovel
- Hammer
- Knife
- Piece of flat wooden plank
- Retractable tape measure
- Core sampler

Photo 2.1.1 Equipment for soil bulk density sampling. Credits: Lieven Waeyenberge, ILVO

CALCULATIONS

No calculations are made during sampling and pre-processing. To measure the bulk density, section 7.1. should be consulted.

REMARKS

The method is not intended for loose, sandy soils. Additionally, dry or hard soils can shatter when the cylinder is hammered in the soil. In this case, pressing the cylinder into the soil reduces the risk of shattering the sample.

The cylindrical cores should have a thin, sharp edge to avoid compaction during sampling. If compression is excessive, the soil core may not be a valid sample for analysis. Rock fragments can damage the cores and interfere with the sampling.

2.2. SAMPLING FOR GENERAL SOIL CHARACTERISTICS, MICROBIAL DIVERSITY AND NEMATODES DIVERSITY

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

A composite soil sample is taken to assess a number of general soil characteristics and the microbial and nematode diversity. The sample is composed of several cores taken by a core sampler on a part of an agricultural field with an area of approximately 1 ha following a straight line between the remainders of the crop or following a zig-zag pattern across the field. The total number of cores taken depends on the length and the diameter of the core sampler. The length of the soil core should be 25 cm. The diameter of the core sampler is variable. However, the soil composite sample should be at least 1,5 l or 2 kg.

At arrival in the lab, after sampling, the soil samples have to be homogenized manually (not mechanically to avoid damage of nematodes) and divided into different parts:

- a minimum of 25 grams of each composite sample is transferred into a plastic tube (Falcon tube) using a spoon or spatula. This tube is sent to UCPH (Kristian Koefoed Brandt) for bacterial and archaeal genetic diversity analysis; a second tube again with a minimum of 25 grams is to be sent to UPCT (Raúl Zornoza) for some chemical properties and micro-organisms assessments. Before dividing the next sample, another clean spoon or spatula is used or the spoon or spatula is cleaned (70% ethanol).
- the remainder of the soil sample is split into 2 equal parts (minimum of 500 mL each). One part is sent to EV-ILVO (Waeyenberge Lieven) for the nematode functional biodiversity assessment. The other part is dried at room temperature for several nights (possibly 5 to 7 nights depending on soil moisture) and sent to UPCT (Raúl Zornoza) for soil physical and other chemical measurements.

Table 2.2.1. provides an overview of the partners receiving samples and the downstream analyses that each partner is responsible for.

Dried samples for soil physical and other chemical properties are stored at room temperature as the lack of water ensures preservation. The remaining field-moist samples are stored at 4°C until shipment to minimize changes in the analysed soil biological properties. Field-moist samples should be sent as soon as possible (express delivery) with cold packs included in the package. For nematodes, it is recommended to analyse samples within a month (better few weeks). Upon arrival in the receiving laboratory, samples for microbial diversity assessment may be stored frozen at -20°C for several weeks or at -80°C for several months prior to analysis. A list with sample codes and any valuable information are added in the transport box. This information is also sent by e-mail to the representative partner with the message that samples are coming. Answering with an email confirming availability for receiving samples in the coming days is desirable before sending the samples.

Table 2.2.1. Partners responsible for the acquisition of different types of data

PARTNERS IN CHARGE OF DATA ACQUISITION		
ANALYSIS TYPE	PARTNER IN CHARGE	SAMPLE ORIGIN (PEDOCLIMATIC REGIONS*)
Physical and chemical soil characteristics	UVIGO & UPCT	All
Nematode diversity	EV-ILVO	All
Whole microbial diversity	UVIGO	All
Bacterial and archaeal genetic diversity	UCPH	All
Fungal & mycorrhizal genetic diversity	LUKE	All
Microbial functional diversity	UPCT	All
Earthworm diversity	TI	ATN, CON
	EV-ILVO	ATC, PAN
	LUKE	BOR
	UVIGO	LUS, MDN, MDS
	EULS	NEM

(*) Pedoclimatic regions: ATC = Atlantic Central, ATN = Atlantic North, BOR = Boreal, CON = Continental, LUS = Lusitanian, MDN = Mediterranean North, MDS = Mediterranean South, NEM = Nemoral, PAN = Pannonian.

PROCEDURE

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Sampling bags and twist tie
- Marker
- Core sampler with thumb
- Spray bottle with 70% ethanol
- Roll of paper
- Cool box with cool packs (when temperature is above 15°C)

Photo 2.2.1 Equipment for soil sampling.
Credits: Lieven Waeyenberge, ILVO

1.

Before going to the field, label strong plastic sampling bags appropriately: code of pedoclimatic region + 'C' or 'O' for conventional or organic farming + unique code of the field. One field = one plastic bag.

2.

After arriving at the location, note the GPS coordinates if not known yet.

3.

Take a soil sample spread all over an area of 1 ha. The easiest way is to follow a zig-zag pattern (A) or a pattern with straight lines (B). Go 3 times from one end to the other end of the field, trying to cover the whole area of 1 ha but avoiding coming too close to the borders. Each time you cross the field, take 20 cores using the core sampler. Thus, in total 60 cores, one at each 60 sampling points, are taken. Move approximately 6-7 steps (representing 5 m) between each core taken. When the field has an irregular form, adapt your sampling pattern accordingly.

4.

At each sampling point, press the core sampler vertically in the soil. Use both hands if needed.

5.

Twist the core sampler half turn and pull it out in a slight angle in an attempt to keep the soil core positioned into the core sampler.

6.

Move the core sampler into the already labelled plastic bag and use the thumb to release the soil from the core sampler into the plastic bag.

7.

Go to the next sampling point and repeat this procedure until all sampling points are sampled.

8.

Close the sample bag with a twist tie and place it in a cool box, with cool packs when the weather is more than 15°C, to protect the sample from heat and light.

9.

Before going to the next field, the sampling material (core sampler and thumb) is disinfected with 70% ethanol and wiped dry with paper. This should especially prevent carry-over of soil containing organisms from one sample to the other.

CALCULATIONS

No calculations are made during sampling and pre-processing. Consult the next chapters for more information concerning the subsequent analyses.

REMARKS

It should be avoided to take soil samples that are very wet or very dry. If conditions are not favourable, it is recommended to postpone the sampling by a couple of days.

It is recommended not to use sampling bags with a zip lock. The zip lock is not strong enough to keep the bag closed at all times. It can easily cause spilling of soil into the cool box or even cause carry-over of soil from one sampling bag into the other.

Photo 2.2.2 Demonstrating how to take a soil sample (lower parts) and how to close the sampling bag properly (upper part). Credits: Lieven, Waeyenberge, ILVO.

2.3. SAMPLING FOR EARTHWORM DIVERSITY

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Digging and hand-sorting of soil is the most widely used standard method to collect earthworms. However, it is not very efficient in capturing deep burrowing anecic earthworms, and for this reason, it is usually combined with chemical expelling by a vermifuge (Bartlett et al. 2010); here the active agent in mustard, allyl isothiocyanate (AITC; mustard oil) will be used as described in ISO 23611-1:2018. From each sampling site three replicate samples has to be taken (i.e. sampling of 3 different quadrats) to account for spatial variability.

In the following, the systematic procedure is described and explained in three steps:

- **Hand-sorting of soil samples in the field**
- **Chemical expelling of deep burrowers from the same quadrats**
- **Processing of the collected live material in the field or laboratory**

PROCEDURE

Hand-sorting in the field

Hand-sorting is a physical or passive method where the earthworms are directly removed from the soil by hand.

Place the first quadrat on the soil surface at a random location or mark the area (Fig. 2.3.1.). Do not sample areas where you have walked just before. Cut and remove the aboveground vegetation (do not pull the roots out). If there is a litter layer, please check it carefully for any earthworms.

Fig. 2.3.1. Area for earthworm sampling defined by a quadrat (left) or marked (right).

Photo credits: <http://www.ucd.ie/agbiota/studies/worms.htm> (left); <https://worms.educ.ualberta.ca/quadrat.html> (right)

Excavate a 50 cm x 50 cm x 25 cm deep soil block (cut along edges of your marked area), unless the clay content of your soil is more than 50%, in which case the sampled area can be reduced to 25 x 25 x 25 cm. Place the intact soil block on the plastic sheet (e.g. bin liner) or a large tray (Fig. 2.3.2.). This is needed to prevent earthworms from escaping. Sort through soil manually; carefully check the roots. Please wear disposable protective gloves. The sampled earthworms should be soon transferred into labelled plastic containers, which should be filled with moist soil from the pit. Once the soil is sorted return it back into soil pit and leave the spot in a tidy state.

To avoid mortality keep the containers with the earthworms in cool conditions (e.g. in a cool box) and away from direct sunlight until they can be processed. Repeat this procedure at two other random locations. Keep each replicate sample separate throughout the sorting process.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Wire or wooden frames (50 cm x 50 cm) or simply mark the area with sticks
- Garden scissors (secateurs)
- Spade (flat blade if possible)
- Large plastic sheets (e.g. a large bin bag or trays)
- Tweezers/forceps, labels, permanent markers
- Plastic containers with lids (Tupperware, lock&lock)
- Cool box and ice packs
- Disposable protective gloves

Fig. 2.3.2. Excavated soil placed on a large tray (left) and large plastic sheet (right). Photo credit: <https://soils.sectormentor.com/case-study/building-soil-health-5-key-soil-tests-to-get-you-started/>

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- **Allyl-isothiocyanate (AITC), synthetic grade (about 94% to 97% (volume fraction)). [Aldrich 37,743-0]**
- **Isopropanol [2-propanol] 100 % (volume fraction).**
- **Test tubes or vials (50 mL) for stock solution**
- **F-style jugs or watering cans (Fig. 2.3.3.).**

Fig.2.3.3. F-style jug (left) and watering can (right). Image credits: <https://www.containerandpackaging.com/products/65/pvc-f-style-bottle/B048> (left) and <https://www.spottygreenfrog.co.uk/Set-of-Four-Watering-Cans/p-204-105-361-1020/>

- **Tap water**
- **Plastic containers with lids (Tupperware, lock&lock)**
- **Tweezers/forceps, labels, permanent markers**
- **Cool box and ice packs**
- **Disposable protective gloves**

Chemical expelling of deep burrowers in the same quadrats

Chemical expelling is an active method where earthworms are irritated and forced to leave the soil.

The stock solution should be prepared under a laboratory fume hood for safety reasons because AITC is a toxic irritant. Please wear disposable protective gloves, strictly avoid all skin contact and inhalation and carefully protect eyes. In the lab, mix 2 mL allyl- isothiocyanate into 40 mL isopropanol (to provide a 5 g L⁻¹ stock solution) in small bottles that can be easily transported to the field (in cool boxes). Because AITC is not readily soluble in water, alcohol acts as an emulsifier when AITC is added to water. Store the stock solution in a fridge and no longer than 5 days before usage.

Just before application in the field, dilute the stock solution (42 ml (2 ml AITC + 40 ml propanol) with 20 L water to give a final concentration of approximately 0.1 g L⁻¹ (Zaborski 2003; Pelosi et al. 2009) in F-style jugs or watering cans and mix vigorously.

Use 10 L of the mixture per quadrat (or 20 L depending on the soil conditions; e.g. if the soil is too dry) by pouring it down into the bottom of the pit after the soil block has been excavated. Optional: pour half of the mustard solution evenly across the quadrat, and after about 15 minutes, pour the remaining solution. In case of a very low infiltration rate, less than 10 litres of mixture will suffice.

Sit next to the sampling spot and collect the expelled earthworms with forceps from inside of the sampling area as they emerge (only collect earthworms once they have left their burrows completely). Transfer the collected worms to containers containing clean tap water to rinse off the irritant. Soon after, they can be placed in labelled plastic containers filled with moist (clean) soil.

After the whole AITC solution is added, continue to monitor the plot because earthworms might crawl out; the biggest ones often take the longest time to emerge. Collect all the earthworms for 15-20 minutes before moving to the next plot.

Processing the collected live material in the field or laboratory

Rinse each subsample of earthworms with tap water and blot on paper towels. Place the live earthworms in a deep Petri dish/ plastic container containing a fixing solution (1:1; 4% formalin:96% ethanol) for 2 minutes or until they stop moving.

Put 1-3 earthworms one at a time (rather than a whole handful all at once) so they do not get tangled up into a big mess of earthworms. Please wear disposable protective gloves and avoid inhalation and skin contact.

Thereafter, carefully extend every specimen onto a flat surface (or the upturned lid of a Tupperware; Figure 2.3.4.) and after 3-5 minutes they can be placed in a leak proof vial containing 4% formalin labelled both outside and inside (pencil written label in the liquid). Store the vials in horizontal position for at least 24 hours to allow enough time for the soft tissues to be fixed.

Once the earthworms have been in formalin for at least 24 hours, change the solution (if after that time it becomes too cloudy). The worms can now be stored in the formalin 4% until further identification (long-term storage). Alternatively, 70% ethanol (volume fraction) can be used instead for long-term storage.

In addition to species identification, the total biomass of the preserved individuals collected per replicate is a useful parameter and can be determined using a balance with a precision of 0.01 g. For details see section 5.1.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Tissue paper/paper towels
- Analytical balance (0.01 g)
- Petri dishes or a plastic container
- Formalin, formaldehyde solution 4 % (volume fraction), for storage purposes only
- Ethanol 70% and 96%
- Tweezers/forceps, labels, permanent markers, pencil
- Test tubes or vials
- Disposable protective gloves

Fig. 2.3.4. Earthworms placed onto a flat upturned lid of a Tupperware for careful extension before storage. Photo credit: <https://www.earthwormsoc.org.uk/sampling>

CALCULATIONS

Present all data on abundance and biomass as individuals per square meter (ind m⁻²) and grams per square meter (g m⁻²), respectively. For details see section 5.1.

REMARKS

Labelling

Note the coding for site and plot (= sampling pit), sampling date, coordinates, dominant vegetation, and person in charge.

Timings

- Marking and cleaning each quadrat (10 minutes per replicate)
- Collecting earthworms i.e. hand-sorting and chemical expelling (30-60 minutes)
- Washing the worms, drying and weighing the worms (5 minutes per replicate depending on the numbers)
- Fixing the material and placing it in labelled vials (15 minutes per replicate depending on the numbers)

Recommendations

- Take samples when soil is sufficiently moist, and the earthworms are active. These conditions vary by region, climate, vegetation, land use, etc., but usually coincide with the rainy season. For temperate regions in the Northern Hemisphere, the best time would be spring and fall; in areas with only dry and wet seasons, the end of the wet season is recommended.
- In case of sunny weather, an umbrella for protecting the crawling earthworms in the pit from direct UV-radiation is recommendable.
- The fixing of earthworms can also be done in the field for logistic reasons; for instance, when processing the collected specimens needs to be delayed (e.g. long distances between the sampling site and the laboratory) or if there is a risk that temperatures during storage get too high. If this is the case, earthworms can be transferred to cool water (instead of fresh soil) and from there to the fixing solution and then carefully extended (see above).

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3. CROP GROWTH, INCIDENCE OF PESTS/DISEASES AND CROP YIELD EVALUATION

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Sustainability substantiates on three main pillars, which are the social, economic and environmental, commonly represented by three intersecting circles with overall sustainability at the centre (Fig. 3.1.).

Fig. 3.1. Representation of sustainability as three intersecting circles

As a consequence, there is no sustainable agriculture if only on pillar is assessed, and only improvement in soil quality and biodiversity is achieved. Farmer revenues highly depend on crop production and quality, and so, any proposed practice must be conceived with the aim of ensuring high production of secure and quality food. For this reason, the evaluation of crop growth and crop yield are essential to conclude if a specific management practice is sustainable, since there should not be detrimental effects on crop production, at least below a threshold under that farmers may not depend on that cultivation, always subject to market price fluctuations and production costs.

Moreover, one of the main goals of SoildiverAgro is elucidate the link between soil biodiversity and crop growth and crop production, so that a proper determination of these indicators is needed to further infer those relations by means of the proper statistical analyses. Besides soil quality and fertility, crop growth and production is conditioned by the incidence of pests and diseases, which can devastate entire fields if they are not properly controlled. There are some strategies to reduce the incidence of pests and diseases, based on prevention first, and on control once they appear. The enhancement of soil biodiversity can contribute to promote plant health and protection against diseases. Hence, a proper methodology to monitor the incidence of crop and diseases is vital to properly assess if changes in soil biological communities can reduce this incidence by enhancing plant health or reducing pathogens abundance.

In the following chapters we define the methodology proposed to assess crop growth, crop yield and monitor pests and diseases in the field experiments established in SoildiverAgro WP5 so that they can be easily performed by case study leaders.

3.1. CROP GROWTH

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Crop growth is an indicator about the proper development of a crop within its cycle, giving information about the development of the different phenological stages of the plant. Commercially, it can be interesting whether to favour that harvest comes early in time, or to delay harvest, depending on markets fluctuations and conditions. Weather conditions and pest/disease incidences can alter crop growth and so the crop cycle, but also management practices can affect crop growth by improving or declining soil fertility and quality (García-López et al. 2019; Mo et al. 2016; Liu et al. 2018).

The crop growth of arable crops can be controlled with measurement of the aboveground biomass (Álvaro-Fuentes et al. 2019) or by the corresponding period length of a specific phenological stage (Liu et al. 2018). In this chapter we propose this second method selecting flowering and harvest as specific phenological stages to assess crop growth, owing to its simplicity but important information derived concerning anticipation or delay of the crop cycle.

PROCEDURE

- Split the farm in different plots to assess crop growth. The size can be variable depending on the specific crop type. It is recommended that plots are not smaller than 200 m².
- Note exactly the date of crop sowing or plantation in case of seedlings.
- Monitor the evolution of the crop in each plot and note the exact date when at least 75% of plants reach the flowering phenological stage.
- Continue monitoring the crop and note the exact date when crop is harvested.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Notebook with a table to monitor the corresponding period lengths (Table 3.1.1).

CALCULATIONS

The growth period length f is calculated as:

- Growth period length for flowering (day) = days from sowing/planting to flowering (>75% of total plants).

- Growth period length for harvest (days) = days from sowing/planting to harvest.

Table 3.1.1. Example of template to monitor the crop growth length

Plot number	Crop type	Sowing/planting	>75% of plants at flowering	Harvest
		date	date	date

PROCEDURE

- Álvaro-Fuentes, J, D Lóczy, S Thiele-Bruhn, and R Zornoza Belmonte. 2019. Handbook of Plant and Soil Analysis for Agricultural Systems. Edited by Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena.
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3.2. INCIDENCE OF PESTS AND DISEASES

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

The objectives of sampling or monitoring are to detect the presence or absence of pests, quantify their abundance and their natural enemies and follow the progress of an arthropod population or a disease, through time by regular, periodic sampling. The goal of monitoring is to reach a decision as to whether, or when, a pest population requires control action. Monitoring means checking the field to identify which pests are present, how many there are, or what damage they have caused. Correctly identifying the pest is key to knowing whether a pest is likely to become a problem and to determining the best management strategy. The parameters most frequently used are (Álvarez-Fuentes et al. 2019):

- Pest Populations.
- Disease Incidence.
- Damage Proportion.

Pest monitoring is site, crop and pest-specific so giving a general methodology is difficult. Each situation will require specialized knowledge and tools, however some practical standards are reported.

PROCEDURE

1. Choose the plots where to sample with homogeneity (with the same variety, previous cultivation, planting date, management, ...) and representativeness criteria.
2. Install in the plot the necessary traps for monitoring some flying insects, if more strict control is needed besides visual checking.
3. Conduct periodic samplings of pests and diseases, by direct measures (visual checking) or by indirect measures (monitoring the traps to assess the insects trapped).

3.1 Visual checking

The most common way of making measurements for the sampling of pests and diseases is by visual checking. In the case of pests, measures can be direct counting of pests, or indirect measuring of the effect of pest damage and pest products, such as skin, casts, frass, nests, etc. The entire plant, or parts of it, may be used to estimate the pest population. Knowing the biology or behaviour of the pest can be very helpful when choosing the strata or parts of the plant in which the population is more abundant, presents a more homogeneous distribution, and/or shows a closer relation with the total population. It is also useful to know the state or stage of development of the most representative arthropod of the total population. It must be noted that the common dispersion patterns of pests in the field are random, uniform, and clumped, even many pest populations tend to be clumped, as well as deciding the sampling accuracy. All this facilitates the choice of the sampling unit.

For diseases, you have to consider that it may be caused by fungi, bacteria or viruses. Identify the causal agent. knowing its chronology in the crop is very useful. To determine the incidence of the disease, the number of plants, leaves, flowers, etc., that are infected or killed by fungi, bacteria or viruses is counted.

Visual observations will be made weekly or biweekly in the critical periods of each harmful agent. Depending on the surface of the plot, the Main Sampling Unit (MSU) varies as:

- In plots ≤ 4 ha: select 25 plants, 4 squares of 1.25 m² or 2 sections of 25 m long across the seeding line per plot.
- In plots > 4 ha: select 50 plants, 1 square of 1.25 m² or one section of 25 m long across the seeding line per ha.

In cereals, it is recommended (Koyshibayey and Muminjanov, 2016):

- to select the plant as MSU to assess the roots affected by aphids, Hessian fly, Cerambycidae, neck and root diseases, Septoria leaf.
- to select the square as MSU to assess wheat bugs, powdery mildew, leaf and yellow rust, helminthosporium leaf blight and scald.
- to select the section of 25 m long as MSU to assess the plants killed by wireworms.

In other crops (Campos and Ortiz, 2020):

- In the case of wireworms and cotton leafworm or cutworms, all the plants of 4 sections of 25 meters long will be observed in plots of less than 4 ha, or more lines of 25 meters in larger plots to determine percentage of fallen plants.
- In the case of heliotis, cabbage lopper and defoliating caterpillars, all the plants of 4 squares of 1.25 m² will be sampled in plots of less than 4 ha, or more squares of 1.25 m² in plots of more than 4 ha. The number of larvae per ha is counted.
- In the case of red spider, eriophids, aphids, oidiopsis, mildew, alternariosis, gray rot, neck and root rot, root rot, vascular diseases and black spot, 25 or 50 plants will be randomly sampled according to size of the plot. The percentage of occupied plants is determined.
- In the case of thrips, the sampling will be carried out on a leaf of the apical third of 25 plants if the plot is less than 4 ha, or 50 plants if the plot is greater than 4 ha. The number of larvae per leaf is counted.
- In the case of whiteflies, observations will be made on a leaf from the lower third of 25 plants if the plot is less than 4 ha, or 50 plants if the plot is larger. The number of nymphs per leaf is determined.
- In the case of the potato beetle, 25 plants are taken for every 4 ha of cultivation or 50 for larger plots and the number of larvae and adults in each plant is counted.
- For the potato moth, delta-type sex pheromone traps are used to detect the increase in adult flight.

3.2 Use of traps

FEROMONA TRAPS

Several kinds of traps are widely used to help monitor certain pests. They will be suitable tools for checking population activity and getting information for setting the action threshold. Traps will be installed in the different plots for monitoring or following the flight of adults, such as Delta type (Fig. 3.2.1a) or Funnel type (Fig. 3.2.1b) with specific pheromones for each insect.

Especially known are the pheromones of lepidoptera, tortricides and noctuides, and also some beetles, such as some diaspino coccidus. These sex pheromones are usually very specific and are marketed together with traps for the capture of insects with the indication of the number of traps per surface and the duration of the effect of the pheromone. Traps should be placed at least every 100 meters. It is common to use Delta-type traps to monitor potato moths (*Phthorimaea operculella*) and Funnel-type for *Heliothis* spp., cabbage looper and defoliating caterpillars in horticultural crops.

YELLOW STICKY TRAPS

Some insects are attracted to bright yellow or other colors so they can be caught on colored sheets of plastic or cardboard that has been coated with glue. Yellow sticky traps can be used for monitoring most pests, including whiteflies, thrips, winger aphids, leafminer, scales and many others (Fig.3.2.1c). They may also capture parasitic wasps. By regularly checking the sticky traps a grower can find out when the first of the adult insects are present among the plants.

Figure 3.2.1. a) Delta trap ; b) Funnel trap; c) Yellow sticky traps

Each trap will be suspended on a support (stake, sheaf, stick ...) at the height of the crop, so that as the plant grows we can gradually raise the trap. It is useful to place a plastic tape or other visible sign in the distance, at the upper end of the support so that we can locate it once the crop reaches its maximum vegetative development, or for it to be seen by the farm operators and avoid that can be hit with agricultural machinery. Weekly or every fifteen days, the number of individuals captured in each trap should be counted, then emptied, not forgetting to leave the pheromone inside.

CALCULATIONS

To determine the disease incidence, the following expression is applied:

$$\text{Disease incidence (\%)} = \left[\frac{\text{Plants diseased}}{\text{Total plants}} \right] \times 100$$

To determine the damage proportion, previous to harvest, the number of damaged plants (whose production would be null) will be counted, by identification of the species responsible for the depredation. The following expression is applied:

$$\text{Damage proportion (\%)} = \left[\frac{\text{Damaged plants with no production}}{\text{Total plants}} \right] \times 100$$

To determine the catch rate of pests (ATD: Adults per Trap and Day), the following expression is applied (voluntary).

$$\text{Adults per Trap and Day (ATD)} = \frac{\text{No. of adults captured}}{\text{Number of traps} \times \text{Number of days passed}}$$

REMARKS

To identify the type of pests and diseases or more details on sampling you can use regional/local handbooks and manuals or ask field technicians expert in pests and diseases.

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3.3. CROP YIELD

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Crop yield is known as the quantity of agricultural production harvested per unit of land area. Crop yield is the metrics most widely used to assess the productivity of a farm and the related economic benefits, and it is normally expressed as kilograms (or metric tons) per hectare. In addition, crop yield can be also referred as the quantity of useful parts or economic product of a crop harvested at an appropriate development stage on a unit of land area (Fischer 2015).

To estimate crop yield, the amount of the harvested product (grain, tuber, etc.) for a given crop is weighed in a sample area (Álvaro-Fuentes et al. 2019).

PROCEDURE

Crop yield can be measured by harvesting completely each experimental plot using either a commercial combine harvester or an experimental combine harvester for grains and tubers, or manually if it is the case for the particular crop, depending on the cultural practice of the region. If you use a combine harvester, pay attention that the machine does not lose too much grain.

Harvest all the commercial product in the harvesting area and place it in a bag/basket, and, finally, weigh the product collected.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Harvester.
- Balance.
- Bags/baskets.
- Data recording sheet/ Notebook.
- Recording material (pen, pencil, ...).

REMARKS

In multiple cropping or intercropping systems, the yield of each crop obtained within a given year and piece of land must be summed to obtain an annual land production value.

CALCULATIONS

To determine the crop yield, the following expression is applied:

$$\text{Crop yield (kg/ha)} = (\text{total weight of the commercial product (kg)}) / (\text{harvested area (ha)})$$

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4. CROP QUALITY AND NUTRITION EVALUATION

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When analyzing the results of a crop, it is important to consider, in addition to the quantity, the quality and nutritional value of the product obtained. These parameters, that include protein content, starch content, specific grain weight, moisture content and flour yield, among others, are the ones that will condition the use that can be given to the product and, therefore, its sale price.

The quality and nutritional composition of a crop will depend on factors inherent to the growing area such as soil conditions and climate, that is, the pedoclimatic region in which the crop is located, but they will be also influenced by other factors that depend on the type of agriculture that is carried out. The quality of the crop will be conditioned, for example, by the quality of the seed (the presence or absence of adventitious plants), the quality of the soil (structure, biodiversity, chemical composition, etc.) and the quality of the irrigation water, the type of tillage, and the fertilization and pest control methods employed.

The indicators that determine the quality of each crop are similar but not exactly the same, so the methods used to analyze each of these properties are slightly different depending on the crop. Throughout this section, the methods used to determine the quality of cereals, legumes, and some vegetables will be considered. Table 4.1 summarizes the characteristics related to nutritional quality and composition that are going to be measured throughout WP5.

Table 4.1. Analysis used to characterize the crop quality of the samples and partners in charge of the analysis.

QUALITY AND NUTITIONAL PROPERTIES MEASURED	
CROP	Analysis type
Cereals and legumes	Specific grain/legume weight
	Flour yield
	Moisture content
	Ash content
	Protein and nitrogen content
	Starch content
Vegetables, fruits and tubers	Vegetable/Fruit/Tuber weight
	Size distribution
	Flesh firmness
	Starch content (only for potatoes)

4.1. CEREALS AND LEGUMES

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Cereals are plants of the Poaceae family (gramineous) whose cultivation produces a large part of the calories ($\approx 35\%$) consumed by humans (Neumann et al. 2010). Since the 1960s, cereal production has grown enormously: in the case of wheat or rice it has tripled, for example (FAO 1997). The latter is mainly due to the intensive production of grain and the use of inputs, since the area of cultivated land devoted to these crops has not grown in proportion.

Legumes are the seeds of fabaceous plants (Fabaceae), and include beans, peas, lentils, chickpeas, lupins, and soybeans, among others (Steib et al. 2020). Legumes have been cultivated for years since they are an important source of vegetal proteins, carbohydrates, fibre, minerals, and vitamins. Furthermore, in recent years, the consumption of legumes has been found to possess certain beneficial effects: for example, it has been found to reduce the amounts of LDL (Rebello, Greenway, and Finley 2014), as well as the concentration of insulin and glucose in blood (Becerra-Tomás et al. 2018).

To determine the quality and nutrient content of cereals and legumes, the following properties can be measured: specific grain weight, flour yield, moisture content, ash content, protein content and starch content.

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4.1.1. SPECIFIC GRAIN/LEGUME WEIGHT

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

When determining the quality of cereals and legumes, one of the most used parameters, in addition to humidity, is the specific grain (or legumes) weight, i.e., the volume occupied by a given quantity (mass) of grain (or legumes), since it is easily determined (Hook 1984; Levy Häner et al. 2013). It is a characteristic that some authors associate with the potential flour yield (Baker, Fifield, and Jartsing 1965). In the case of wheat, for example, depending on the density of the endosperm and on the amount of water, the specific grain weight can vary greatly, between 60 and 90 Kg hL⁻¹. Moreover, some soil characteristics condition this property: for example, the amount of nitrogen in the soil increases the specific weight of some varieties of wheat (Clarke, Gooding, and Jones 2004). The specific weight is a very useful feature when storing grain.

PROCEDURE

For the determination of the specific grain (and legumes) weight, we can follow the UNE-EN ISO 7971-2: 2019 "Cereals. Determination of the volumetric density, called weight per hectolitre". The procedure is the following:

- A 0.5 L test tube is weighted.
- The test tube is filled to the mark with grain (or legumes).
- The weight in grams of the sample is determined on a balance.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- 0.5 L test tube
- Analytical balance (0.01 g)
- Spatula

CALCULATIONS

In order to calculate the specific grain (and legumes) weight (in Kg hL⁻¹), the following equation is employed:

$$\text{Specific Weight} = \frac{\text{Grain (or Legumes) Weight (g)}}{0.5 (L)} \times 0.1$$

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4.1.2. GRAIN AND LEGUME MOISTURE

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

The moisture of grains and legumes is a fundamental aspect that indicates the maturation and can be used to point the moment of the harvest. The amount of water is the characteristic that determines the period that the grain can remain stored (May and Van Sanford, 1992). During the maturation of grains and legumes the amount of dry matter typically increases steadily while water filling occurs mainly in the first days (Schnyder and Baum, 1992). In the case of grain, when it reaches 33% of dry matter (in weight), it stops accumulating water and continues storing dry material until it reaches a proportion of 55% in weight. The loss of ability to absorb water from the grain coincides with the end of the nuclear division of the endosperm.

PROCEDURE

The moisture determination is executed following the UNE-EN ISO 712 standard "Cereals and derived products. Determination of moisture content. Reference method". The procedure is the following:

- First, an aluminium tray and about 25 g of grain are weighed. It is important to write down the exact weight.
- The tray with the grain is introduced in an oven at 130°C until constant weight.
- The tray is reweighed when constant weight is reached.
- For legumes we used the same procedure.

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EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Aluminium tray
- Analytical balance (0.01 g)
- Oven
- Spatula

CALCULATIONS

The percentage of moisture in the grain or in the legume is calculated with the equation:

$$\%H = \frac{M_T - M_{dry}}{M_T} \times 100$$

Where,

M_T is the weight of grain or the legume at room temperature.

M_{dry} is the weight of dry grain or legume.

4.1.3. FLOUR YIELD

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Cereal seeds are made up of several parts, and bran, germ and endosperm can usually be distinguished (Mog 1991). To obtain flour using cereals or legumes it is necessary to mill them, but depending on the parts used during the milling procedure we can obtain different types of flour. Thus, for example, white flour is obtained by discarding the bran of the grain, while whole flour is the one that preserves this part. The consume of the latter has been increased recently in order to add fiber to the diet (Rieder et al. 2012).

With the expression flour yield, we usually speak of white flour. And this performance depends on the milling process: the purpose of this procedure is to separate the endosperm part of the grain to obtain white flour (Antoine et al. 2004). The details of this milling affect the economic value as well as the quality of the product obtained (Mog 1991).

PROCEDURE

The procedure to determine the grain yield is the following: 100 g of grain, with a known humidity (this can be determined by the method proposed in 4.1.2. Grain and legume moisture), are weighed. To make the bran less brittle, the grain or the legume is previously moistened until it has between 15 and 17% moisture (Cardós, Campaña, and Abbate 2017). In this way, a flour with less amount of bran flakes will be obtained. In addition, since all the samples have the same humidity, comparable data can be obtained since the flour yield will fluctuate depending on the humidity of the sample.

Next, the sample is introduced into a roller mill which will break the grains and the protective covers. Subsequently, the material obtained is sieved (470 µm) (Kweon, Martin, and Souza 2009) to separate the bran, while the material that passes through the sieve is milled until reaching the desired grain size. Flour yield is usually provided for one moisture level.

Depending on the size of the grain and on the crop (barley, wheat, corn, lentil, bean, etc), the intensity of the milling, the adequate amount of moisture and the size of the sieve used can vary.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Balance.
- Distilled water.
- Stove.
- Mill.
- Sieve.

CALCULATIONS

In order to calculate % of flour yield the following equation is applied:

$$\% \text{ flour yield} = \frac{(\text{Grain or Legume Weight} - \text{Bran Weight})}{\text{Grain or Legume Weight}} \times 100$$

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4.1.4. NITROGEN AND PROTEIN CONTENT OF GRAINS AND LEGUMES

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

The protein content is a characteristic that greatly conditions the quality of grains and legumes, as well as their destination and market value (Hare 2017). For example, a grain that has a protein content lower than 11.5% (by weight) is not suitable for pasta production.

There is a very close relationship between the amount of protein in a grain and its richness in nitrogen: the availability of nitrogen causes crops to produce protein-rich grains (Jones and Olson-Rutz 2012). This is because nitrogen is an essential component of amino acids. It has been proven that, in addition to nitrogen fertilization, some environmental factors such as drought or high temperatures during the ripening of the grain, produce cereals with higher protein content, but in these last cases, the yield is usually affected.

The amount of protein in the grain can be determined through the nitrogen content of the sample. The Kjeldahl method (ISO 20483:2013 2013) can be used to determine the amount of nitrogen. Then, by multiplying the nitrogen content by 5.7, which is the factor of conversion for wheat (Kowalczewski et al. 2019), the amount of protein is obtained. To obtain the protein content of other grains or legumes, another factor of conversion of nitrogen can be used (Mossé 1990; Mariotti, Tomé, and Mirand 2008).

PROCEDURE

The process for determining nitrogen in wheat is presented below. For other grains and legumes, the method is the same.

The procedure to determine the amount of nitrogen in wheat begins with the digestion, which consists of the following steps:

- Weigh 1 g of sample (grinded and homogenized) and place it in a digestion tube.
- Add 5 g of Kjeldahl catalyst to the tube with the sample, and 10 mL of 95-98 % sulphuric acid.
- Place the digestion tubes with the samples in a digester unit (Bloc-digest) with the smoke collector running, and perform the digestion at a temperature of 400°C for 30 minutes.
- Allow the sample to cool to room temperature.
- Slowly add 50 ml of distilled water. This should be done carefully, slowly dropping water through the walls of the tube.

The next part of the procedure includes neutralization and distillation:

- Add 25 mL of boric acid in a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask and 2 or 3 drops of mixed indicator.
- Submerge the refrigerant extension in the Erlenmeyer with the boric acid solution.
- Place the tube with the sample on the left side of the distiller, and add 2 or 3 drops of phenolphthalein.
- Once the sample tube and the Erlenmeyer are placed with boric acid, add the solution of NaOH (35%) until the colour change and start the distillation. Distillation should be prolonged long enough for a minimum of 150 mL to be distilled, approximately 5 to 10 minutes.

The last step is the titration:

- The distillate obtained is titrated with 0.31N hydrochloric acid, until the solution turns from green to violet.
- The same is done with a blank.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Digestion tubes
- Digester unit (Bloc-Digest)
- Fume collector/extractor
- Erlenmeyer flasks
- Distiller
- Burette
- Laboratory mill
- Analytical balance (0.01 g)

REAGENTS

- Sulphuric Acid (95-98%)
- NaOH solution (35%)
- Mixed indicator
- Kjeldahl Catalyst
- Boric Acid
- Phenolphthalein
- HCl solution (0.31 N)

CALCULATIONS

The % of nitrogen is calculated with the following equation:

$$\% \text{ Nitrogen} = \frac{1.4 \times (V_1 - V_0) \times N}{P}$$

Where:

- P is the weight of the sample (g).
- V1 is the volume of HCl used in the titration of the sample (mL).
- V0 is the volume of HCl used in the titration of the blank (mL).
- N is the normality of the HCl.

With the % of Nitrogen known, it is possible to calculate the % of protein:

$$\% \text{ Protein} = \% \text{ Nitrogen} \times F$$

Where F is 5.7, the conversion factor for wheat (Kowalczewski et al. 2019). For other grains and legumes, another factor must be used (Mossé 1990; Mariotti, Tomé, and Mirand 2008).

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4.1.5. ASH CONTENT

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Ash content is one of the main quality indicators of flour quality (Czaja, Sobota, and Szostak 2020), and is defined as the amount of mineral matter obtained after the calcination of the flour. This mineral remnant is mainly made up of phosphorus, potassium, calcium, and magnesium, but it also contains small amounts of iron, zinc, copper, and other elements. The ash content of a grain or a legume depends on the species and the variety, but it is also determined by the environmental conditions (Singh, Singh, and Bakshi 1998). Furthermore, taking into account that the ash concentration is usually higher in the bran (in the case of wheat, the ash content is 6% in the bran and around 0.4% in the endosperm (Pomeranz 1988)), the ash content of a flour can be an indicator of its purity.

PROCEDURE

The procedure to determine the ash content is as follows (Ahmed et al. 2014):

- A sample of cereal grains or legume is milled until 50% of the material passes through a 0.5 mm sieve and more than 90% passes through a 1 mm sieve.
- Three grams of milled sample (with a known moisture content) are weighed and placed in a previously tared crucible.
- The sample is introduced into a muffle and kept at 550 °C for 5 hours.
- The crucible is weighed to determine the amount of the ashes.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Balance.
- Mill.
- Muffle.
- Porcelain crucible.
- Spatula.
- Sieves (0.5 and 1 mm)

CALCULATIONS

Using the following formula, the percentage of ash can be obtained (for the humidity considered):

$$\text{Ash content (\%)} = \frac{\text{Ash weight (g)}}{\text{Sample weight (g)}} \times 100$$

It is also possible to determine the ash content of the dry matter, using the moisture content of the sample and the following formula:

$$\text{Ash content in dry matter (\%)} = \text{Ash content (\%)} \times \frac{100}{100 - \text{Moisture content (\%)}}$$

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4.1.6. STARCH CONTENT

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Starch, cellulose and chitin are the most common polysaccharides in nature (Agama-Acevedo, Flores-Silva, and Bello-Perez 2018). And, while cellulose and chitin have a structural function, starch is a homo-polysaccharide used by plants to store carbohydrates. In the case of cereals, starch is stored in the seed and is used during germination. Starch is widely used by the food industry because, in addition to its nutritional quality (it is a source of glucose), it has desirable functional properties such as its great ability to retain water. Starch is present in many tubers and cereals, especially in maize and wheat (99%).

The Megazyme Total Starch Assay Kit (McCleary, Charmier, and McKie 2019), which is based on the AOAC Method 2014.10 (Hall 2009), was used to determine starch in cereal flours. The principle of this method is as follows: the starch present in the flour is degraded through the action of α -amylase and amyloglucosidase, first to maltodextrins and finally to glucose. Glucose, through a glucose oxidase/peroxidase agent, is converted into quinoneimine and measured by spectrophotometry.

PROCEDURE

- To determine the starch content in samples of legumes or cereals, it is necessary to have the samples milled to a size smaller than 0.5 mm.
- First, 100 mg of sample (W) are weighed into two test tubes and tapped gently so that the entire sample is deposited at the bottom. One of these tubes will be used for the sample blank.
- Add 10 mL of reagent 7 to each test tube and vortex for 5 sec.
- Then, 0.1 mL of Reagent 1 are added to one of the tubes (sample) and 0.1 mL of reagent 7 are added to the other tube (blank).
- The tubes are vortexed for 3 seconds and placed in a boiling water bath. At 2, 5 and 10 min, the tubes are vortexed for 5 seconds.
- After 15 minutes in the water bath, 5 sec of vortexing are applied before placing them into a bath at 50 °C for 5 minutes.
- To the sample tube, 0.1 mL of Reagent 2 are added and vortexed for 3 sec, and to the blank tube 0.1 mL of Reagent 7 are added.
- Allow the tubes to cool to room temperature for 10 minutes. It is important to turn the tubes over from time to time to ensure that the condensation is mixed with the rest of the sample.
- Two mL of each tube are transferred to microfuge tubes and centrifuged at 13000 rpm for 5 min.
- One mL of the supernatant is transferred into test tubes containing 4 mL of Reagent 1 and mixed with vortex.
- Transfer (in duplicate) 0.1 mL of the sample and sample blank into test tubes and add 3 mL of Reagent 4. The tubes are incubated at 50 °C for 20 min and then the absorbance is recorded at 510 nm.
- This last step (incubation) is also done with the reagent blank and the glucose standard. For the former, 0.1 mL of reagent 7 and 3 mL of Reagent 4 are added in a test tube. For the latter, 0.1 mL of a glucose standard (1 mg mL⁻¹, Reagent 5) and 3 mL of Reagent 4 are added.
- At the end, the sample absorbance (SA), the sample blank absorbance (SBA), the glucose standard absorbance (SSA) and the reagent blank absorbance (RBA) are measured.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

The Megazyme Total Starch Assay Kit contains the following reagents:

- Reagent 1: Thermostable α -amylase.
- Reagent 2: Amyloglucosidase.
- Reagent 3: GOPOD Reagent Buffer. This reagent must be diluted in one litre of distilled water just before use.
- Reagent 4: GOPOD Reagent Enzymes. This reagent is dissolved in 20 mL of Reagent 3 and then mixed with the remaining content of Reagent 3. This reagent can be kept in the refrigerator for approximately three months (2-5°C) or in the freezer for more than 12 months (-10°C).
- Reagent 5: D-Glucose standard solution.
- Reagent 6: Standardised regular maize starch control.

Moreover, it will be necessary to use:

- Reagent 7: Sodium acetate buffer (100 mM at pH 5.0) with calcium chloride (5 mM).
- Mill.
- Sieve (0.5 mm).
- Balance.
- Spatula.
- Spectrophotometer.
- Thermostatically controlled water bath
- Vortex.
- Pipettes.
- Test tubes.
- Microfuge tubes

CALCULATIONS

$$\text{Starch (\%)} = \Delta A \times F \times \frac{D}{W} \times 9.18$$

Where $\Delta A = (\text{SBA} - \text{RBA}) - (\text{SBA} - \text{RBA})$

F is a factor used to convert absorbance values to μg glucose, which is equal to 100 μg glucose divided by the absorbance value obtained for 100 μg of glucose (SSA).

D is a dilution factor (if the starch concentration is very high).

W is the sample weight in mg.

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4.2. VEGETABLES

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The term vegetable refers to those foods that are derived from plants, i.e. it is a very generic category that includes greens and fruits. Fruit, for example, is a sub-group formed by the edible part of many plants that contains the seeds inside. A fruit is the plant's ovary, whose wall has thickened (pericarp) with the function of protecting the seeds. The development of the fruit allows many plant species to spread, to disperse their seeds. In 2018, around 8.6 10⁸ tons of fruit were produced in the world, of which the most important crops (in tons produced) are bananas (1.2 10⁸), watermelons (1.0 10⁸) and apples (8.6 10⁷) (FAO 1997). On the other hand, tubers are underground stems in which the plant stores nutrients. In 2018, around 8.3 10⁸ tons of tubers were produced in the world, and within this group the production of potato (3.7 10⁸) and cassava (2.8 10⁸) are the most important ones regarding the total production of tubers (FAO 1997). Nondestructive methods including sonic vibration, nuclear magnetic resonance, or electrical properties can be used to determine the quality of some vegetables, and their crop yields (Gao, Zhu, and Cai 2010). However, the following methods will be used in this book: weight, size distribution, and flesh firmness.

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4.2.1. VEGETABLE WEIGHT AND SIZE DISTRIBUTION

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

After harvesting vegetables, it is important to separate them to determine the use of each piece. Depending on the size and quality, the products obtained can be used for various purposes such as sales, production of processed foods or planting (Glasbey, McRae, and Fleming 1988).

When determining the size, it is important to consider both the weight and the dimensions of the piece. The combination of both measurements can be used to determine other properties (density, for example). To determine the weight, only a balance is necessary, but several methods can be used to measure the dimensions: from a Vernier caliper, an instrument that allows the determination of the three spatial dimensions of the product (length, width and height), meshes of different sizes that classify vegetables considering the minimum size they are able to pass through, to more modern methods that include, for example, optical sizing.

PROCEDURE

The balance determines the weight of each piece.
The Vernier caliper determines the three dimensions (length, width and height).

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EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Balance.
- Vernier caliper.

CALCULATIONS

The data obtained can be used to determine the volume of the piece (adapting it to a sphere or an ellipsoid), and the density.

To determine the volume of an ellipsoid (V), the following formula can be used:

$$V = \frac{4}{3}\pi abc$$

Where a is half the length, b half the width, and c half the height.

The density (ρ) of each piece will also be determined by dividing the weight of each piece by its volume.

4.2.2. VEGETABLE FLESH FIRMNESS

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

The firmness of a vegetable is understood as its consistency, and it is a very important characteristic when considering the ripening of a vegetable and the optimum point for its harvesting, since it is a property closely related to the fragility of the vegetable. This can condition its transport, storage and destination: if the firmness is not adequate, the vegetable will not have the same acceptance by the consumer (Barreiro Elorza and Ruiz Altisent 1996).

Usually, the characteristic of firmness is measured as the force required to produce a deformation or breakage in the skin or the pulp of a vegetable (e.g. a fruit or a tuber). It is frequent to employ a penetrometer to determine the flesh firmness (Brezmes Llecha 2001). However, there are other non-destructive methods that can be used to measure this property, such as acoustic impulse resonance frequency (AIF) combined with spectral readings (in the visible wavelength) (Zude et al. 2006).

PROCEDURE

The procedure to determine the flesh firmness (Brezmes Llecha 2001) is as follows:

- Depending on the type of vegetable to be measured (and its firmness), a piston of a certain size is placed in the penetrometer. This is done because traditional penetrometers have a limited scale, and it is important that the pressure measurement falls within the optimal range of the penetrometer. Before starting each measurement the needle must be at zero.
- The piece is then divided into two halves and a superficial cut is made in the skin of one of them.
- The penetrometer piston is then placed (vertically) in the cut and inserted up to the notch in the piston. This procedure is repeated in the half that has not been cut.
- Both values are recorded and, considering the size of the piston used (its surface), the results are converted to Kg cm⁻².

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Penetrometer.
- Knife.

CALCULATIONS

When noting the penetrometer values it is important to note the piston used, as the scale on the penetrometers is usually referred to Kg cm⁻². Therefore, it is necessary to divide the Kg of pressure obtained by the surface of the piston used.

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4.2.3. STARCH CONTENT OF POTATOES

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

As in the case of cereals, potatoes (*Solanum tuberosum*) also store energy in the form of starch. However, the forms of starch in potatoes present certain differences compared to the ones found in cereals: for example, the amylose chains of potato starch are longer (Chavan, Khedkar, and Bhatt 2016), and their content in phosphates is higher (Navarre, Goyer, and Shakya 2009). Due to its characteristics, this type of starch is considered "pure" and has many applications in the food industry, as well as in the purification of paper and in the production of viscous hydrocolloidal systems (Bertoft and Blennow 2016).

The starch content can be determined chemically by acid or enzymatic hydrolysis with subsequent determination of glucose content (Widmann et al. 2008). However, it can also be determined by indirect methods: as it represents a very important part of the dry matter of the potato, starch can be calculated through density (there is a linear relationship between starch content and density) (Neiker 2005).

PROCEDURE

The procedure to determine the density and, therefore, the starch content, is as follows:

- An empty basket is placed on the arm of a "Roman" scale or on a spring scale. Note the weight of the basket in the air (AB).
- Next, the basket is immersed in a bucket with water. Once the weight is constant, the weight of the basket in water (WB) is noted.
- Then the basket is removed from the water and some potatoes are placed on it. The weight of the potatoes and the basket in the air (AP) is noted.
- Finally, the basket with the potatoes is submerged and it is waited until the weight is constant before recording it (WP).

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EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Basket.
- Balance.
- Water bucket.

CALCULATIONS

To calculate the starch content, it is necessary to first determine the density using the following formula:

$$Density = \frac{(AP - AB)}{(AP - AB) - (WP - WB)}$$

Where AP is the weight of the potatoes and the basket in the air; AB is the weight of the empty basket in the air; WP is the weight of the potatoes and the basket submerged; and WB is the weight of the submerged basket.

Taking into account the linear relationship between density and starch content, the latter can be calculated using the following formula:

$$Starch (\%) = 216.61 Density - 219.81$$

5. ASSESMENT OF SOIL BIODIVERSITY

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There are a lot of different biological analyses for soil biota. Each reveal the enormous richness of species and their diverse functional potential. Assessment of soil health through complete analysis of the soil food web consisting of bacteria, fungi, protozoa, nematodes, earthworms, enchytraeids, mites, insects, ants, tardigrades, collembola, moles etc. is practically daunting. Alternatively, a well-considered selection of indicator organisms is typically applied. Together they should reflect the structure and functions of ecological processes and they should exhibit sensitive responses to different soil conditions as affected by either natural or anthropogenic change.

The soil organisms selected to be investigated during the SoildiverAgro-project are important complementary bio-indicators concerning the linkage between soil biodiversity and soil functioning as described in the Technical Report-2010-049 “soil biodiversity: functions, threats and tools for policy makers” (European Commission DG ENV, DOI 10.2779/14571). One representative of each functional group in a soil ecosystem is present: bacteria and fungi as chemical engineers, responsible for the decomposition of organic material into plant nutrients; nematodes as biological regulators, responsible for the general management of the food web structure; earthworms as ecosystem engineers, responsible for the formation of biogenic soil aggregates and macropores as habitats and for controlling the soil water balance and air ventilation.

The (functional) diversity of the selected soil organisms will be determined as explained in the following sections. Table 5.1. shows an overview of the methods used by the partners in charge of a certain type of biodiversity analysis.

Table 5.1. Partners responsible for the acquisition of different types of biological data and the methods used

Methods for biodiversity assessments		
Analysis type	Partner in charge	METHOD
Nematode diversity	EV-ILVO	SSU rRNA gene amplicon sequencing
Whole microbial diversity	UVIGO	PLFA/NLFA
Bacterial and archaeal genetic diversity	UCPH	SSU rRNA gene amplicon sequencing
Fungal & mycorrhizal genetic diversity	LUKE	Fungal ITS sequencing
Microbial functional diversity	UCPT	Transcriptomic dynamics of key genes (C and N cycling)
Earthworm diversity	TI, EV-ILVO, LUKE, UVIGO, EULS	Morphological analysis

5.1. EARTHWORM DIVERSITY

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Earthworm populations are usually characterized according to different criteria: i) developmental stage to quantify the proportion of adults and juveniles; ii) ecological groups to describe the feeding and burrowing behaviour; iii) species identification to determine species richness.

This protocol describes how:

- to identify earthworm species
- to assign each specimen to one of the established ecological groups (Bouché, 1977): epigeic, anecic and endogeic,
- to distinguish developmental stages: adult, subadult and juvenile
- to separate incomplete specimens and fragments from all others
- to determine total abundance (individuals m⁻²) and biomass (g m⁻²)

PROCEDURE

Wear disposable protective gloves and use plastic forceps when handling earthworms. The specimens from each replicate sample should be placed into a plastic container filled with cold tap water. Before the species identification under the stereo microscope and weighing, each specimen should be cautiously dried on tissue paper.

Developmental stage

Earthworms are first separated according to their developmental stage by looking at their sexual maturity:

- Adults have a fully developed clitellum (glandular thickened section of the body wall in the middle or towards the anterior end of the body)
- Subadults do not have a developed clitellum but tubercula pubertatis (glandular thickenings on the ventral surface) are present
- Juvenile worms do not show any visible signs of clitellum nor tubercula pubertatis.

Figure 5.1.1. shows some of the morphological characters for identifying earthworms to species level, and includes the position of the clitellum and the tubercula pubertatis, two distinct characteristics of fully adult specimens.

Ecological groups

Most earthworm individuals (adults and sub-adults but often also juveniles) can be assigned to their ecological groups according to their dorsal pigmentation:

- Epigeic species are heavily pigmented small earthworms.
- Anecic species are large earthworms and moderate to heavily pigmented on their front end (until some segments behind the clitellum);
- Endogeic species are unpigmented or nearly unpigmented; in some species, the epidermis is translucent showing through inner organs

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Disposable protective gloves
- Tissue paper or paper towels
- Plastic forceps
- Flat plastic containers (vol.: ca. 1 L) with cold fresh tap water
- Plastic cups with cold fresh tap water
- Stereo microscope (magnitude: ca. 10x to 50x)
- Analytical balance (precision: 0.01 g)
- Identification keys
- Data sheets

REMARKS

All fragments of earthworms in the sample must be included for determining total earthworm biomass. However, only those fragments that include the head and as best also the clitellum can be identified to the species level and if this is the case, they can be used for total abundance and diversity estimates. Any other fragments are listed as “unidentified fragments”.

Figure 5.1.1. Some of the main morphological characters that are used in identifying developmental stage and species of earthworms

Figure 5.1.2. shows one example species, its typical pigmentation and type of burrow system for each ecological group.

Taxonomical identification

Adult earthworms can be identified to species level by using a stereo microscope (magnitude: 10x to 50x) and a taxonomic identification key. For example, the identification guide by Sims and Gerard (1999) and key to the earthworms of the UK and Ireland by Sherlock (2018) are useful for identifying the majority of the common European species. Because they do not cover completely European earthworm fauna, national or regional keys should also be used when necessary.

Figure 5.1.2. Earthworm ecological groups (Bouché, 1977): epigeic (*Lumbricus castaneus*; top left), anecic (*Lumbricus terrestris*; right), and endogeic (*Octolasion cyaneum*; bottom) (the size of the species not to scale). Photo credit: Guide to British earthworms (<https://www.opalexplornature.org/earthwormguide>).

The most important diagnostic characters are the position and shape of the clitellum and location of the tubercula pubertatis (see Figure 5.1.1.). Other important diagnostic characters are the shape of prostomium (in front of the first segment) and the clitellum (annular, saddle), setae pattern (distance between setae on each segment) (Fig. 5.1.1.). Subadult earthworms can be identified to species in many cases, however, juvenile earthworms can only be assigned to ecological groups (see above). If the specimen cannot be accurately identified, then annotate all available information and classify it as ‘unknown’.

CALCULATIONS

Use a balance with precision of 0.01g for determination of the preserved earthworm biomass (g). Determine the biomass per species, per ecological group and in total for each sample. Express all abundance (of individual species and ecological groups) and biomass data as individuals per square meter (ind. m^{-2}) and grams per square meter (g m^{-2}), respectively. In case of a 50 cm x 50 cm sampling quadrat, multiply the density and mass in the sample by 4. In case of a 25 cm x 25 cm sampling quadrat, multiply by 16.

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A microscopic view of various nematodes, showing their characteristic long, thin, cylindrical bodies and some with distinct head and tail regions. The worms are scattered across the field of view, some appearing in cross-section and others in longitudinal view. The background is a light, slightly textured surface.

5.2. NEMATODES DIVERSITY

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Nematodes (also called roundworms) constitute a diverse species-rich group of organisms. They inhabit nearly all ecosystems including marine, freshwater, and terrestrial environments. In the soil, they occur across multiple trophic levels making them vitally important in the soil environment. Nematodes are frequently the most abundant and diverse invertebrates present in the soil. Consequently, the nematode composition contains high intrinsic information value for each soil sample (Yeates et al., 1993; Van den Hoogen et al., 2019).

While there are many general indices of biological diversity, specific indices have been developed for nematodes. For example, the Maturity Index (MI), is a weighted mean frequency of c-p scaling across the entire nematode community, a scaling based on the nematode's differential life-style, and provides the information of the likely condition of the soil environment (Bongers, 1990). Ferris et al. (2001) assigned weights to indicator nematode guilds representing basal, enriched and structured conditions of the food web. This concept led to the development of food web indices including Enrichment (EI) and Structure Index (SI). The EI describes whether the soil environment is nutrient enriched (high EI) or depleted (low EI). SI describes whether the soil ecosystem is structured with greater trophic links (high SI) or degraded (low SI) with fewer trophic links. Plotting of EI versus SI provides a model framework of nematode faunal analysis as an indicator of the likely conditions of the soil food web in a given habitat.

The characterization of a nematode community through microscopy is time-consuming and requires trained taxonomists. As a consequence, molecular techniques are increasingly preferred to unravel changes in nematode communities. Such a technique combined with a practical understanding from the research generated is believed to help in choosing farming strategies for improved ecosystem services directly or indirectly influenced by the nematode community.

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5.2.1. NEMATODES COMMUNITY DNA EXTRACTION AND PURIFICATION

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Nematode community DNA is extracted from a nematode suspension isolated from a soil sample (enrichment procedure). The suspension is obtained by extracting the nematode community from a 100 ml soil sample using the technique of automated zonal centrifuging (AZC, Hendrickx, 1995). The suspension is then concentrated and stored at -20°C until DNA-extraction.

The nematode suspension is concentrated by gravity force. Centrifugation is not recommended because strong forces can cause nematodes to burst open and be lost while pipetting away the upper layer (supernatant) during multiple steps.

To extract DNA, the DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) is used following the protocol "Purification of total DNA from animal tissues" according to the manufacturer's instructions with minor adaptations. Samples are first lysed using proteinase K. The buffer added next, provides optimal DNA-binding conditions before the lysate is loaded onto the DNeasy Mini spin column. During centrifugation, DNA is selectively bound to the DNeasy (silica-based) membrane while contaminants pass through.

Remaining contaminants and enzyme inhibitors are removed in two wash steps and DNA is then eluted in water or buffer, ready for use.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Large volume pipet or suction machine
- 50 mL conical tubes
- 15 mL conical tubes
- 1.5 and 2 mL Eppendorf tubes
- Pasteur pipets (glass pipets)
- A set of Micropipettes
- DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit from Qiagen, hereafter called 'Qiagen-kit'
- Vortex
- Centrifuge (min. 20,000 rcf)
- Warm water bath (56°C)
- Refrigerator (4°C)
- Freezer (-20°C)

REAGENTS

- Ethanol (96-100%)

CALCULATIONS

No calculations are made during DNA-extraction.

REMARKS

The quality and quantity of the DNA do not have to be measured. The subsequent PCR-reaction and electrophoresis demonstrate whether the extracted DNA is amplifiable and thus provides an impression of the DNA quality and/or yield.

The use of an optimal DNA extraction protocol is crucial. The Qiagen-kit scored the highest yield compared with several other commercial DNA-extraction methods. However, there is still room to further optimize the DNA-extraction procedure (Waeyenberge et al., 2019).

PROCEDURE

1.

Place the beakers (150 mL) holding the nematode suspensions obtained from the AZC endrickx, 1995), on a bench at room temperature.

2.

After 4 hours, reduce the volume till 40 mL without disturbing the nematodes at the bottom of the beaker. Several devices can be used: from large volume pipets till a suction machine.

3.

Swirl the beaker and transfer the nematode suspension to a 50 mL conical tube.

4.

Store the tubes at 4°C for one night.

5.

Remove the supernatant till a volume of 5 mL. Again several devices can be used.

6.

Swirl the tube and transfer the nematode suspension to a 15 mL conical tube.

7.

Store the tubes at 4°C for one night.

8.

Remove gently (!) the supernatant till a volume of 2 mL using a micropipette. Be careful not to suck up nematodes.

9.

Homogenize the 2 mL nematode suspension with a Pasteur pipet and divide it equally (250 µL each) into 2 mL Eppendorf tubes.

10.

Store the 8 Eppendorf tubes with nematode suspensions at -20°C until use.

11.

In the morning, take 2 Eppendorf tubes out of the freezer and add in each 180 µL buffer ATL and 20 µL proteinase K (Qiagen-kit).

12.

Vortex and incubate at 56°C for 3 hours. Preferably, mix the suspensions by turning the tubes now and then during incubation.

13.

Vortex 15 s and add in each tube 200 μ L buffer AL (Qiagen-kit).

14.

Mix thoroughly by vortex.

15.

Add 200 μ L ethanol (96-100%) in each tube and mix thoroughly by vortex.

16.

Pipet maximally 700 μ L mixture into one DNeasy Mini spin column placed in a collection tube (Qiagen-kit).

17.

Centrifuge at 6000 g for 1 min and discard the flow-through.

18.

Repeat steps 16 and 17 until the mixtures from both Eppendorf tubes have passed the same DNeasy Mini spin column.

19.

Place the spin column in a new collection tube and add 500 μ L buffer AW1 (Qiagen-kit).

20.

Centrifuge at 6000 g for 1 min and discard the flow-through.

21.

Place the spin column in a new collection tube and add 500 μ L buffer AW2 (Qiagen-kit).

22.

Centrifuge at 20,000 g for 3 min and discard the flow-through.

23.

Place the spin column in 1.5 mL Eppendorf tube, labelled properly.

24.

Elute the DNA by adding 75 μ L buffer AE (Qiagen-kit) to the centre of the spin column membrane and by incubating for 1 min at room temperature.

25.

Centrifuge at 6000 g for 1 min and discard the DNeasy Mini spin column.

26.

Close the 1.5 mL Eppendorf tube and store the purified DNA at -20°C until further use.

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5.2.2. NEMATODES COMMUNITY CHARACTERIZATION BY SSU RRNA GENE AMPLICON SEQUENCING

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Within the relatively conserved 18S rDNA gene, variable sequence regions covering the required taxonomic resolution for nematodes, are alternated by short conserved sequences useful for universal primer design (Hadziavdic et al., 2014). Further, an extensive number of 18S rDNA sequences of different nematode species are available for diagnostic assignment (Van Megen et al., 2009). As a consequence, ssu rRNA gene amplicon sequencing is currently the mostly used high throughput method to identify nematode communities from various habitats (Waeyenberge et al., 2019).

The method for nematode community characterization is based on the amplification and sequencing of a variable region within the ssu or 18S rRNA gene. The amplicon libraries of approximately 300 different nematode communities are pooled and sequenced using a Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) technology on an Illumina MiSeq platform with PE300 reads (70% \geq Q30). The sequences are subsequently analysed using a bio-informatics pipeline and characterised by comparison with a nematode 18S sequence database. This results in the determination of the nematode genera present in all the nematode suspensions processed and their relative abundances. Index primers incorporated in the amplicons, containing a unique 8 bp multiplex identifier per nematode suspension, make it possible to group all sequences from one nematode community together.

An open-source R package, DADA2 (Callahan et al., 2016), is used for sequence data analysis. This cluster-free pipeline not only infers amplicon sequence variants (ASV) directly, the reads are 'corrected' by a quality-aware model of Illumina-amplicon errors. Whether this approach yields a better evaluation of soil nematode communities compared to the use of OTUs (Operational Taxonomic Units) is yet unknown. However, the authors stated that in mock communities DADA identifies more real variants and outputs fewer spurious sequences than other methods. Additionally, it has been recently reported for marine nematodes that the DADA2 pipeline produced the most realistic estimates of species richness yet taxonomic assignment of ASVs were reduced (Macheriotou et al., 2018).

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EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- LThermocycler
- 1.5 or 2 mL Eppendorf tubes
- 0.2 mL PCR tubes, strips or multiwell plates
- A set of Micropipettes
- Vortex
- Centrifuge (min. 20,000 rcf)
- Refrigerator (4°C)
- Freezer (-20°C)
- Microwave
- Gel electrophoresis apparatus including a casting gel tray, an electrophoresis tank, few combs and a power supplier
- Gel Imaging System (for example, Azure Biosystems c150, Dublin, CA, USA)
- Fluorometer (for example, Quantus, Promega, WI, USA)

REAGENTS

- 2X KAPA HiFi HotStart ReadyMix (Roche Diagnostics)
- 18S rRNA forward primer with Illumina adapter (5'-TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAG-3')
- 18S rRNA reverse primer with Illumina adapter (5'-GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAG-3')
- MilliQ water
- Agarose
- TAE buffer (ready-to-use)
- Midori Green Advanced DNA stain (Nippon Genetics Europe GmbH, Düren, Germany)
- Loading dye (for example, 6X Orange DNA Loading Dye from Life Technologies Europe B.V.)
- DNA marker (for example, GeneRuler 100 bp DNA Ladder, ready-to-use, from Life Technologies Europe B.V.)
- PCR-purification method with magnetic beads (CleanNGS, GC Biotech BV., Alphen aan den Rijn, the Netherlands)
- Index primers, Illumina Nextera XT Index Kit v2, set A-D (Illumina Inc., San Diego, CA, USA)
- QuantiFluor ds DNA System (Promega, WI, USA)

CALCULATIONS

DNA quantities are calculated by the software provided with the Quantus (Promega, WI, USA).

PROCEDURE

1.

Execute a PCR (= amplicon-PCR) using the next mixture:
12.5 μL of 2X KAPA HiFi HotStart ReadyMix
0.75 μM of both the forward and reverse 18S rRNA gene primer
MilliQ water up to a volume of 23 μL .
To reduce pipetting steps, make a master mix in a 1.5 or 2 mL Eppendorf tube(s) with a volume depending on the number of reactions. Include at least 3 negative controls. Then distribute 23 μL of the master mix in a number of 0.2 mL PCR tubes, strips or multiwell plates.

2.

Add 2 μL DNA-extract obtained from a nematode community (see section 5.2.1). The final volume is now 25 μL .

3.

Put the tubes, strips or multiwell plate in a thermocycler programmed as follows:
95 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3 min
35 cycles of 98 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 20 s, 64 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 15 s, 72 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 30 s
72 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 min
Hold temperature at 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}$

4.

During PCR, a 1.5% agarose gel is prepared by melting agarose powder in 1X TAE-buffer in a microwave. After cooling partially, Midori Green Advanced DNA stain is added to the gel at a ratio of 8 μL per 100 mL of agarose gel.

5.

Pour the prepared gel on a casting tray and place one or more combs.

6.

Transfer the gel tray with the completely solidified gel into an electrophoresis tank filled with 1X TAE buffer; The gel should be completely submersed.

7.

Remove the combs gently.

8.

Take the PCR tubes, strips or multiwell(s) with amplicons and transfer per sample 5 μL amplicon to another tube, strips or multiwell(s) and mix each with 1 μL loading dye.

9.

Load this mixture in the different gel wells (one sample mixture per well).

10.

Also load a (100 bp) DNA marker in a separate well.

11.

Turn on the power supplier (100V) and let the electrophoresis run until the amplicons have migrated sufficiently.

12.

Place the gel in a gel imaging system, visualise the amplicons with UV-light and take a photo. Evaluate the amplicons by investigating the photo.

13.

Take again the PCR tubes with amplicons and clean the amplicons by separating them from unincorporated primers, dNTPs, and primer dimers using a PCR-purification method with magnetic beads. Follow the manufacturer's instructions.

14.

Execute a second PCR (= index-PCR) using the next mixture:
12.5 μL of 2X KAPA HiFi HotStart ReadyMix
0.75 μM of both a forward and reverse index primer
MilliQ water up to a volume of 23 μL .
Making a master mix is not possible since for each sample another combination of index primers has to be used.

15.

Add 2 μL purified amplicons as DNA-source. The final volume is now 25 μL .

16.

Put the tubes, strips or multiwell plate in a thermocycler and run the same temperature profile as used for the amplicon-PCR (see step 3) but reduce the number of cycles from 35 till 15 only.

17.

Repeat step 4 till 10 for a selection of samples to visualize the amplification after index-PCR.

18.

Repeat step 11 to purify the amplicons from the index-PCR

19.

Quantify the amplicons using a fluorometer and a double-stranded DNA quantification system (QuantiFluor ds DNA System, Promega, WI, USA) following the manufacturer's instructions.

20.

Pool the amplicons of each sample in equimolar concentrations (10 nM) in a 2 mL Eppendorf tube and send (part of) the pooled sample to a sequence service provider. Follow the instructions of the provider for storage and transportation.

21.

After receiving the raw sequence data from the sequence service provider, the data is analysed and quality checked as follows: Remove primer sequences from the obtained reads using Trimmomatic v0.32 (Bolger et al., 2014). Perform all subsequent analyses in R 3.4.3 (R Core Team) using the package DADA2 (Callahan et al., 2016) containing a full amplicon workflow starting from filtering, dereplication, chimera identification, until merging paired-end reads. In the filtering step, forward and reverse reads are trimmed. Finally, the sequences are compared with our sequence database (own produced 18S rRNA gene sequences added to the most recent SILVA release from which only sequences belonging to the phylum Nematoda are retained) to link them to a certain nematode taxon using the naive Bayesian classifier method (Wang et al., 2007) assigning taxonomy across multiple ranks (e.g. Kingdom to Genus) with minimum bootstrapping support of 80. In addition, all sequences are blasted against the non-redundant database of Genbank to confirm their taxonomic assignment. Relative abundances for each sequence variant per sample are calculated and exploratory barplots and other graphs are produced.

5.3. MICROORGANISMS DIVERSITY

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Microbial diversity is immense in soils and refers to the number of different bacterial, archaeal, and fungal species and their relative abundance (Maron et al., 2018). Microorganisms are crucial for the stability and productivity of agroecosystems as they are involved in key processes such as the formation of soil structure, organic matter decomposition, biodegradation of organic pollutants and cycling of essential elements such as carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus, and sulphur (Garbeva et al., 2004). Soil microorganisms can furthermore be highly beneficial for plants as they can suppress soil-borne diseases and enhance plant growth. Microbial diversity is, therefore, often linked to plant and soil quality, and constitute an important indicator for evaluating soil health (Abawi and Widmer, 2000; Schloter et al., 2003). Physicochemical properties of soil are considered key determinants for microbial diversity and can be affected by soil management and treatment, such as tillage, crop rotation (Lupwayi et al., 1998), pesticide application (Jacobsen and Hjelmsø, 2014) and fertilization (Zhong et al., 2010).

Traditionally, cultivation based methods have been used to investigate microbial diversity, but these methods are time-consuming, and only a small fraction of microorganisms are cultivatable (Kirk et al., 2004). Advancements in molecular technologies such as direct DNA extraction from soil, PCR amplification of conserved gene targets and next-generation DNA sequencing now allow for comprehensive, high-throughput cultivation-independent analyses of soil microbial diversity (Schöler et al., 2017). Gene targets include the small sub-unit ribosomal RNA (ssu rRNA) gene (taxonomic gene marker) or a range of different functional gene markers indicative of the functional diversity of the soil microbiome. Collectively, these techniques have proven highly useful for assessing soil microbial diversity.

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5.3.1. DNA EXTRACTION AND PURIFICATION

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

To extract metagenomic DNA from soil for subsequent ssu rRNA gene amplicon sequencing, we used the DNeasy PowerSoil Kit according to the general protocol with minor deviations (Vishnivetskaya et al. 2014; Ramírez, Graham, and D'Hondt 2018). Nanodrop (ThermoFisher Scientific) and D Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer (Invitrogen) were used for subsequent analysis of DNA yield and quantity.

PROCEDURE

DNA Extraction

1.

To the PowerBead Tubes provided, add 0.25 grams of soil sample.

2.

Gently mix the tubes using a Ribolyzer (1 min, 5.5 m/s).

3.

Check Solution C1. If Solution C1 is precipitated, heat solution to 60°C until dissolved before use.

4.

Add 60 µl of Solution C1 and invert several times or vortex briefly.

5.

Secure PowerBead Tubes in the MP Fastprep-24 instrument, and run the recommended program for soil samples (30s, 5.5 m/s).

6.

Make sure the PowerBead Tubes rotate freely in your centrifuge without rubbing. Centrifuge tubes at 10,000 x g for 30 seconds at room temperature.

7.

Transfer the supernatant to a clean 2 ml Collection Tube

8.

Add 250 µl of Solution C2 and vortex for 5 seconds. Incubate at 4°C for 5 minutes.

9.

Centrifuge the tubes at room temperature for 1 minute at 10,000 x g.

10.

Avoiding the pellet, transfer up to, but no more than, 600 µl of supernatant to a clean 2 ml Collection Tube.

11.

Add 200 μ l of Solution C3 and vortex briefly. Incubate at 4°C for 5 minutes.

12.

Centrifuge the tubes at room temperature for 1 minute at 10,000 x g.

13.

Avoiding the pellet, transfer up to, but no more than, 750 μ l of supernatant into a clean 2 ml Collection Tube.

14.

Shake to mix Solution C4 before use. Add 1200 μ l of Solution C4 to the supernatant and vortex for 5 seconds.

15.

Load approximately 675 μ l onto a Spin Filter and centrifuge at 10,000x g for 1 minute at room temperature. Discard the flow through add an additional 675 μ l of supernatant to the Spin Filter and centrifuge at 10,000 x g for 1 minute at room temperature. Load the remaining supernatant onto the Spin Filter and centrifuge at 10,000 x g for 1 minute at room temperature.

16.

Add 500 μ l of Solution C5 and centrifuge at room temperature for 30 seconds at 10,000 x g.

17.

Discard the flow through.

18.

Centrifuge again at room temperature for 1 minute at 10,000 x g.

19.

Carefully place the spin filter in a clean 2 ml Collection Tube (provided). Avoid splashing any Solution C5 onto the Spin Filter.

DNA Extraction

20. Add 100 µl of Solution C6 to the centre of the white filter membrane.
21. Centrifuge at room temperature for 30 seconds at 10,000 x g.
22. Discard the Spin Filter. The DNA in the tube is now ready for any downstream application. No further steps are required.
23. Long-term storage of DNA at -80°C.

Determination of DNA quantity and quality using Nanodrop

1. Make sure the measuring arm on the Nanodrop apparatus is in a down position.
2. Open the ND-1000 program by double-clicking on the NanoDrop ND1000 icon.
3. Choose "Nucleic Acid measurements" and "DNA"
Lift up the measuring arm on the apparatus and remove the tissue paper.
Check that both measuring surfaces are clean (if not then clean with a soft piece of paper (Kleenex))
Apply 1.5 µl of MQ water
Close the measuring arm
4. Click "OK"
To calibrate
Lift up the measuring arm
Clean of the measuring surface with a soft piece of paper (Kleenex)
Apply 1.5 µl of solution C6 as a blank, close the measuring arm. Click on "blank"
To measure the DNA concentration:
Lift up the measuring arm
Clean of the measuring surface with a soft piece of paper (Kleenex)
Apply 1.5 µl of the extracted DNA sample, close the measuring arm.
Write the sample name in the field on the right-hand side of the screen
Click on "measure"
Write down the measured concentration (or print a report after the last sample)
Repeat from step a) to f) for all samples

Determination of DNA quantity using Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer

1.

Prepare High Sensitive (HS) standards and DNA samples according to the manual supplied by the Invitrogen™ Qubit™ dsDNA HS Assay Kit.

2.

Calibrate the Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer according to the manual using the prepared HS standards.

3.

Measure the DNA concentration in all samples according to the Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer manual.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment necessary (* provided with the DNeasy PowerSoil kit)

- Analytical balance (0.01 g)
- Micropipettes
- Collection tubes of 2 mL *
- PowerBead tubes *
- Spin Filter tubes *
- Distilled water
- Vortex
- Centrifuge
- Refrigerator
- Ribolyzer
- MP Fastprep-24™ instrument
- Nanodrop 1000 spectrophotometer
- Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer
- Invitrogen™ Qubit™ dsDNA HS Assay Kit
- 500 µL thin-walled PCR tubes

REAGENTS

- 70% ethanol
- Solutions C1, C2, C3, C4, C5, and C6 *

CALCULATIONS

The DNA concentration of all samples is calculated by the Nanodrop and Qubit 2.0 software. The quality of the DNA is determined by the A260/280 and A260/230 ratios quantified by the nanodrop software.

REMARKS

The use of an optimal DNA extraction protocol is crucial. The PowerSoil Kit method is the most universally applicable DNA extraction kit, resulting in high-quality data, with lower bias than other methods (Hermans, Buckley, and Lear 2018). Nevertheless, all DNA extraction protocols will be biased to some extent. It is thus crucial to always standardize DNA extraction protocols for samples to be directly compared with each other.

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5.3.2. BACTERIAL AND ARCHAEAL GENETIC DIVERSITY: SSU RRNA GENE AMPLICON SEQUENCING

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Small subunit (ssu) rRNA amplicon sequencing is a widely used high throughput method to identify prokaryotic taxa in different environments allowing for cultivation-independent determination of bacterial and archaeal community composition (Caporaso et al., 2012). The technique is based on PCR amplification of hypervariable regions of the ssu rRNA gene (also termed 16S rRNA gene in bacteria), which are then analysed using Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) technology and compared against DNA sequence databases to determine the identity and abundance of prokaryotic taxa. Within the SoildiverAgro Project, UCPH has opted to use a commercial next-generation sequencing provider for our sequencing needs in order to enhance our ability to meet tight deadlines for our project deliverables.

PROCEDURE

1. For amplicon sequencing, send the high-quality DNA samples obtained by DNA extraction (minimum concentration of 10 ng/μL) to NOVOGENE (HK) COMPANY LIMITED.
2. At Novogene, PCR amplification will be conducted using the modified bacterial/archaeal primer pair 515F -GTGYCAGCMGCCGCGGTAA and 806R-GGACTACNVGGGTWTCTAAT targeting the V4 region of the bacterial 16s rRNA gene (Parada et al., 2016; Walters et al., 2016).
3. The PCR products will subsequently be purified and used for library preparation.
4. The prepared library will be sequenced on an Illumina HiSeq2500 platform, and 250-bp paired-end reads will be generated with at least 50,000 raw reads per sample (Q30 ≥ 75%).
5. The obtained reads will subsequently be quality checked and analysed using the following methods and software:

Standard Analysis	Software
Data split and reads merging	FLASH
Data quality control: data filtration and chimera removal	QIIME
OTUs(Operational Taxonomic Units) Clustering and Species annotation, including OTUs Heatmap, GraPhIAn display, Taxonomy Tree, KRONA results	Uparse, PyNast, Mothur
Species distribution, including Ternary plot, Species Abundance Heatmap, the evolutionary tree in genus.	RDP
Alpha-diversity Analysis, including Alpha Indices table (Observed species, Good's coverage, Chao1, ACE, Shannon, Simpson, PD whole tree), Species diversity curves, Species accumulation boxplot, Venn and Flower diagram(Up to 5 figures for free)	QIIME, R
Beta-diversity Analysis, including Beta diversity heatmap, (un)weighted unifrac distance analysis, PCA (Principal Component Analysis), PCoA (Principal Co-ordinates Analysis), UPGMA (Unweighted Pair-group Method with Arithmetic Means), MetaStat, LEfSe analysis	QIIME, R

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5.3.3. FUNGAL/MYCORRHIZA

GENETIC DIVERSITY: FUNGAL ITS

ILLUMINA AMPLICON SEQUENCING

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Amplicon sequencing is a highly targeted approach that enables the analysis of genetic variation in specific genomic regions. This method, that employs DNA metabarcoding, allows the paralleled amplification and sequencing of potentially thousands of different barcoded regions belonging to different species. The barcoded region corresponds to a short fragment within the genome of an organism, whose sequence is conserved within a species, but varies among different species. By comparing the sequences obtained to those of a reference database, it is possible to gather information about the community composition of a complex sample. The ultra-deep sequencing of PCR products (amplicons) allows efficient variant identification and characterization. Illumina amplicon sequencing uses oligonucleotide probes designed to target and capture regions of interest, followed by next-generation sequencing (NGS). NGS overcomes the limits of the cultivation-based methods and allows profiling the entire microbiome by directly sequencing the DNA taken from a wide range of different and complex samples.

In this protocol, we chose the fungal Internal Transcribed Spacer (ITS) region for fungal amplicon sequencing. ITS is part of the non-transcriptional

region of the fungal rRNA gene. The ITS sequences used for fungal identification usually include ITS1 and ITS2 because in fungi, 5.8S, 18S, and 28S rRNA genes are highly conserved, whereas ITS can tolerate more mutations in the evolutionary process and exhibits extremely wide sequence polymorphism in most eukaryotes. At the same time, the conservative type of ITS is relatively consistent within species, the differences between species are easily detectable and they have been widely used in phylogenetic analysis of different fungi (Kim et al. 2013).

In this protocol, the Illumina MiSeq system with a read length of 2 x 300 bp and an output of 22-25 M reads, was chosen to characterize the fungal diversity. Illumina sequencing by synthesis (SBS) chemistry is the most widely adopted NGS technology, generating approximately 90% of global sequencing data (Illumina 2015).

PROCEDURE

1.

Amplicon library preparation

This protocol is based on the protocol described in the Earth Microbiome Project (<http://www.earthmicrobiome.org/protocols-and-standards/its/>). The libraries are prepared following a 2-step PCR protocol. For the first PCR, the fungal ITS1- ITS2 region with an amplicon of ~450 bp (Bokulich and Mills 2013; Hoggard et al. 2018) is amplified using the primers ITS1f (5' - CTTGGTCATTTAGAGGAAGTAA - 3') (Gardes and Bruns 1993) and ITS2 primer (5' - GCTGCGTTCTTCATCGATGC - 3') (White et al. 1990). These primers include an oligonucleotide extension at their respective 5' ends in order to make the amplicons suitable for sequencing in an Illumina MiSeq sequencer. The complete primer sequences are shown in table 5.3.3.1. The reaction mixture and the cycling conditions of the first PCR are described in table 5.3.3.2. and 5.3.3.3, respectively. The indices, which are required for multiplexing different samples in the same sequencing run will be added in a second PCR with identical conditions but with only 5 cycles and 60 °C as the annealing temperature.

A negative control containing no DNA needs to be included in every PCR run to check for contamination during the library preparation.

The libraries are verified by electrophoresis on 2 % agarose gel stained with GreenSafe (NZYTech), and imaged under UV light to verify the library size.

The libraries are purified using the Mag-Bind RXNPure Plus magnetic beads (Omega Biotek), following the instructions provided by the manufacturer. Then, they will be pooled in equimolar amounts according to the quantification data provided by the Qubit dsDNA HS Assay (Thermo Fisher Scientific).

Table 5.3.3.1. PCR primers

PCR #	Primer name	Primer sequence (5' – 3')*	Reference
PCR1	ITS1f	ACACTCTTTCCCTACACGACGCTCTTCCGATCTCTTGGTCATTAGAGGAAGTAA	Gardes and Bruns 1993
	ITS2	GTGACTGGAGTTCAGACGTGTGCTCTTCCGATCTGCTGCGTTCTTCATCGATGC	White et al. 1990
PCR2	Forward primer	AATGATACGGCGACCACCGAGATCTACACNNNNNNNNACACTCTTTCCCTACACGA	
	Reverse primer	CAAGCAGAAGACGGCATAACGAGATNNNNNNNNGTGACTGGAGTTCAGACGTG	

* N represent the index sequences, which will differ among samples.

Table 5.3.3.2. PCR reaction mixture

Reagent	Initial Conc.	Vol/rxn (µl)	Final Conc.
Supreme NZYtaq 2x Green Master Mix (NZYTech)	2x	12.5	1x
Forward Primer	10 µM	1.25	500 nM
Reverse Primer	10 µM	1.25	500 nM
Sterile H2O	***	7.5	***
Total volume		25	

Table 5.3.3.3. PCR cycling conditions

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95 °C	5 min
Denaturation	35	95 °C	30 sec
Annealing		52 °C	30 sec
Extension		68 °C	30 sec
Extension		68 °C	10 min

2.**High-throughput sequencing**

The pooled DNA will be sequenced in a MiSeq PE300 run (Illumina). The MiSeq run includes a 5-10 % control PhiX library (Illumina) to increase the sequence diversity among amplicons.

**EQUIPMENT
AND MATERIAL**

- Digestion tubes
- Digester unit (Bloc-Digest)
- Fume collector/extractor
- Erlenmeyer flasks
- Distiller
- Burette
- Laboratory mill
- Balance

REAGENTS

- Sulfuric Acid (95-98%)
- NaOH solution (35%)
- Mixed indicator
- Kjeldahl Catalyst
- Boric Acid
- Phenolphthalein
- HCl solution (0.31 N)

REMARKS

The quantity and quality of the extracted metagenomic DNA is crucial. Low DNA yield or poor DNA quality will likely lead to an inaccurate estimation of microbial diversity (Claassen et al. 2013; Inceošlu et al. 2010). To avoid this, DNA 260/280 and 260/230 ratios should be higher than >1.8. At the same time, the quantified DNA should have a minimum concentration of 10 ng μl^{-1} with at least 200 ng, and should be re-suspended in water, 10 mM Tris HCl pH 8.5 or TE buffer (although water should be avoided to prevent acid hydrolysis).

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5.3.4. MICROBIAL FUNCTIONAL DIVERSITY: ESTIMATION OF ABUNDANCE OF SELECTED MICROBIAL GENE SEQUENCES BY QUANTITATIVE PCR FROM DNA DIRECTLY EXTRACTED FROM SOIL (C AND N CYCLES)

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Carbon and nitrogen biogeochemical cycles are mostly driven by microbial activities (Burgin et al. 2011). In this protocol, microbial C and N cycling gene abundance is determined by qPCR targeting the genes *ureC*, *amoA*, *narG*, *nirK*, and *nifH* involved in the N cycle and the genes *cbbL* and *GH7* involved in the C cycle.

Ammonification is the process whereby organic N is mineralized to ammonium (NH_4^+). It is the first step in organic N decomposition and is often referred to as N mineralization (Hopkinson and Giblin 2008). Ammonium is then available to be assimilated and incorporated into amino acids or used for other metabolic purposes (Strock 2008). Urease is a nickel-containing enzyme that catalyses the conversion of urea to ammonia and carbonic acid (Reed 2001). The *ureC* gene is the largest of the genes encoding urease functional subunits and contains several highly conserved regions (Su et al. 2013).

Nitrification is the biological oxidation of ammonia (NH_3) or ammonium (NH_4^+) to oxidized N in the form of nitrite (NO_2^-) and further to nitrate (NO_3^-). Nitrification is of pivotal importance in agricultural systems since it increases the mobility of N through the soil matrix, strongly influencing N retention in the system (Norton and Ouyang 2019). Ammonia oxidation is considered to be the rate-limiting step of nitrification and is catalysed by the ammonia monooxygenase enzyme (AMO), which is encoded by the *amoA* gene (Li et al. 2015).

Denitrification is the reduction of nitrate (NO_3^-) to nitrous oxide or dinitrogen and is the major biological mechanism by which fixed nitrogen returns to the atmosphere from soil and water. This removal of soluble nitrogen oxide (N_2O) from the biosphere is of great importance in agriculture, where it can account for significant losses of nitrogen fertilizer from soil (Henry et al. 2004). A phylogenetically broad group of bacteria can reduce nitrate (NO_3^-) into nitrite (NO_2^-), which can be then reduced into gaseous nitrogen compounds by denitrification or into NH_4^+ by dissimilatory nitrate reduction in ammonium (DNRA). Denitrification is the dominant process in soils and lake sediment. The ability of facultative anaerobic bacteria to respire nitrate when oxygen is limiting has been ascribed mainly to the activity of a membrane bound nitrate reductase encoded by the *narGHJ* operon (Philippot and Højberg 1999). For nitrite reduction, two different types of nitrite reductase have been characterized: copper nitrite reductase encoded by the *nirK* gene and a cytochrome *cd1*-nitrite reductase encoded by the *nirS* gene (Zumft 1997).

Nitrogen-fixing microorganisms are globally significant in that they provide the only natural biological source of fixed nitrogen in the biosphere. These organisms enzymatically transform dinitrogen gas from the atmosphere (N_2) into ammonium (NH_4^+) equivalents needed for biosynthesis of essential cellular macromolecules. The *nifH* gene, encoding the nitrogenase reductase subunit, is the most widely sequenced marker gene used to identify nitrogen-fixing bacteria and archaea (Gaby and Buckley 2012).

Carbon fixation is the assimilation of inorganic C (CO_2) to organic compounds by living organisms. The Calvin-Benson-Bassham cycle is the major pathway for CO_2 fixation (Shively et al. 1986), and the most abundant protein on Earth, ribulose-1,5-biphosphate carboxylase/oxygenase (RubisCO), catalyses the first, rate-limiting step in the Calvin cycle (Ellis 1979). The large subunit of form I RubisCO is encoded by the *cbbL* gene in bacteria (Kusian and Bowien 2006). I RubisCO proteins can be subdivided into two major groups, the green-like and red-like groups (Watson and Tabita 2006). In this protocol, we choose the *cbbL* red-like genes to quantify carbon-fixing microorganisms.

Carbon degradation, as plant litter decomposition, is a major source of organic carbon in soils and a key step in nutrient recycling (Berg et al. 2001). Fungi are considered key players in organic matter decomposition in soil because of their ability to produce a wide range of extracellular enzymes, which allows them to efficiently attack the recalcitrant lignocellulose matrix that other organisms are unable to decompose (Kjøller, Struwe, and Kjøller 1982; De Boer et al. 2005). Cellulose is the main structural component of higher plant cell walls, representing 35–50 % of plant dry weight, and through decomposition and transformation makes up much of soil organic matter (Lynd, Wyman, and Gerngross 1999). The Glycoside hydrolase encoding GH7 gene is widely used to evaluate cellulose degradation (Merlin et al. 2014; Hu et al. 2019; Tian et al. 2017).

REAGENTS

1. Soil DNA extracted according to the method described in chapter 4.3.1 of this Handbook.
2. Ice
3. 70% Ethanol
4. PCR Buffer
5. BSA
6. Primers
7. TE buffer × 10: pH 8.0, 100 mL of 1 mol/L Tris-HCl pH 8.0, 20 mL of 50 mmol/L EDTA pH 8.0 in 880 mL of molecular grade water.
8. TE buffer × 1: 100 mL of TE buffer × 10 in 900 mL of H₂O.
9. Molecular-biology-grade water
10. Agarose
11. SYBR Safe DNA stain
12. DNA ladder with known lengths and concentrations of fragments.
13. NucleoMag® NGS Bead Suspension
14. pGEM®-T Easy Vector Systems with competent cells (Promega)
15. LB plates with ampicillin/IPTG/X-Gal
16. LB Broth
17. Glycerol
18. Ampicilline sodium, C₁₆H₁₈N₃NaO₄S (CAS No. 69-52-3)
19. Qubit™ dsDNA HS Assay Kit (Invitrogen™)
20. ISOLATE II Plasmid Mini Kit (Bioline)
21. SYBR Green® qPCR kit

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- PCR hood
- PCR thermocycler
- Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer (Invitrogen™)
- Horizontal electrophoresis system
- Gel imaging system
- Water bath
- Shaking incubator
- Autoclave
- Oven
- Real-time PCR thermocycler
- Filtered tips
- Pipettes
- Low DNA binding eppendorfs
- PCR tubes
- Syringe filters
- qPCR tubes
- Cold well-loading block

PROCEDURE

1.

qPCR standard preparation
 qPCR standards targeting a sequence of the microbial gene of interest (GOI) are obtained from DNA extracted from soil samples according to chapter 5.3.1 of this Handbook. To select the appropriate amplicon to settle down each qPCR assay, primer pairs listed in Table 5.3.4.1 will be used for each GOI. First, using the DNA mentioned above as the template, PCR reactions will be conducted with the primer sets from Table 5.3.4.1, the reaction mixture described in Table 5.3.4.2. and the corresponding PCR cycling conditions described in Tables 5.3.4.3 to 5.3.4.9.

Table 5.3.4.1. PCR primers set for quantitative analysis

Function	Target gene	Gene definition	Primer name	Primer sequence (5' – 3')	Annealing temp. (°C)	Amplicon size (bp)	Reference
Ammonification	ureC	urease	ureC-F ureC-R	TGGGCCTTAAATHCAYGARGAYTG GGTGGTGGCACACCATNANCATRTC	55	340	Reed et al. (2001)
Nitrification	amoA	ammonia monooxygenase	amoA1F amoA1R	GGGGTTTCTACTGGTGGT CCCCTCKGSAAGCCCTTCTTC	57	491	Rotthauwe et al. (1997)
Denitrification	narG	nitrate reductase	narG1960m2F narG250m2R	TAYGTSGGGCAGGARAACCTG CGTAGAAGAAGCTGGTGCTGTT	56	110	López-Gutiérrez et al. (2004)
Denitrification	nirK	nitrite reductase	nirK876F nirK1040R	ATYGGCGGVCA YGGCGA GCCTCGATCAGRTTRTGGTT	58	165	Henry et al. (2004)
N₂ fixation	nifH	nitrogenase reductase	PoIF PoIR	TGCGAYCCSAARGCBGACTC ATSGCCATCATYTCRCCGGA	55	342	Poly et al. (2001)
Carbon fixation	cbbL	cbbL red-like gene	cbbL-RedF cbbL-RedR	AAGGAYGACGAGAACATC TCGGTCGGSGTGTAGTTGAA	57		Selesi et al. (2005)
Carbon degradation	GH7 (fungal)	cellulose degradation	GH7-F GH7-R	GAGATCAAGCGCYTCTAYGTBCA GTCRAGCCASAGCATGTTGG	56	242	Tian et al. (2017)
Cloning site			SP6 T7	ATTTAGGTGACACTATAG TAATACGACTCACTATAGGG			

Table 5.3.4.2. qPCR reaction mixture.

Reagent	Initial Conc.	Vol/rxn (uL)	Final Conc.
Sybr Green Bioline	2x	10	1x
BSA	20 mg/mL	0.6	0.6 mg/mL
Forward Primer	10 uM	0.8	400 nM
Reverse Primer	10 uM	0.8	400 nM
DNA template	2 ng/ul	5	10 ng
Sterile H ₂ O	***	2.8	***
Total volume		20	

Table 5.3.4.3. ureC cycling conditions.

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95 °C	10 min
Denaturation	40	95 °C	30 sec
Annealing		55 °C	30 sec
Extension		72 °C	30 sec

Table 5.3.4.4. amoA PCR cycling conditions.

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95°C	10 min
Denaturation	35	95°C	25 sec
Annealing		57°C	25 sec
Extension		72°C	40 sec
Extension		72°C	10 min

Table 5.3.4.5. narG cycling conditions.

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time	
Denaturation	1	95 °C	10 min	
Denaturation	6	95 °C	15 sec	
Annealing		65 to 60 °C	30 sec	Touchdown (annealing temperature progressively decreased by 1C by cycle)
Extension		72 °C	30 sec	
Reading		80 °C	15 sec	
Denaturation	40	95 °C	15 sec	
Annealing		60 °C	30 sec	
Extension		72 °C	30 sec	

Table 5.3.4.6. nirK cycling conditions.

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time	
Denaturation	1	95 °C	10 min	
Denaturation	6	95 °C	15 sec	
Annealing		63 to 58 °C	30 sec	Touchdown (annealing temperature progressively decreased by 1C by cycle)
Extension		72 °C	30 sec	
Reading		80 °C	15 sec	
Denaturation	40	95 °C	15 sec	
Annealing		58 °C	30 sec	
Extension		72 °C	30 sec	

Table 5.3.4.7. nifH cycling conditions.

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95 °C	10 min
Denaturation	40	95 °C	60 sec
Annealing		55 °C	60 sec
Extension		72 °C	60 sec

Table 5.3.4.8. cbbL cycling conditions.

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95 °C	10 min
Denaturation	40	95 °C	60 sec
Annealing		57 °C	2 min
Extension		72 °C	2 min

Table 5.3.4.9. GH7 cycling conditions.

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95 °C	10 min
Denaturation	40	95 °C	10 sec
Annealing		56 °C	30 sec
Extension		72 °C	30 sec

The expected size of the qPCR standard amplicons (PCR products from the above reactions) are verified by electrophoresis on 2% agarose gel in TBE buffer stained with SYBR Safe® DNA gel stain. Amplicons are purified with NucleoMag® NGS Bead Suspension according to the manufacturer instructions and quantified with Qubit™ dsDNA HS Assay Kit following the manual. Make sure you get at least 10 ng/μl of PCR product.

2.

Cloning of qPCR standard

- The same day after purifying the PCR product obtained in the PCR reactions mentioned above (Tables 5.3.4.3 to 5.3.4.9.), the ligation should be started. If the PCR product is stored, the A-Overhangs left by the polymerase may detach from the product and ligation efficiency will go down.
- The ligation is made using the pGEM®-T Easy Vector Systems kit from Promega following the manufacturer instructions but incubating the ligation reaction overnight instead of a few hours.
- Transform your competent cells (108 cfu/μg DNA) that are provided with the kit, with the ligation mixture following the kit's instructions and plate 100 μL aliquots of the cells suspension onto LB/Amp/IPTG/X-Gal solid medium. Incubate the Petri dishes at 37°C overnight in the dark for no more than 13 h. This process will facilitate white or blue colour development of the colonies.
- For screening of the recombinant clone, pick three white colonies per GOI (colonies containing the PCR product) and a blue one. Transfer them to liquid LB media with Ampicillin and incubate overnight at 37°C.
- Extract the plasmid using the Isolate II Plasmid Mini Kit from Bioline.
- To make sure you get the desired product size, run a test PCR for the white and blue colonies for each GOI using the primers listed in Table 5.3.4.1. with the reaction mixture of Table 5.3.4.2 and the cycling conditions described in Tables 5.3.4.3 to 5.3.4.9.
- Quantify the plasmids with Qubit™ dsDNA HS Assay Kit.

3.

qPCR standard curve

The qPCR standard curve is performed on serial dilution of the standard plasmid ranging from 10⁸ to 10¹ copies per reaction. The GOI is amplified by using the specific primers pair listed in Table 5.3.4.1., the reaction mixture described in Table 5.3.4.10, and the cycling program described in Tables 5.3.4.3. to 5.3.4.9. replacing the final extension by a dissociation stage (melt analysis) by gradually increasing the temperature from 60°C to 95°C. Standard dilutions and non-template controls (NCT) made of molecular grade water should be amplified in triplicate.

Table 5.3.4.10. qPCR reaction mixture.

Reagent	Initial Conc.	Vol/rxn (μL)	Final Conc.
SYBR Green®	2x	10	1x
BSA	20 mg/mL	0.6	0.6 mg/mL
Forward Primer	10 μM	0.8	400 nM
Reverse Primer	10 μM	0.8	400 nM
Plasmid standard	***	2	***
Sterile H ₂ O	***	5.8	***
Total volume		20	

At the end of the assay, the results are analysed using the automatic option of the thermocycler. The qPCR is validated with the following observations:

- (1) no amplification in NTC reactions,
- (2) a single dissociation peak for each dilution of qPCR standard,
- (3) a linear calibration curve (standard curve) with R² ≥ 98 %.

The qPCR calibration curve gives the number of cycle threshold (Ct) as a function of the amount of the log of the number of copy of standard sequences. The efficiency of the qPCR assay, which is calculated by the thermocycler software, is estimated from the calibration curve formula:

where,

$$Ct = \alpha \times q + c$$

Ct is measured cycle threshold;
 α is the slope of the calibration curve;
 q is the log copy number of qPCR standard;
 c is the ordinate at the origin (Ct for 1 copy of qPCR standard).

$$E = 10^{\left(-\frac{1}{\alpha}\right)} - 1$$

where E is the efficiency of the calibration assay and α is the slope of the calibration curve.

It shall be stated that a calibration curve having a slope equal to -3.32 is 100 % efficient. Therefore, a 10-fold-dilution of a given DNA template gives a Ct difference of 3.32 for a qPCR assay 100 % efficient (i.e. if 108 Ct = 10, so 107 Ct = 13.32).

4.

DNA inhibition test

Inhibition in qPCR occurs when components used in qPCR hinder the activity of the (Taq) polymerase. Such a component is the intercalating fluorescent dye SYBR Green® itself used in qPCR. However, inhibition in qPCR usually refers to impurities, such as humic acid substances, co-purified with sample nucleic acids. These impurities may have an impact on PCR efficiency, thus delaying the amplification and therefore decreasing the samples copy number in absolute quantification. Inhibition is tested the following way:

- Spike 104 copies of plasmid DNA to soil DNA and perform a qPCR using SP6 and T7 primers.
- The amplification reaction is performed with the reaction mixture described in Table 4.3.4.10 including the soil DNA dilutions to be tested, three positive controls containing only plasmid DNA, and three NTC. The qPCR cycling program is shown in the following table and it will include a final dissociation stage (melt analysis).

Table 5.3.4.12. Inhibition test qPCR cycling conditions.

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95°C	15 min
Denaturation	30	95°C	15 sec
Annealing		55°C	30 sec
Extension		72°C	30 sec
Melt curve	1	65-95°C	2-5 sec/step*

*temperature progressively increased by 0.25°C increments

The inhibition test is validated by observing the following:

- a) no amplification for NTC,
- b) similar Ct values in qPCR performed from spiked soil DNA extract and plasmid only DNA.

Soil DNA dilution showing no inhibition is chosen as the template to perform the qPCR assay.

5.

qPCR assays

Once we have come out with a proper standard curve and obtained a DNA template free of inhibitors, the qPCR assay can be run for our DNA samples extracted from soil according to chapter 3.1 of this Handbook. 10⁸ to 10¹ dilutions of the standard plasmid are run in every qPCR assay to create the standard curve and obtain an absolute quantification. The qPCR assay targeting the GOI will be performed on each soil DNA template at the dilution showing no inhibition exactly as described in “3. qPCR standard curve” with the only difference that both standards and DNA templates will be performed in duplicate.

CALCULATIONS

In this section the calculation of the copy number of the GOI in the soil DNA extract is described. The calibration curve and qPCR efficiency shall be calculated for each assay and recorded with the estimated number of copies of the GOI. The copy number of GOI can be calculated to the copy number per ng of soil DNA or per g of soil with the following formulas:

(I) Estimation of the number of sequences of the GOI per ng of soil DNA

$$I \text{ (GOI/ng DNA)} = (\text{GOI in assay}) / (\text{volume of template in assay } (\mu\text{L}) \times \text{concentration of template in assay (ng}/\mu\text{L}))$$

(II) Estimation of the number of sequences of the GOI per g of soil

$$II \text{ (GOI/g soil)} = (I \times \text{extracted DNA from soil (ng)}) / (\text{soil sample from which DNA is extracted (in g of dry mass equivalent)})$$

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5.4. WHOLE MICROBIAL DIVERSITY: PLFA AND NLFA

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

The study of the structure and diversity of soil microorganisms is a tool widely used to know the changes produced on microbial communities by different environmental disturbances (Kirk et al. 2004). One widely used technique to determine the changes in the microbial community structure is the analysis of the fatty acids (chain length between 14 and 20 C atoms) of different lipid groups: phospholipid fatty acids (PLFA) and neutral lipid fatty acids (NLFA) (Malosso et al. 2004). These lipids play important roles in living cells as either structural components of the cellular membranes (PLFA) or as energy (storage compounds (NLFA) (Ruess and Chamberlain 2010).

Within the neutral lipids, the triglycerides, formed by three fatty acids linked by ester bonds to a single glycerol molecule, are the most abundant. Since the polar parts are linked (the carboxyl groups of fatty acids and the alcohol group from the glycerol) these neutral lipids are nonpolar and not soluble in water (Nelson et al. 2005).

The phospholipids are formed by fatty acids, glycerol or sphingosine (depending on the type of phospholipids) and a phosphate group. Since 1980, phospholipid fatty acids (PLFA) have been frequently used as biomarkers and to determine both the microbial biomass (total biomass and

biomass of specific groups of microorganisms) and the diversity of microbial communities due to the fact that while some fatty acids are unspecific, others are characteristic of determined microorganisms (White and Findlay 1988). Some fatty acids are more common in prokaryotes and others in eukaryotes, while the triglycerides (and the fatty acids that compose them, NLFAs) are exclusive to eukaryotic organisms (fungi) as storage compounds. The analysis of both types of fatty acids (PLFA and NLFA) helps to improve the microbial community characterization (Bååth 2003).

Table 5.4.1. Fatty acid biomarkers (adapted from Frostergård et al. 1996 and Kaur et al. 2005)

Group	Biomarker
Bacteria	i15:0, a15:0, 15:0, i16:0, 16:1 ω 9, 16:1 ω 7t, i17:0, a17:0, 17:0, cy17:0, 18:1 ω 7, cy19:0
Gram-positive Bacteria	br17:0, br18:0, i17:0, a17:0, i16:0, i16:1, 10Me16:0, 10Me17:0, i15:0, a15:0, 16:1 ω 9, 16:1 ω 7c, 16:1 ω 5*, 18:1 ω 7 and C19:1
Gram-negative Bacteria	cy17:0, cy19:0, r-hydroxy fatty acids, 16:1 ω 9, 16:1 ω 7, 16:1 ω 5, 18:1 ω 7 and 19:1
Fungi	18:2 ω 6 (linoleic acid)
Actinobacteria	10Me16:0, 10Me17:0 and 10Me18:0
Anaerobic Bacteria	Non-ester linked phospholipid fatty acids (NEL-PLFA)
Sulphate Reducing Bacteria (Desulfobacter sp.)	cy17:0 and 10Me16:0 without high level of 10Me18:0
Methanogens: Type I	16:1 ω 8
Methanogens: Type II	18:1 ω 8

*characteristic of arbuscular mycorrhiza within roots (Frostegård et al, 2011)

The carbon chains of PLFA can be saturated (carbons appear linked by simple bonds) or unsaturated (when double bonds appear between carbons) (Benatar et al. 2011). Carbon α is the one that belongs to the carboxyl group, while the furthest is carbon ω . However, when numbering them the 1 is the furthest from the carboxyl group (the ω carbon). When naming them, the nomenclature usually used is “total carbon number of the fatty acid:number of double bonds ω position of double bonds from the methyl end of the molecule separated by commas”. To indicate a cis or trans configuration, the letter “c” or “t” is usually added. The prefixes “i” and “a” indicated iso- or anteiso-branching; “br” indicates unknown methyl branching position (Ran-Ressler et al. 2014). If there is a methyl group in carbon 10, “10Me” is added, “cy” if there is a cyclopropane, and “di” if is a dicarboxylic fatty acid. The prefixes “p” and “r” point that the OH groups of the OH fatty acid are in the positions 2 and 3 respectively. If there is a strange or difficult-to-describe configuration, “br” is added (Bååth 2003; Kaur et al. 2005).

PLFA and NLFA soil microbial community analysis can be divided into four parts: extraction of lipids from the soil, fractionation of the different types of lipids (neutral lipids, glycolipids and polar lipids), mild alkaline methanolysis of the different lipids to convert their components, the fatty acids, into volatile methyl esters, and analysis of these by gas chromatography (Frostegård et al. 1993; Díaz-Raviña et al. 2006).

PROCEDURE

Preparation of reagents

- 5 N NaOH solution. Weight 200 g of NaOH in a volumetric flask and bring up to 1000 ml with deionized water.
- 0.15 M citrate buffer, pH 4: dilute 28.82 g of citrate acid in 850 ml of water and add the 5 N NaOH solution to adjust the pH to 4 before dilute to 1000 ml with deionized water. This solution must be prepared at the time of use.
- Bligh and Dyer (B&D) reagent: mixt CHCl₃:MeOH:citrate buffer in a proportion 1:2:0.8 (v/v/v).
- Methanol:toluene: Mix both solutions in a proportion 1:1 (v/v)
- Hexane:CHCl₃ Mix both solutions in a proportion 4:1 (v/v)
- Acetic acid 1 M. Add 57.2 ml of acetic acid in a volumetric flask and bring up to 1000 ml with deionized water.
- KOH 0.2 M in methanol. Weight 11.22 g of KOH in a volumetric flask and bring up to 1000 ml with methanol. This solution must be prepared at the time of use.
- Standard methyl nonadecanoate (Std19:0, molecular weight 312.54 g). Dissolve 115 µg of the standard in 5 ml of hexane (concentration 23 µg ml⁻¹). This solution must be prepared daily.
- Detergent free of phosphates (2% in deionized water type II).

1. Lipid extraction

- Weight between 0.5 and 6 grams of dry soil (0.5-1.5 g if high OM (Organic Matter) content, 3-6 g if low OM content) and place in 50 ml Teflon tubes. Moist, air-dried, frozen or freeze-dried soil samples are used. Blanks without soil, treated under the same conditions, are prepared in each batch of samples.
- Add 10 ml of B&D reagent, shake with vortex for 1 min and keep for 2 hours at room temperature to allow the compounds to be extracted.
- Centrifuge for 11 minutes at 1677 x g and transfer the supernatant to a 50 ml Teflon or glass tube.
- To complete the extraction, repeat the process, adding 5 ml of B&D to the residue. Add the supernatants to the 50 ml tube mixing both supernatants.
- Add 4 ml of chloroform and 4 ml of citrate buffer to the extract obtained and to shake in the vortex for 1 min.
- The suspension is left overnight at room temperature to extract the lipids in the organic phase. Another option is to centrifuge for 11 min at 1677 x g.
- The lower phase (organic) is extracted with a Pasteur pipette. An aliquot of 3 ml (high OM content soil) or 5 ml (low OM content soil) of this phase is dried at 40 °C under a flow of nitrogen in a dry block heater. The rest of the extract is stored at 4 °C until the end of the procedure.
- Dry samples are frozen a -20 °C. In case of continuing with the fractionation on the same day, it is not necessary to freeze.

2. Fractionation

The second step consists in separating the different lipid fractions.

- Dried samples (and thawed) are re-suspended using 100 µl of chloroform and agitation in the Vortex. This suspension is added to a silica column (SPE-SI), previously placed on glass tubes of 25 ml. Repeat this process twice by adding 100 µL of CHCl₃.
- Once the lipids have been retained in the silica column, reagents of increasing polarity are applied successively to eluate the different lipid fractions collected in different glass tubes:

- 1.5 ml of chloroform to elute the neutral lipids
- 6 ml of acetone in two 3 ml steps to separate the glycolipids
- 1.5 ml of methanol to eluate the polar lipids
- At the end of the fractionation, the contents of the tubes are dried at 40 °C under a flow of nitrogen in a dry block heater

In this method, the first (neutral lipids) and last (polar lipids) fractions will be analysed and the procedures detailed below are the same for both and must be performed with each of the samples.

3. *Mild alkaline methanolysis (Transesterification)*

The third step involves a transesterification reaction to convert the fatty acids of the phospholipids (PLFA) and neutral lipids (NLFA) into volatile derivatives that can be measured by gas chromatography.

- Add 100 µl of the Std19:0 (23 µg ml⁻¹ concentration) to all samples
- Evaporate the hexane under a flow of nitrogen.
- Add 1 ml of the MeOH:toluene (1:1) mixture and shake in a vortex for 5 s.
- Add 1 ml of 0.2 M KOH in methanol, shake in a vortex 5 seconds and incubate in a bath (at 37°C) for 15 min. Let the samples cool some minutes at room temperature.
- Add 2 ml of hexane:chloroform (4:1), 0.3 ml of 1M acetic acid and 2 ml of water.
- Stir for 1 min in a vortex, check that the pH of the lower phase is around 6, centrifuge 11 min at 1677 x g and remove with a Pasteur pipette the upper phase to a glass container. This step must be repeated by adding 2 ml of hexane:chloroform, stirring and centrifuging again.
- Evaporate the solvents in the samples under a flow of nitrogen without heating. It is important to remove the samples when the last drop of the solvent evaporates to avoid losses of the more volatile fatty acids. Freeze the dry samples at -20 °C until its further analysis.

4. *GC Analysis*

The last step is the sample analysis on a gas chromatograph with a flame ionization detector (GC-FID). A HP5 (phenilmethyl silicone) capillary column (50 m longitude, 0.2 mm internal diameter, 0.33 µm film thickness) is used.

- Chromatographic conditions (Frostergård et al. 1993):
 - Carrier gas was He (flow 0.8 ml/min)
 - Detector temperature: 230 °C
 - Injector temperature: 230 °C, injection was made in splitless mode
 - Oven temperature program: initial temperature 80 °C for 1 min, increasing first with 20°C min⁻¹ to 160 °C and after with 5°C min⁻¹ to reach 270°C, remain at this temperature 5 min.
- The frozen sample is thawed to room temperature.
- Add 100 µl of hexane to dissolve the sample and transfer to GC vials.
- 1 µl of this solution is analysed by GC-FID by duplicated.
- The PLFAs and NLFAs were separated, identified by the relative retention times compared with those obtained for the standards and the peak areas are quantified by adding, before the transesterification step, methyl nonadecanoate (Std19:0) as internal standard.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- 50 ml Teflon centrifuge tubes with screw cap
- Glass tubes with screw cap
- Erlenmeyer flasks
- Beakers
- Volumetric flasks
- Graduated cylinder
- Pasteur pipettes
- Micro-centrifugation tubes of 1.5 or 2 ml
- Petri dishes
- GC vials
- Spatulas and tweezers
- Racks
- LCR Cartridges Bond Elut SI (SPE) normal phase (polar)

REAGENTS

- Citric acid (C₆H₈O₇)
- Sodium hydroxide (NaOH)
- Potassium hydroxide (KOH)
- Acetone (C₃H₆O)
- Acetic acid (CH₃COOH)
- Chloroform (CHCl₃)
- Hexane (C₆H₁₄)
- Methanol (CH₃OH)
- Toluene (C₇H₈)
- Methyl nonadecanoate (Std19:0, C₂₀H₄₀O₂)
- Water deionized type I (Resistivity 18 Ω cm⁻¹, C < 5 ppb) used to prepare the reagents and water deionized type II (Resistivity > 5 Ω cm⁻¹, TOC < 30 ppb) to wash the material
- Phosphate-free detergent

REMARKS

Due to the high sensitivity of the method, impurities from the reagents and ineffective cleaning of the material used can cause serious contamination problems that can be detected in the blanks (without soil).

It is important to wash the material with a phosphate-free detergent. All clean and dry glass material (non-volumetric) must also undergo a heat treatment at 400°C for at least 6 hours to eliminate any other organic matter including lipid contaminants.

All reagents used are analytical grade, except the n-hexane, which is solvent to GC chromatography.

During the process, the following security measures must be taken into account: a) work in the gas extraction cabinet and, if it is not possible, use a mask with a filter to organic solvents, b) wear dust mask to weigh the powder reagents and c) use gloves and safety glasses whenever there is any possibility of splashes.

CALCULATIONS

Each identified PLFA is quantified (nmol g⁻¹ of dry soil) in each sample using the following equation:

$$PLFA (nmol g^{-1}) = \frac{Area PLFA_{sample}}{Area 19:0_{sample}} \times CI_{Std19:0 added} \times R \times V \times \frac{1}{dry\ soil\ weight}$$

Where:

- Area PLFA_{sample} is the peak area of each PLFA identified in the sample
- Area 19:0_{sample} is the peak area of PLFA 19:0 in the same sample
- CI_{Std19:0} is the amount of internal standard, methyl nonadecanoate (Std19:0) added in step 3 to each sample, expressed in nmol.

$$CI_{Std19:0 added} (nmol) = \frac{23000\ ng\ ml^{-1} \times 10^{-1}\ ml}{312.54\ ng\ nmol^{-1}} = 7.36\ nmol$$

- R is the correction factor determined by the recovery of the internal standard to each sample, calculated as:

$$R = \frac{Area_{19:0 blank}}{Area_{19:0 sample}}$$

Where

- Area_{19:0 blank} is the peak area of PLFA 19:0 in the blank
- Area_{19:0 sample} is the peak area of PLFA 19:0 in the sample
- V is the factor obtained from the quotient between the total volume of CHCl₃ used in the lipids extraction, 7.95 ml, and the aliquot volume used to fractionation (3 or 5 ml) (step 1).

The procedure for the quantification of neutral lipids fatty acids (NLFAs) is the same as described for the PLFAs.

Total PLFA microbial biomass estimations

The sum of the content of all the PLFAs (around a total of 30-35 unspecific and specific to different microbial groups) identified and quantified of each sample were used to obtain the total PLFA biomass (nmol g⁻¹ of dry soil)

Microbial PLFA biomass of specific microbial groups

The content of each PLFAs biomarkers characteristic of the specific microbial groups are summed to obtain the PLFA biomass of these groups.

For example, the bacterial PLFA biomass is determined following the equation (Frostegard et al. 1996)

$$TB = \Sigma i15:0 + a15:0 + 15:0 + i16:0 + 16:1\omega9 + 16:1\omega7t + i17:0 + a17:0 + 17:0 + cy17:0 + 18:1\omega7 + cy19:0$$

TB, is the bacterial PLFA biomass (nmol g⁻¹ of dry soil)

In the same way, the biomass of other microbial groups was obtained by the sum of their specific PLFAs biomarkers (fungi, Gram-positive bacteria, Gram-negative bacteria, actinobacteria, anaerobic bacteria, etc.) (see Table 5.1.). It should be noticed that the criteria of the PLFAs characteristics of specific microbial groups could differ among authors (Frostegård et al. 1993; 1996; Zelles 1999; Kaur et al. 2005; Díaz-Raviña et al. 2006); thus, in these biomass estimations the reference used should be included.

Ratios between different biomarker fatty acids

The relationships between some specific fatty acids are used to obtain information on the composition or the microbial status of soil microbial communities. The mostly used ratios are the following:

- *Fungal PLFA/Bacterial PLFA ratio*: provides information about the predominance of these main microbial groups, which play a different role in soil (Frostegård et al. 1996; 2011).
- *Gram-negative to Gram-positive bacterial PLFA ratio*: provides information concerning the microbial status of microorganisms (Zelles 1999; Kirk et al. 2004; Frostegård et al. 2011)
- *Ratios of PLFAs trans/PLFAs cis of monounsaturated fatty acids (16:1 ω 7t/16:1 ω 7c, 18:1 ω 7t/18:1 ω 7c) or cyclo/mono-unsaturated precursor (cy17:0/16:1 ω 7c and cy19:0/18:1 ω 7c)*: provides information on stress or starvation (Zelles 1999; Kirk et al. 2004).
- *NLFAs/PLFAs ratios for specific fatty acids*: provides information on nutrient status or physiological conditions of soil fungi (Bååth 2003).
- *PLFA or NLFA diversity indexes*
- *The richness (R) of the fatty acids is expressed as the total number of PLFAs or NLFAs present in each sample. The diversity of the FAs is calculated with the Shannon index H.*

$$H = \sum_{i=1}^R p_i \ln p_i$$

Where p_i is the relative abundance of each fatty acid in the total sum and R is the number of detected fatty acids.

The equitability of the fatty acids is calculated with the Shannon's evenness E .

$$E = \frac{H}{\ln(R)}$$

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6. SOIL FERTILITY AND POLLUTION ASSESSMENT

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The expression soil fertility refers to the soil ability to maintain the agricultural production . Formerly, fertility was limited to the chemical part, to provide nutrients to increase production, but in recent years other fertilities have been gaining weight and we can distinguish three types: chemical, physical and biological. In the previous chapter, the methods to determine some of the characteristics of the biological fertility of a soil (**5. Assessment of soil biodiversity**), were summarized, while in this chapter those characteristics related to chemical fertility will be determined.

Soil is composed of organic and inorganic matter, air and water, and it is common for these elements to experience reactions that include adsorption, weathering, complexation, ion exchange and precipitation. This is crucial from the point of view of fertility and environmental safety, since the compounds and nutrients that are introduced in the soil can undergo a series of transformations that will be conditioned by the characteristics of that soil. However, that also means that if the chemical characteristics of a soil are known, it is possible to predict the behaviour and fate of these external inputs.

When analyzing the chemical fertility of the soil, it is important to take into account contamination, that is, the presence of materials that can be harmful to the crops or to soil microorganisms. This type of substances, whose presence is usually associated with intensive agriculture and with the abuse of inputs such as pesticides, can reduce soil fertility as well as their biological activity.

The chemical properties that will be considered in this work as well as the project members in charge of each analysis are summarized in Table 6.1.

Table 6.1. Chemical analysis used to characterize the samples and partners in charge of each analysis.

CHEMICAL PROPERTIES MEASURED	
ANALYSIS TYPE	PARTNER IN CHARGE
Soil pH	UVIGO
Soil Salinity	UVIGO
Total nitrogen	UVIGO
Inorganic nitrogen (nitrates and ammonium)	UPCT
Available P in the soil (Bray / Olsen)	UVIGO
Effective cation exchange capacity and Ca, Mg and K availability	UPCT
Available Fe, Mn, Cu, Zn and Mo	UVIGO
Available Boron	UVIGO
Total pesticides	UVIGO
Glyphosate and AMPA	UVIGO

6.1. SOIL PH

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

The pH is the negative logarithm of the concentration of hydrogen ions (H^+) expressed in mol L^{-1} , assuming that concentration and activity of an ion are comparable in strongly diluted aqueous solution. The pH of a soil is conditioned by the base-forming cations (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ and K^+), and by the acid-forming cations (Fe^{2+} or Fe^{3+} , H^+ and Al^{3+}) (Mccauley, Jones, and Olson-Rutz 2017). The pH is a fundamental property of soils since it determines solubility, concentration in solution, mobility and ionic form of nutrients (Fageria and Nascente 2014), and, therefore, their availability (Horrocks and Vallentine 1999). Some elements are more available at acidic pHs, such as nitrogen, iron or copper, and others such as calcium, magnesium and sodium are easily leached at acidic pH and are more available in basic soils (Figure 6.1.1.).

Figure 6.1.1. Effect of the soil pH in the availability of some nutrients. The wider the blue line, the more available the element (from Roques et al. 2013)

Usually, a 1:5 soil suspension in distilled water is used to measure soil pH (Ditzler, Scheffe, and Monger 2017). However, certain electrolytes can also be used for different purposes. Sometimes, instead of water, a 0.01M solution of calcium chloride (CaCl_2) is applied because it dampens the suspension effect, the variations in the soil:solution ratios and the initial saline concentration. The use of potassium chloride (KCl) is also common due to its ability to displace H^+ and Al^{3+} cations, adsorbed to exchangeable sites of soil colloids, to the solution leading to lower pH values (Kome et al. 2018). Soil pH values measured in neutral salt solutions (CaCl_2 or KCl) is often referred as exchangeable acidity, being narrowly related to the degree of the cation exchange complex by aluminium. Soil pH has an strong influence on crop growth and thus, some crops develop properly in water with a pH in the range of 6-7 (Daniels 2016), while others prefer soils with more acidic conditions (Miller 2016).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Analytical balance (0.01 g)
- Greiner tubes of 15mL
- Spatula
- Shaker
- Distilled water
- Potassium Chloride (KCl)
- Calcium Chloride (CaCl₂)
- pH-meter (preferably with an automatic temperature compensation probe)
- Buffers (pH 4.00, 7.02 and 9.21)

CALCULATIONS

The difference between the soil pH measured in KCl and measured in H₂O ($\Delta\text{pH} = \text{pH KCl} - \text{pH H}_2\text{O}$) is calculated to determine if the negative charges in soil colloids predominate, conferring it as cation exchange capacity ($\Delta\text{pH} < 0$). Otherwise, if $\Delta\text{pH} > 0$, soil has an anion exchange capacity due to the predominance of positively charged colloids (Kome et al. 2018).

REMARKS

At the start of pH measurements (or when a pronounced change in pH value between two successive samples is observed), it is recommended to extend the pH measurement period for a few minutes (using the continuous mode if it is available) in order to favour the stabilization of the measurement before recording the final value. It is possible to establish a correlation between the organic matter content of a soil and its pH in CaCl₂ (Fuentes et al. 2019).

PROCEDURE

The procedure to measure pH is as follows:

1. Weigh 2 g of soil (sieved, 2 mm).
2. Add 10 mL of distilled water.
3. Shake for 1 h.
4. Let the suspension rest for 1 h.
5. Calibrate the pH-meter with pH 4.00, 7.02 and 9.21 standards
6. Measure with a pH-meter before the next 2 h.

The procedure is repeated twice replacing distilled water with a 1M solution of KCl, and a 0.01 M solution of CaCl₂, always maintaining the same weight:volume ratio (1: 5). Hence, three soil pH values measured in different solutions (water, 1 M KCl or 0.01 M CaCl₂) are routinely obtained. Two hours of equilibration are needed before measuring the pH.

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6.2. SOIL SALINITY

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

The salinity of a soil is the amount of dissolved salts present in the aqueous phase of that soil (Kalev and Toor, 2018). These salts have a series of effects on water movement, soil structure, and microbial and plant diversity (Artiola et al., 2019). For example, a high concentration of salts can limit the growth of crops.

Salinization is the high concentration of salts in a soil, and can occur for various reasons, for example, the lack of rainfall, the presence of a water table near the surface that evaporates easily, or the use of irrigation water with high salt content. It is estimated that 7% of the Earth's area presents salinity problems (Gupta and Abrol, 1990). Furthermore, it is a growing problem that can already be favored by the increase in global mean temperature caused by climate change and by the increase in salinity in water resources (McFarlane and Williamson, 2002).

The concentration of salts in the soil and, therefore, of ions in solution, is related to electrical conductivity (EC): those soil suspensions that have more ions are capable of conducting an electric current more easily. For this reason, the method for determine soil salinity is based on the standard method for measuring electrical conductivity (Soil Science Division Staff, 2017). Based on conductivity, a classification of soils can be made: those soils with a conductivity less than 2 dS m⁻¹ are considered non-saline, while those with a conductivity greater than 16 dS m⁻¹ are considered strongly saline (Figure 6.2.1)

Class		Electrical conductivity dS/m (mmhos/cm)
0	Non saline	0-2
1	Very slightly saline	2-4
2	Slightly saline	4-8
3	Moderately saline	8-16
4	Strongly saline	≥16

Figure 6.2.1. Soil classification based on electrical conductivity (adapted from Soil Science Division Staff, 2017).

PROCEDURE

The procedure is the following

- Two grams of soil are weighed in a 25mL beaker.
- 10 mL of distilled water are added.
- The mixture is stirred for one hour.
- The conductivity meter is calibrated with a 0.01 M KCl solution (with an electrical conductivity of 1412 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$).
- The suspension is measured by introducing the conductivity electrode.

PROCEDURE

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EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Conductivity meter
- Beaker
- KCl standard solution 0.01 M (1412 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ at 25°C)
- Balance
- Pipette.
- Stirrer.

CALCULATIONS

A rough conversion (Hardie and Doyle, 2012) of electrical conductivity (in mS cm^{-1}) to total dissolved ions (TDI) can be done:

$$TDI (\text{mg L}^{-1}) = CE (\text{mS cm}^{-1}) \times 667$$

And to milliequivalents per liter:

$$\text{Meq L}^{-1} = CE (\text{mS cm}^{-1}) \times 10$$

6.3. TOTAL NITROGEN

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Nitrogen (N) is one of the essential elements for crop development, together with potassium (K) and phosphorus (P). N is distributed across the atmosphere, the biosphere and the lithosphere, but, unlike K and P, N is not found in the rocks, so it must be introduced into the soil through fertilization or through the fixation of the atmospheric N₂ (Figure 6.3.1) (Hofman and Cleemput 2004). The total soil N content is usually between 0.05 and 0.2% by weight, but only a small proportion can be directly assimilated by plants that mainly assimilate the inorganic N species ammonium (NH₄⁺) or nitrate (NO₃⁻).

Figure 6.3.1. Simplified diagram of the terrestrial N cycle (from Lappalainen et al. 2016)

N deficiency is associated with lower crop yields and quality via reduced protein content (Dalal et al. 1991). There is a big difference in phytoavailable N between different soils as it is conditioned by many factors including weather, season, depth, vegetation, crop history, slope, soil texture etc (Lin 2006).

N deficiencies are common in unfertilized soils (Hofman and Cleemput 2004), and it is therefore necessary to fertilize the soil providing this element. N fertilization (in the form of synthetic fertilizers) in intensive agriculture reaches 600 kg per hectare and year in the field, and about 2000 kg in the greenhouse (Escanhoela et al. 2019). It is also possible to provide N by using organic fertilizers or rotations with N-fixing legumes (Crews and Peoples 2004). As can be seen in Figure 6.3.1, the bacteria symbiotically associated with the roots of legumes are a crucial part of the soil N cycle, since they are capable of fixing atmospheric nitrogen.

Total soil N can be determined by a CHN elemental analyzer (see also Section 7.7.). Soil samples are burned at high temperatures in order to liberate the nitrogen, hydrogen and carbon gases. The gases are separated and the amount of nitrogen is measured through a thermal conductivity detector, since the thermal conductivity varies from one element to another.

PROCEDURE

The method used to determine the total nitrogen is the same as the method used for soil carbon (**3.2. Organic Matter and Carbon Content**). About 50 mg of grinded dry soil is weighed in tin capsules and measured with the Elemental Analyzer. The nitrogen standards are also weighed and analysed. The proportions obtained with this method have to be converted into grams of total nitrogen per kilogram of dry soil.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Elemental Analyzer
- Analytical balance (0.0001 g)
- Oven
- Spatulas
- Soil mill
- Tin capsules

CALCULATIONS

The results of total nitrogen are obtained in percentage by weight (g of N in 100 grams of dry soil), a unit that can be converted to grams of N per kilogram of dry soil by multiplying by 10.

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6.4. INORGANIC NITROGEN (NITRATES AND AMMONIUM)

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

(N) is an essential element for the nutrition of plants and microorganisms. Most soil nitrogen is present as organic N compounds with only a small fraction being found in the mineral forms that are directly usable by crop plants. The process of mineralization of organic nitrogen, necessary for its assimilation as a plant nutrient, occurs mainly through ammonification (organic N mineralization to ammonium) and nitrification (oxidation of ammonium into nitrite and nitrate).

Nitrate and ammonium are extracted from soil samples using a 2 M solution of potassium chloride (KCl), and subsequent analysed by ion chromatography (nitrate and nitrite) and spectrophotometry (ammonium) (Sempere et al. 1993; Kandeler and Gerber 1988; Keeny and Nelson 1982). Soil used for the determination of inorganic nitrogen may be kept at 4 °C at field-moist conditions if it is analysed within 3 days of sampling. Alternatively, soil may be stored at -20°C to avoid the loss of mineral N.

PROCEDURE

Nitrate determination

1.

Homogenize the soil sample (manually or mechanically). The soil sample must be transferred into a refrigerated container.

2.

Weigh 2.5 g of sieved field-moist soil (< 2 mm) in a plastic vial, recording the exact weight. Add 25 mL of the deionized water (soil / extractant ratio 1:10).

3.

Shake for 60 min on the rotating plate.

4.

Centrifuge the samples for 2 min at 3000 g. Filter supernatant using syringe filters.

5.

The extract obtained is measured in the ion chromatography equipment.

6.

Prepare a calibration curve from the NO₃⁻ stock solution.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Analytical balance (0.01 g)
- Plastic vials (50 mL)
- Volumetric flask (100 mL)
- Rotating plate
- Plastic test tubes with cup (10 mL)
- Centrifuge
- Syringe filters (0.2 µm)
- Syringe (10 mL)
- Ion chromatography equipment

REAGENTS

- Stock or commercial nitrate solution (1000 mg L⁻¹ NO₃⁻)

CALCULATIONS

$$NO_3^- \text{ (mg kg}^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{(C \times V \times df)}{m}$$

- C is the concentration of nitrate obtained from ion chromatography (mg L⁻¹)
- V is the total volume of the added deionised water (25 mL)
- df is the dilution factor. If it is not applied, it is 1
- m is the weight of the dry soil sample (g) (moisture correction is needed by determination of soil moisture)

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Analytical balance (0.01 g)
- Plastic vials (50 mL)
- Plastic test tubes with cup (10 mL)
- Volumetric flasks (100, 500 and 1000 mL)
- Plastic buckets (2.5 mL)
- Vortex shaker
- Centrifuge
- Automatic pipette (1-5 mL)
- Rotating plate
- Visible / UV spectrophotometer

CALCULATIONS

$$NH_4^+ (mg\ kg^{-1}) = \frac{(C \times V \times df)}{m}$$

- C is the concentration of nitrate obtained from ion chromatography (mg L⁻¹)
- V is the total volume of the added deionised water (25 mL)
- df is the dilution factor. If it is not applied, it is 1
- m is the weight of the dry soil sample (g) (moisture correction is needed by determination of soil moisture)

Ammonium determination

1.

Homogenize the soil sample (manually or mechanically). The soil sample must be transferred in a refrigerator container.

2.

Weigh 2.5 g of sieved soil (< 2 mm) in a plastic vial, recording the exact weight. Add 25 mL of the 2M KCl solution (soil / extractant ratio 1:10).

3.

Shake for 60 min on the rotating plate.

4.

Centrifuge the samples 2 min at 3000 g.

5.

Take a 5 mL aliquot of the supernatant from each sample. For samples with a high ammonium content, pipette 2.5 mL (in this case the dilution factor is 2). Pour the aliquot in a 10 mL test tube. Add 2.5 mL of deionized water to the test tube if 2.5 mL has been pipetted to have a final volume of 5 mL in all tubes.

6.

Prepare tubes to determine the calibration curve. The standards will have concentrations of 0, 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2.5 and 5 mg L⁻¹ of NH₄⁺, and are prepared from the stock solution of 100 mg NH₄⁺ L⁻¹ (Table 6.4.1.). These concentrations will be the dependent variables and the corresponding absorbance values will be the independent variable.

Table 6.4.1. Preparation of standards from the 100 mg stock solution NH₄ + L-1 (Final volume of 10 mL).

NH ₄ + standard concentration (mg L ⁻¹)	
0	0
0.5	0.05
1	0.10
1.5	0.15
2.5	0.25
5	0.5

7. Add 2.5 mL of Salicylate-Na/NaOH solution and 1 mL of 0.1% sodium dichloroisocyanide to all tubes.
8. Cover, shake (using the vortex shaker), and let stand for 30 min in darkness.
9. Then, turn on the spectrophotometer and adjust the wavelength (λ) to 690 nm. Perform the auto-zero with the 0 mg NH₄ + L-1 standard.
10. Measure all standards, including 0 mg NH₄ + mL⁻¹, to perform the calibration curve in which the NH₄ + concentration of the samples and blanks will be calculated.
11. Measure the absorbance of the samples in the spectrophotometer. In the event that any sample gives an absorbance greater than the maximum value of the calibration curve, it is necessary to take less volume of supernatant to make a dilution (step 5).

REAGENTS

- Solution of potassium chloride (2 M KCl): dissolve 149 g of potassium chloride (KCl) in a 1000 mL graduated flask containing approximately 800 mL of H₂O. Fill up to the final volume with deionised water.
- Sodium hydroxide (0.3 M NaOH): dissolve 12 g of NaOH in a 1000 mL graduated flask containing approximately 800 mL of H₂O. Fill up to the final volume with deionized water.
- Sodium salicylate solution: dissolve 85 g of sodium salicylate (C₇H₅NaO₃) and 600 mg of sodium nitroprusside (Na₂ [Fe (CN)₅ NO]). Fill up to 500 mL with deionized water. Store at 4°C.
- Salicylate-Na / NaOH solution: mix equal volumes of 0.3 M NaOH, sodium salicylate and deionized water (1: 1: 1). Prepare daily.
- Solution of sodium dichloroisocyanide (0.1% C₃Cl₂N₃NaO₃) (w:v): dissolve 0.1 g of sodium dichloroisocyanide in 100 mL of deionized water. Prepare daily.
- Ammonium stock solution (100 mg L⁻¹ NH₄⁺): dissolve 0.297 g of NH₄Cl in 1000 mL of 2M KCl

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6.5. AVAILABLE P IN THE SOIL (BRAY / OLSEN)

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

After nitrogen, (N), phosphorus (P) is the second-most important element for plant nutrition (Kauffman 2002). P is a component of nucleic acids (DNA and RNA) and of adenosine triphosphate (ATP); an energy storage molecule essential for life. In plants, P is a crucial element in development (a significant amount of phosphorus is needed for cell division), flowering, fruit ripening and photosynthesis (Weil and Brady 2017).

Intensive agriculture (without the addition of phosphorus) usually results in low P-containing soils on which plant growth is strongly constrained. This type of soils remains unprotected from erosion (Weil and Brady 2017). However, it is also common to find the opposite scenario such as agricultural systems where more phosphorus is added than removed through harvest. In many cases, this phosphorus surplus is mobilized towards groundwater by seepage and finally ends up in freshwaters (rivers and lakes), contributing to generate eutrophic conditions and putting at risk the quantity and quality of drinking water.

In soils, P normally occur in low quantities, and it appears in forms which are not usually available for plant uptake. In addition, highly soluble P forms are used for soil fertilization (as slurries, for example), it is insolubilized quite easily after contact with the soil. This is one of the reasons why agricultural soils are usually fertilized with P in excess.

As only a small proportion of total P in soils is available for plant uptake, more attention should be paid in determining this P fraction. The concentration of available phosphorus can be assessed using different extractant solutions (depending on soil pH). Two main methods can be distinguished depending on soil pH: the Olsen method is recommended to be applied for alkaline soils, whereas for neutral and acidic soils the Bray II method is preferred (Dari et al. 2019).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Magnetic stirrer
- Shaker
- Greiner tubes (50 mL)
- Dispenser
- Beakers
- Analytical balance (0.0001 g)
- Centrifuge
- 0.45 µm Filters
- Sulphuric acid, H₂SO₄
- Sodium hydroxide, NaOH
- Sodium bicarbonate, NaHCO₃
- p-Nitrophenol (NO₂C₆H₄OH)
- Ammonium molybdate [(NH₄)₆Mo₇O₂₄ x 4H₂O]
- Potassium antimony tartrate [(K(SbO) x C₄H₄O₆ x 1/2 H₂O)]
- Ascorbic acid (C₆H₄O₆)
- Potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH₂PO₄)
- Spectrophotometer

CALCULATIONS

To present the results, the phosphorus content is usually referenced to grams of dry soil. For this, we can use the following formula:

$$C_p = (A - B) \frac{V_E}{V_S} \frac{50}{m}$$

Where:

- CP is the extractable phosphorus content in the soil (in mg of P g⁻¹ of dry soil)
- A is the P concentration in the sample (mg mL⁻¹)
- B is the P concentration in the blank (mg mL⁻¹)
- VE is the volume of extractant used (mL).
- VS is the volume of sample measured by spectrophotometry (mL).
- m is the soil mass (g)

PROCEDURE

A) Olsen

Before starting it is necessary to prepare several solutions:

1.

Sulphuric acid solution 2.5 M. Carefully add 140 mL of H₂SO₄ (with 96% purity) to a one-litre volumetric flask containing about 400 mL of water, and dilute to the mark with distilled water.

2.

Sodium hydroxide solution 1M. Dissolve 40 mL of NaOH in distilled water. It is an exothermic solution, so it is necessary to stir and let cool before completing the volume with water.

3.

Sodium bicarbonate solution. In a volume close to one litre (\approx 0.8-0.9 L), dissolve 42 g of sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO₃). The pH of the solution is adjusted to 8.5 (adding drops of the O₂ solution) before completing the volume (1 L).

4.

0.25% solution of p-Nitrophenol. 0.25 g of p-Nitrophenol (NO₂C₆H₄OH) are dissolved with distilled water in a 100 mL volumetric flask, completing the dilution to mark with water.

5.

Ammonium molybdate solution 40g L⁻¹. 40 g of ammonium molybdate [(NH₄)₆Mo₇O₂₄] are weighed, dissolved in distilled water and made up to 1000 mL.

6.

Potassium antimony tartrate solution. This solution should contain 1 mg of antimony per millilitre, so 0.2728 g of potassium antimony tartrate [(K(SbO) x C₄H₄O₆ x ½ H₂O)] are dissolved in distilled water and made up to 100 mL.

7.

Ascorbic acid solution 0.1 M. This solution must be prepared at the time of use. 1.76 g of ascorbic acid (C₆H₄O₆) are dissolved in water and made up to 100 mL.

8.

Sulphomolybdic solution. This solution must be prepared at the time of use. Mix: 50 mL of O1 solution, 15 mL of O5, 30 mL of O7 and 5 mL of O6.

9.

It is also necessary to prepare a phosphorus stock solution to make the standards. To prepare this solution weight 4.3938 g of KH_2PO_4 (dried at 40 °C), dissolve it in distilled water and make it up to 1000 mL. The phosphorus concentration in this solution is 1000 mg L⁻¹.

The phosphorus determination can be divided into two parts: extraction and measurement by spectrophotometry.

To carry out the phosphorus extraction, two grams of soil are weighed (m) in a 50 mL Greiner tube and 40 mL of the O3 solution are added (VE). This is stirred for 30 minutes and filtered by a 0.45 µm filter. It is important to make a blank without soil, but following the same steps.

For the determination by spectrophotometry an aliquot of the extract is taken (the volume of this aliquot depends on the amount of P the soil has, VS), 5 drops of O4 are added and then O1 is added until the colour changes to yellow. This is diluted with water and 8 mL of O8 are added. In the end, the volume of 50 mL is completed with distilled water. Let the solution stand for 10 min and measure with a spectrophotometer, using a wavelength of 882 nm.

When measuring, it is necessary to employ the same procedure with the standards that are going to be used in the calibration, replacing the soil or blank with a known concentration of phosphorus. Standards of 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 mg L⁻¹ are usually employed.

B) Bray II

Before starting it is necessary to prepare several solutions:

1.

Extraction solution of hydrochloric acid (0.1 N) and ammonium fluoride (0.03 N). Add 1.11 g of NH_4F and 8.28 mL of HCl (37%) to a 1 L volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with distilled water.

2.

This solution is obtained by mixing two solutions. The first one is made dissolving 0.116 g of potassium antimony tartrate in 500 mL of distilled water, and the second results from the dissolution of 4.8 g of ammonium molybdate in 250 mL of distilled water. After mixing of both solutions in a 1 L volumetric flask, 55 mL of concentrated H_2SO_4 are carefully added, and the resultant solution is diluted with distilled water to the mark.

3.

Solution of p-Nitrophenol (0.25 %). Weigh 0.25 g of p-Nitrophenol in a 100 mL volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with ethanol.

4.

Solution of NH_3 (5%). Add 20 mL of NH_3 in a 100 mL volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with distilled water.

5.

Solution of H_2SO_4 (5%). Add 5.1 mL of H_2SO_4 in a 100 mL volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with distilled water.

6.

This solution must be prepared just before the measurement process. Dissolve 1 g of ascorbic acid in 100 mL of solution B2.

7.

It is also necessary to prepare a phosphorus stock solution to make the standards. Weigh 4.3938 g of KH_2PO_4 (dried at 40 °C), dissolve it in distilled water and make it up to 1000 mL. The phosphorus concentration in this solution is 1000 mg L⁻¹.

The procedure is the following:

First, 1 g of sieved dry soil (m) is weighted in a Greiner tube and 10 mL of solution B1 is added (VE).

This suspension is shaken for 30 min and filtered by a 0.45 µm filter. In a 50 mL volumetric flask, an aliquot of the filtered suspension is added (0.1-0.5 mL). The volume used depends on the expected amount of phosphorus (VS).

The following solutions are added to the flask

0.5 mL of boric acid.

2-3 drops of B3 solution.

2-3 drops of B4 solution (until the solution turns yellow).

2-3 drops of B5 solution (until the solution becomes colourless).

5 mL of B6 solution.

Dilute to the mark with water.

It is necessary to employ the same procedure with the blank and the standards that are going to be used in the calibration. Standards, replacing the soil with a known concentration of phosphorus of 0.04, 0.08, 0.12, 0.16 and 0.24 mg L⁻¹ are usually employed.

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6.6. EFFECTIVE CATION EXCHANGE CAPACITY AND CA, MG AND K AVAILABILITY

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Cation exchange capacity (CEC) represents the total number of negative charges of the colloidal soil complex, expressed in cmol per kg of soil.

CEC is an index of soil fertility, since it provides information about the content of nutrients that a soil can retain by ionic exchange, and so, the nutrients that are available for the plants. CEC values of 8-10 cmol kg⁻¹ are usually considered the minimum acceptable for Ap horizons in cultivated soils in order to obtain a satisfactory crop production (Porta et al. 1999).

The method to determine the CEC shown here is the determination of the effective cation exchange capacity and base saturation level using barium chloride solution as exchangeable salt (ISO 2018).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Shaker, rotary shaker (end-over-end) or horizontal
- Tightly locking polyethylene centrifuge tubes (ca. 50 mL)
- 50 or 100 mL polyethylene (PE) flasks
- Funnels
- Filter paper (Whatman No. 42, Schleicher & Schuell 595 1/2, Macherey-Nagel 261 G 1/4, or similar)
- Glass vacuum line (e.g. electric pump)
- Flame atomic absorption spectrometer (FAAS) or ICP-OES

REAGENTS

- Deionised water (electric conductivity $< 0.2 \text{ mS m}^{-1}$ at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)
- Barium chloride (BaCl_2) solution; $c(\text{BaCl}_2) = 0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. Preparation: Dissolve 24.43 g of $\text{BaCl}_2 \times 2 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$ in 1000 mL of water (use volumetric flask)
- BaCl_2 solution; $c(\text{BaCl}_2) = 0.0025 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. Preparation: Dilute 25 mL of solution BaCl_2 solution (0.1 mol L^{-1}) in 1000 mL of water
- Magnesium sulphate solution; $c(\text{MgSO}_4) = 0.020 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. Preparation: Dissolve 4.930 g magnesium sulphate heptahydrate ($\text{MgSO}_4 \times 7 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$) in 1000 mL of water (use volumetric flask). Prepare fresh solution. Magnesium sulphate can lose crystal water during storage. Therefore, wrap the flask in an additional PE bag and store the chemical in a refrigerator. Hydrochloric acid, $c(\text{HCl}) = 12 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ ($\rho = 1.19 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$)
- Magnesium standard solution; $c(\text{Mg}) = 0.0010 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. Preparation: Add 50 mL of MgSO_4 solution (0.020 mol L^{-1}) to a 1000 mL volumetric flask and fill up with water to the mark (see Remarks).
- Acidified lanthanum solution: $c(\text{La}) = 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$. Preparation: Add 15.6 mg lanthanum nitrate hexahydrate [$\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \times 6 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$] to a 500 mL volumetric flask, add 42 mL hydrochloric acid (12 mol L^{-1}), and fill up with water to 500 mL
- Acidified caesium chloride solution: Dissolve 10 g caesium chloride in some water. Add 83 mL of hydrochloric acid (12 mol L^{-1}), and make up to 1000 mL with water
- Sodium and potassium stock solution: $c(\text{Na}) = 400 \text{ mg/L}$, $c(\text{K}) = 1000 \text{ mg/L}$. Dissolve 1.0168 g sodium chloride and 1.9068 g potassium chloride in water. Transfer to 1000 mL volumetric flask and fill up to the mark with water (see Remarks)
- Diluted stock solution: $c(\text{Na}) = 40 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $c(\text{K}) = 100 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$. Pipette 25 mL of solution ($c(\text{Na}) 400 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $c(\text{K}) = 1000 \text{ mg/L}$) in 250 mL volumetric flask and fill up with water to the mark (see Remarks).
- Hydrochloric acid, $c(\text{HCl}) = 4 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. Add 333 mL of commercial HCl 37% ($\rho = 1.19 \text{ g/cm}^3$) to water, to receive a total volume of 1000 mL. Calcium stock solution: $c(\text{Ca}) = 1000 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$. Dissolve 2.497 g calcium carbonate in water. Transfer to 1000 mL volumetric flask and fill up to the mark with water (see Remarks).
- Magnesium stock solution: $c(\text{Mg})$

PROCEDURE

Leaching and measurement of soil bases

1.

Weigh 2.50 g of air-dried soil into a polyethylene centrifuge tube of about 50 mL capacity. Close cap tightly. Note the combined mass of tube and soil (m_1).

2.

Add 30 mL of BaCl_2 solution (0.1 mol L^{-1}) and shake for 1 h. Subsequently centrifuge the tubes at $3,000 \text{ g}$ for 10 min. Note: Balance tubes before centrifugation. Transfer the supernatant to a 100 mL volumetric flask. Repeat this procedure, i.e. the addition of 30 mL of BaCl_2 solution, shaking and centrifugation twice more. Collect all three supernatants in the same volumetric flask. Fill up to the mark with BaCl_2 (0.1 mol L^{-1}). Mix, filter and store the extract I for the determination of the exchangeable concentration of Na, K, Ca and Mg (sum of bases).

3.

Calibration for Na, K, Ca and Mg determination: Prepare solutions with 0 mL, 5 mL, 10 mL, 15 mL, 20 mL and 25 mL of the diluted stock solution ($c(\text{Na}) = 40 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $c(\text{K}) = 100 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) in 50 mL volumetric flasks. Add 10.0 mL of extraction solution BaCl_2 (0.1 mol L^{-1}) and 5.0 mL of acidified caesium chloride solution. Fill up to the mark with water. The resulting concentrations of Na are 0, 4, 8, 12, 16, 20 mg L^{-1} . The resulting concentrations of K are 0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 mg L^{-1} . Prepare solutions with 0, 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 mL of the stock solution ($c(\text{Ca}) = 1000 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $c(\text{Mg}) = 100 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) in 100 mL volumetric flasks. The resulting concentrations of Ca are 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 mg L^{-1} . The resulting concentrations of Mg are 0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5 mg L^{-1} .

4.

Analysis: Fill 2.0 mL of the extract I and of the blank sample, respectively, into reaction tubes. Add 1.0 mL of acidified caesium chloride solution and 7.0 mL of water and mix (see Remarks). Determine bases with FAAS or ICP-EOS, with the instrument set according to the manufacturer's instructions for optimum performance.

Cleansing

1.

Add 30 mL of BaCl_2 solution ($0.0025 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) to the soil pellet and shake overnight. Resulting Ba concentration in the equilibrium solution will be about 0.01 mol L^{-1} . Centrifuge tubes at $3,000 \text{ g}$ for 10 min. Decant the supernatant liquid.

Re-exchange

2.

Weigh the tube with its contents and cap (m_2). Add 30 mL of MgSO_4 solution (0.020 mol L^{-1}) to the soil pellet and shake overnight. Centrifuge tubes at $3,000 \text{ g}$ for 10 min. Decant the supernatant through a filter paper into a new flask and store the extract II for the determination of the concentration of excess Mg.

3.

Prepare blank samples without the addition of soil in parallel and follow the above described procedure completely.

Determination of CEC**1.**

Pipette 0.20 mL from the extracts II of the samples and blank samples into 100 mL volumetric flasks.

2.

Add 0.3 mL of the BaCl₂ solution (0.1 mol L⁻¹) and additional 10 mL of acidified lanthanum solution (10 mg L⁻¹).

3.

Fill up with water to the mark and mix.

4.

For calibration, use dilutions of the Mg standard solution (10 mg L⁻¹). Pipette 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 mL into a series of 100 mL volumetric flasks. Add 10 mL of acidified lanthanum solution (10 mg L⁻¹) to each flask and fill up to the mark with water. Final concentration of the calibration solutions: 0, 0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, and 0.05 mmol L⁻¹, respectively.

5.

Analyse Mg using FAAS at a wavelength of 285.2 nm or using ICP-OES with instrumentation settings following the manufacturer's instructions for optimum performance of the instrument.

REMARKS

If the barium chloride extract has a yellowish-brown colour, this indicates that some organic matter has been dissolved. If this occurs, record it in the test report.

As an alternative to the preparation of standards and calibration series, respectively, certified standard solutions are commercially available; aliquots are diluted as required.

For a complete analysis of exchangeable cations, it might be reasonable to additionally determine NH₄⁺ in fertilised agricultural soil and exchangeable Al and Fe in very acidic soil respectively.

Any other volumes can be used as well, as long as the same concentrations are obtained and the final sample volume is sufficient for analysis with FAAS or ICP-OES.

Dilutions can be prepared much faster by pipetting or using a diluter system.

CALCULATIONS

Correct the concentrations of Mg in the sample solutions for the volume of the liquid retained by the centrifuged soil after being treated with 0,0025 mol L⁻¹ BaCl₂ solution:

$$c_2 = \frac{[c_1 + (30 + m_2 - m_1)]}{30}$$

where

- c_2 is the corrected Mg concentration in the sample [mmol L⁻¹]
- c_1 is the Mg concentration in the sample [mmol L⁻¹]
- m_1 is the mass of the centrifuge tube with air-dried soil [g]
- m_2 is the mass of the centrifuge tube with wet soil [g]
-

Calculate the cation exchange capacity (CEC) of the soil using the following equation:

$$CEC = \frac{(c_{b1} - c_2) 3000}{m}$$

where

- CEC is the cation exchange capacity of the soil [cmolc kg⁻¹]
- c_2 is the corrected Mg concentration in the sample [mmol L⁻¹]
- c_{b1} is the Mg concentration in the blank [mmol L⁻¹]
- m is the mass of the air-dried sample [g]

If the CEC exceeds 40 cmolc kg⁻¹, the determination should be repeated using less soil, adjusting the calculation accordingly

Calculate the soil bases as follows:

$$c (Na, exchangeable) = \frac{2.1749 \times (c_{sample} - c_{blank})}{m [cmol_C Kg^{-1}]}$$

$$c (K, exchangeable) = \frac{1.2788 \times (c_{sample} - c_{blank})}{m [cmol_C Kg^{-1}]}$$

$$c (Ca, exchangeable) = \frac{8.2288 \times (c_{sample} - c_{blank})}{m [cmol_C Kg^{-1}]}$$

$$c (Mg, exchangeable) = \frac{4.9903 \times (c_{sample} - c_{blank})}{m [cmol_C Kg^{-1}]}$$

with the measured concentrations in the diluted sample (c_{sample}) and the diluted blank sample (c_{blank}), respectively, and m as the soil mass in g.

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6.7. AVAILABLE FE, MN, CU AND ZN

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

When assessing a soil and its fertility it is crucial to take into account the concentration of bioavailable essential metals required for plant nutrition (Zhang et al. 2018). Metal bioavailability depends on the characteristics of the organisms present, the properties of the soil and the chemical metal speciation (Ehlken and Kirchner 2002).

Frequently, to obtain the phytoavailable metals from a soil, one-step extraction is done using either ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) or diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA) as extractants (Haq, Bates, and Soon 1980). These two acids are widely used because they form very stable and water-soluble metal complexes. Considering the work of Feng et al. (2005), the extraction with DTPA is more suitable for neutral or alkaline soils. If DTPA is used for extraction of metals from an acidic soil, the buffering capacity of the soil suspension can be exceeded and metals that are not phytoavailable are likely to be released into the solution. EDTA is used for acidic soils since it forms, at low pH, stable chelates with the metals adsorbed to the soil surface (Hammer and Keller 2002). This trend to form stable soluble chelates with EDTA decreases in alkaline soils, in the presence of calcium and magnesium ions (Manouchehri, Besancon, and Bermond 2006). For this reason, when analysing the phytoavailability of metals, both extractants are usually used depending on the soil pH in water.

PROCEDURE

When extracting Fe, Mn, Cu and Zn, it is important to consider the pH of the soil in water: for soils with a pH higher than 6, DTPA is used, and for those with a lower pH EDTA is applied.

A) Soil with pH > 6

First of all, it is necessary to prepare a DTPA solution by weighing the following reagents in a 250 mL beaker:

- DTPA, 1.9667 g
- CaCl₂ x 2H₂O, 0,0735 g
- Triethanolamine: 14 mL (TEA 98%) or 15.6 mL (TEA 85%).

This solution is shaken by a magnetic stirrer, and distilled water is added until it reaches a volume of 900 mL. Once this is done, the pH is measured and adjusted to 7.3 by adding 37% HCl. Then distilled water is added up to 1 L.

Once the solution has been prepared, 2 grams of soil (sieved by 2 mm) are weighed in a Greiner tube and 4 mL of the DTPA solution are added (the soil:extractant ratio is 1:2). The tubes are shaken for 2 hours, centrifuged during 5 minutes at 1500 g and the supernatant filtered using a 0.45 µm filter. The filtrate is analysed by an atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

B) Soil with pH < 6

In this case, the process is similar but the extractant, and the ratio are different. First, it is necessary to prepare the EDTA solution, for which the following reagents must be weighed in a 250 mL beaker:

- EDTA, 1,8612 g.
- Ammonium acetate, 77 g.

This solution is shaken by a magnetic stirrer and distilled water is added until it has a volume of 900 mL. Once this is done, the pH is measured and adjusted to 4.65 by adding 37% HCl. Then distilled water is added up to 1 L.

Once the solution has been prepared, 2 grams of soil (sieved with a 2 mm mesh sieve) are weighed in a Greiner tube and 10 mL of the EDTA solution are added (the soil:extractant ratio is 1:5). The tubes are shaken for 1 hour, centrifuged for 5 minutes at 1500 g and the supernatant filtered using a 0.45 µm filter. The filtrate is analysed by an atomic absorption spectrophotometer or using an ICP-MS.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid, DTPA, (C₁₄H₂₃N₃O₁₀)
- Calcium chloride, CaCl₂ x 2H₂O
- Triethanolamine, TEA, (C₆H₁₅NO₃)
- Hydrochloric Acid, HCl (37%)
- Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid, EDTA (C₁₀H₁₆N₂O₈)
- Ammonium acetate (C₁₀H₁₆N₂O₈)
- Magnetic stirrer
- Shaker
- Greiner tubes (15 mL)
- Dispenser
- Beakers
- Analytical balance (0.0001 g)
- 2 mm mesh sieve
- Centrifuge
- 0.45 µm Filters
- Atomic absorption spectrophotometer
- Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS)

CALCULATIONS

The results obtained from the atomic absorption spectrophotometer are in mg mL⁻¹ and should be converted into mg g⁻¹ of dry soil.

To do this, if we start from the concentration value that we obtain from the measurement of each metal, C_M (mg mL⁻¹), and assume that the concentration in the filtrate is homogeneous, for DTPA:

$$C_{DS} = \frac{4 C_M}{W_{DS}}$$

Where:

- C_{DS} is the metal concentration by gram of dry soil (mg of metal / g of dry soil).
- C_M is the measured concentration in the spectrometer (in mg mL⁻¹)
- W_{DS} is the exact amount of soil weighted (in g).

And for EDTA:

$$C_{DS} = \frac{10 C_M}{W_{DS}}$$

These formulas will be applied to each measured metal (Fe, Mn, Cu and Zn).

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6.8. AVAILABLE BORON

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Boron is one of the 16 essential nutrients for plants, and needs to be available according to the growth needs of the crop (Motsara and Roy, 2008). Its presence in the soil depends to a large extent on the texture, pH and irrigation: the deficiency of this element is usually caused by irrigation or heavy rain in acid soils with a light texture.

Comparing the data for all essential micronutrients, boron is one of the most studied since it is the one that causes deficiencies more frequently (Keren and Bingham, 1958). The lack of this element produces a series of effects in crops such as shortening of the internodes or stopping terminal growth. Symptoms of a boron deficiency in crops may take time to appear, as in the case of phosphorus deficiency.

When determining available boron, there are various extractants (Table 6.8.1.), but water extraction is usually used (Berger and Truog, 1939): soil boron that can be dissolved in water is considered available boron. It is usually measured by atomic emission spectrometry or by a colorimetric method using a reagent such as Azometin-H.

Table 6.8.1. Methods employed to extract boron from a soil (Adapted from Nable et al., 1997)

Method	Reference
Hot water	Berger and Truog (1939)
CaCl ₂	Aitken et al. (1987)
NH ₄ oxalate (pH 3.75)	De Endredy (1963)
NH ₄ / DTPA	Handreck (1990)

PROCEDURE

Extraction:

- 5 g of dry soil are weighed in a beaker (m1).
- 10 mL of distilled water are added.
- 0.5 g of activated charcoal are added.
- The suspension is boiled for 5 min and filtered through No. 42 filter paper.

Boron determination is made by using an atomic absorption spectrometer (AAS), using a wavelength of 249.7 nm, an acetylene / nitrous oxide flame and boron standards with concentrations between 1 and 10 µg mL⁻¹. Standards are prepared from Na₂B₄O₇·10H₂O. At the end, a boron concentration is obtained in µg mL⁻¹ (CBM).

PROCEDURE

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EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Balance
- Spatula
- Distilled water
- Activated charcoal
- Heating plate
- No. 42 filter paper
- Atomic absorption spectrometer (AAS)
- Na₂B₄O₇·10H₂O

CALCULATIONS

The boron concentration obtained by ASA is in µg mL⁻¹ and it is necessary to convert it to µg of B per g of dry soil. Since we added 10 mL of water to the soil to extract the boron:

$$C_B = \frac{10C_{BM}}{m_1}$$

Where:

CB is the boron concentration in µg per g of dry soil.

CBM is the boron concentration measured through AAS in µg mL⁻¹

And, m₁ is the mass of dry soil.

6.9. TOTAL PESTICIDES

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Currently, at European level, there are 479 active substances that can be used as pesticides, and other 43 are pending approval (European Commission 2009). These pesticides are used to protect crops against possible pests and have contributed to increase agricultural productivity during the last decades (Silva et al. 2019). However, pesticides can reach the ground during the application or by rain (Pérez-Rodríguez et al. 2017), and, given their effects on living organisms, they have become a major threat to the soil, to biodiversity, and to food safety (Stolte, Tesfai, and Keizer 2016). Therefore, when examining the biodiversity of a soil, it is also essential to determine the pesticides present.

To measure pesticides we use the QUECHERS method (Quick, Easy, Cheap, Effective, Rugged, and Safe) adapted to measure soil samples (Mol et al. 2008; Silva et al. 2019). This method is based on the pesticide extraction with one or several solvents, the cleaning of the sample to avoid interferences and the determination of pesticides by LC-MS/MS and GC-HRMS.

PROCEDURE

EXTRACTION

1. Weigh 5 g of the soil sample in a 50 mL Greiner tube.
2. Add 50 μL of a solution of $^{13}\text{C}_3$ -Caffeine with a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$.
3. Add 5 mL of Millipore Water and 10 mL ACN with 1% HAc.
4. Shake mechanically for 1 hour.

CLEANING THE SOLUTION

1. Add 1 g of Sodium Acetate (NaHAc) and 4 g of Magnesium Sulphate (MgSO_4)
2. Stir by vortex and centrifuge for 5 min at 2500 g.
3. Collect supernatant.

The supernatant is analysed by two methods: LC-MS / MS and GC-HRMS.

LC-MS / MS

1. Add 125 μ L of the supernatant obtained in the previous steps to an LC vial.
2. Add 250 μ L of Millipore Water and 125 μ L ACN with 1% HAc.
3. Filter using a PTFE filter.
4. Measure using LC-MS / MS.

GC-HRMS there is an extra cleaning step

1. Add 1500 μ L of supernatant to an Eppendorf vial.
2. Add 38 mg of PSA, 38 mg of C18 and 250 mg MgSO₄.
3. Add 38 μ L of PCB-198 of a solution with a concentration of 1 μ g mL⁻¹.
4. Shake the sample by vortex and centrifuge for 15 min at 13000 g.

- 5. Take a 250 μL aliquot in a GC vial.
- 6. Measure using GC-HRMS.

Figure 6.9.1. Scheme of the procedure followed to determine the concentration of pesticides in soils. This procedure is used to extract, clean and measure the 76 pesticides included in Table 3.9.1. (Adapted from Fuentes et al. 2019)

Analytical determinations by LC-MS / MS and GC-HRMS are made in duplicate. As for the calibrations, they are carried out with multi-pesticide standards that also included the internal standard. The standards are measured before and after measuring the samples (Reynolds et al. 2013). The pesticides measured are summarized in Table 6.9.1., taken from the work of Silva et al. (2019).

Table 6.9.1. Summary of the compounds to be measured in the soil samples with the procedure explained in Figure 6.9.1. The table also includes the type of pesticide and the chemical class.

Compound	Type	Chemical class
Abamectin	Insecticide	Botanical
Aldrin	Insecticide	Organochlorine
Atrazine	Herbicide	Triazine
Atrazine-deisopropyl	Metabolite of simazine and atrazine	Unclassified
Atrazine-desethyl	Metabolite of atrazine	Triazine
Azoxystrobin	Fungicide	Strobilurin
Boscalid	Fungicide	Carboxamide
Carbaryl	Insecticide	Carbamate
Carbofuran	Insecticide; metabolite of furathiocarb, carbosulfan and benfuracarb	Carbamate
Carbofuran, 3-hydroxy	Metabolite of carbofuran, carbosulfan and benfuracarb	Unclassified
Carbofuran, -keto	Metabolite of carbofuran and benfuracarb	Unclassified
Chlordane alpha	Insecticide	Organochlorine
Chlordane gamma	Insecticide	Organochlorine
Chlordecone	Insecticide; metabolite of mirex and kelevan	Organochlorine
Chlorfenvinphos	Insecticide	Organophosphate
Chlorpyrifos	Insecticide	Organophosphate
Chlorpyrifos-methyl	Insecticide	Organophosphate
Cymoxanil	Fungicide	Cyanoacetamide oxime
Cyproconazole	Fungicide	Triazole
Cyprodinil	Fungicide	Anilinopyrimidine
DDD op	Insecticide; metabolite of DDT	Organochlorine
DDD pp	Insecticide; metabolite of DDT	Organochlorine
DDE op	Metabolite of DDT	
DDE pp	Metabolite of DDT	Organochlorine
DDT op	Insecticide	Organochlorine
DDT pp	Insecticide	Organochlorine
Diazinon	Insecticide	Organophosphate
Dieldrin	Insecticide, metabolite of aldrin	Organochlorine
Difenoconazole	Fungicide	Triazole
Dimethomorph	Fungicide	Morpholine
Diuron	Herbicide	Phenylamide
Endosulfan alpha	Insecticide	Organochlorine
Endosulfan beta	Insecticide	Organochlorine
Endosulfan sulphate	Metabolite endosulfan, endosulfan alpha and endosulfan beta	Unclassified
Endrin	Insecticide	Organochlorine
Epoconazole	Fungicide	Triazole
Ethion	Insecticide, metabolite of chlormephos	Organophosphate
Fenpropimorph	Fungicide	Morpholine
Fluometuron	Herbicide	Phenylurea
Fluroxypyr	Herbicide	Pyridine compound

Folpet	Fungicide	Phthalimide
Heptachlor	Insecticide	Organochlorine
Heptachlor epoxide	Metabolite of heptachlor	Unclassified
Hexachlorobenzene	Fungicide, metabolite of quintozene	Organochlorine
Hexachlorocyclohexane, alpha	Insecticide, metabolite of HCH gamma	Organochlorine
Hexachlorocyclohexane, beta	Metabolite of HCH gamma	Unclassified
Hexachlorocyclohexane, gamma	Insecticide	Organochlorine
Imazalil	Fungicide	Imidazole
Imidacloprid	Insecticide	Neonicotinoid
Isoproturon	Herbicide	Urea
Linuron	Herbicide	Urea
Malathion	Insecticide	Organophosphate
Metalaxyl	Fungicide	Phenylamide
Metamitron	Herbicide	Triazinone
Myclobutanil	Fungicide	Triazole
Parathion	Insecticide	Organophosphate
Parathion-methyl	Insecticide	Organophosphate
Penconazole	Fungicide	Triazole
Pentachlorobenzene	Metabolite of quintozene	Unclassified
Phthalimide	Metabolite of folpet	Unclassified
Pinoxaden	Herbicide	Unclassified
Pirimiphos-methyl	Insecticide	Organophosphate
Prochloraz	Fungicide	Imidazole
Procymidone	Fungicide	Dicarboximide
Propiconazole	Fungicide	Triazole
Prothioconazole	Fungicide	Triazolinthione
Pyraclostrobin	Fungicide	Strobilurin
Quinoxifen	Fungicide	Quinoline
Simazine	Herbicide	Triazine
Tebuconazole	Fungicide	Triazole
Terbuthylazine	Herbicide	Triazine
Terbuthylazine-desethyl	Metabolite of terbuthylazine	Unclassified
Triadimenol	Fungicide	Triazole
Trifloxystrobin	Fungicide	Strobilurin
Simazine	Herbicide	Triazine
Tebuconazole	Fungicide	Triazole
Terbuthylazine	Herbicide	Triazine
Terbuthylazine-desethyl	Metabolite of terbuthylazine	Unclassified
Triadimenol	Fungicide	Triazole
Trifloxystrobin	Fungicide	Strobilurin

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Analytical balance (0.0001 g)
- Micropipettes
- Greiner tubes of 50 mL
- Shaker
- Distilled water
- Vortex
- Centrifuge
- LC vials
- PTFE Filters
- Liquid Chromatograph-Mass Spectrometer (LC-MS/MS)
- Eppendorf vials
- GC vials
- High-Resolution Gas Chromatograph-Mass Spectrometer (GC-HRMS)

REAGENTS

- ¹³C₃-labeled caffeine
- PCB-198 (C₁₂H₂Cl₈)
- C18 (40 μm of Particle Size, Prep LC)
- Magnesium sulphate (MgSO₄; ≥99.8%)
- Acetic acid (CH₃COOH; ≥99.8%) (HAc)
- Sodium acetate (CH₃COONa; 99%)
- Acetonitrile (C₂H₃N; 99.95% LC grade) (ACN).
- Primary secondary amine sorbent (PSA)

CALCULATIONS

With the internal standards, a response factor can be calculated in order to determine the efficiency of the extraction procedure. The response factor is the concentration of the internal standard in the sample divided by the initial concentration of the standard. By using this response factor, it is possible to correct the concentration of pesticides measured.

The results obtained from the LC-MS / MS and GC-HRMS are in ng mL⁻¹ and should be converted into ng g⁻¹ of dry soil.

REMARKS

Given the importance of glyphosate and AMPA, these two substances are usually extracted by using more specific methods (Bento et al. 2016), that will be explained in detail in the following section.

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6.10. GLYPHOSATE AND AMPA

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Glyphosate (N-phosphonomethylglycine, $C_3H_8NO_5$) is a broad-spectrum herbicide with a higher solubility in water than in organic solvents. It is one of the most widely used herbicides since it was commercialized in the 1970s (Ghanem et al. 2007). It does not bio-accumulate, is poorly absorbed orally or through the skin, but can cause eye and skin irritation in humans (Farmer 2010). It is a systemic herbicidal substance that is used before planting the crop (before or after harvest), and is used to control the growth of annual or perennial weeds. This substance is also used to remove plants from parks and railway lines or roads (Silva et al. 2018). In Europe, it is mainly used in cereals, vineyards and oilseeds, crops that have not been genetically modified to tolerate glyphosate. In the USA and elsewhere, it is also applied to glyphosate resistant genetically engineered crops such as corn and cotton.

Glyphosate can be degraded by soil microbes into aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA), its main metabolite. The massive use of glyphosate can lead to high levels of AMPA in both soil and water (Grandcoin, Piel, and Baurès 2017). Its presence is frequent in the superficial part of agricultural soils, where it degrades slowly, but it can reach surface water currents adsorbed to the surface of some particles, and, rarely, it reaches groundwater. In vitro

experiments performed with this element have confirmed its toxicity for human cells (Kwiatkowska, Huras, and Bukowska 2014).

Glyphosate and AMPA have a great presence in soils (Figure 6.10.1.). In studies carried out in European soils, these two substances were found at levels higher than those predicted by EFSA (Silva et al. 2019), so they are not usually analysed with the rest of pesticides and a specific extraction is made for these compounds. For this reason, we have not included them in the previous section (6.9. Total Pesticides).

Glyphosate is a highly polar and amphoteric substance, which presents some analytical challenges. Normally, both glyphosate and its metabolite AMPA are measured through some type of derivatization. Pre-column derivatization using 9-fluorenylmethoxycarbonyl chloride (FMOCl) is one of the most commonly used methods (Ghanem et al. 2007) as it facilitates chromatographic separation and subsequent analysis by mass spectroscopy or fluorimetry. FMOCl is able to react with the amino groups of both AMPA and glyphosate (Garba et al. 2018). The derivatization occurs under alkaline conditions, in which the amino group hydrogen (from glyphosate and AMPA) is replaced by an aromatic FMOCl ring, and FMOCl-Glyphosate, FMOCl-AMPA and hydrochloric acid are produced (Figure 6.10.2.).

Figure 6.10.1. Amount of pesticides (in mg per kg of soil) found in 317 samples analysed throughout Europe (from Silva et al. 2019).

Figure 6.10.2. Derivatization reaction that occurs between FMOCl and Glyphosate (GLY) and AMPA under alkaline conditions (from Garba et al. 2018).

PROCEDURE

The process includes the extraction of glyphosate and AMPA, their derivatization to make and determination by LC-MS/MS.

- 5.** Weigh 2 g of the air-dried soil sample in a 50 mL Greiner tube.
- 6.** Add 10 mL of a solution of potassium hydroxide 0.6 M (Extractant agent).
- 7.** Shake for 60 min.
- 8.** Centrifuge 30 min at 2500 g
- 9.** Take an aliquot of 1 mL in Greiner tube of 15 mL.
- 10.** Add 80 μ L of HCl 6 M. In this step a pH of 9 (approximately) is reached.
- 11.** Add 40 μ L of a solution that includes the labelled internal standards of glyphosate and AMPA (5 μ g mL⁻¹).

12. Add 0.5 mL of borate buffer (5 %).
13. Add 0.5 mL of 9 fluorenylmethoxycarbonyl chloride 6.5 mM (Derivatization agent).
14. Vortex for 10-15 seconds.
15. Let the reaction happens for 30 min.
16. Add 50 μ L of formic acid (98-100%) to stop the reaction.
17. Filtrate by 0.45 μ m (using PTFE filters).
18. Transfer 0.5 mL to an LC vial and measure by LC-MS/MS.

It is also necessary to prepare standards of glyphosate and AMPA: 0.005, 0.01, 0.02, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 1 and 2 μ g mL⁻¹. Those have to be injected in the beginning and at the end of the sample measurement. It is also important to inject one or two standards in the middle of the samples.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Analytical balance (0.0001 g)
- Micropipettes
- 50 mL Greiner tubes of 50 mL
- 15 mL Greiner tubes of 15 mL
- Shaker
- Distilled water
- Vortex
- Centrifuge
- LC vials
- PTFE Filters
- Liquid Chromatograph-Mass Spectrometer (LC-MS/MS)

REAGENTS

- Glyphosate Standard (98%)
- AMPA Standard (98%)
- Isotope labelled internal standard of glyphosate (1, 2-¹³C ¹⁵N; 100 µg mL⁻¹)
- Isotope labelled internal standard of AMPA (¹³C, ¹⁵N; 100 µg mL⁻¹).
- Potassium hydroxide (KOH; 85%)
- Hydrochloric acid (HCl; 37%)
- Sodium tetraborate decahydrate (Na₂B₄O₇·10H₂O; 99.5%)
- 9 fluorenylmethoxycarbonyl chloride (Fmoc-Cl; ≥99.0%)
- Formic acid (CH₂O₂; 98–100%)

CALCULATIONS

With the internal standards, a response factor can be calculated in order to determine the efficiency of the extraction procedure. The response factor is the concentration of the internal standard in the sample divided by the initial concentration of the standard. By using this response factor, it is possible to correct the concentration of pesticides measured.

The results obtained from the LC-MS / MS and GC-HRMS are in ng mL⁻¹ and should be converted in ng g⁻¹ of dry soil.

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7. SOIL STRUCTURE, WATER AVAILABILITY AND SOIL CARBON SEQUESTRATION

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Ensuring soil quality is essential to achieve high crop growth and production. Most crops are based on soil, and soil characteristics are going to directly or indirectly affect plant behaviour. Soil has to be well structured so that there is proper aeration, water retention, water infiltration, fauna can freely move and roots can grow and spread. For this, soil management in agricultural systems need to foster the creation of soil aggregates, which are clusters of soil particles that join each other, leaving spaces around, the pores, for retention and exchange of air and water. Particle size distribution, this is to say, the proportion of clay, silt, sand, gravels and coarse fragments is going to highly condition the physical structure of the soil, facilitating or hindering the movement of air, water and biota. However, organic matter content can in all cases contribute to enhance soil aggregation, and together with suitable management practices, can be the perfect allies to improve soil structure and promote the growth of soil organisms and plants. Thus, to foster high crop yield, a proper soil structure must be maintained. In this line, a suitable soil aggregation and organic matter content can also contribute to increase water retention in soil, which directly can promote higher plant growth. Soil biota can contribute to soil aggregation by release of organic compounds, mix organic and inorganic particles, such as earthworms, or directly bind soil particles by their physical structure such as fungal hyphae.

Apart from contributing to soil structure and fertility, soil organic matter accumulation is a suitable strategy for climate change mitigation, since CO₂ is sequestered in soil as stable soil organic carbon. In the last years, there are many attempts to promote agricultural practices that enhance carbon sequestration in soil, such as the 4per1000 initiative (<https://www.4p1000.org/>), as a global strategy to combat climate change. Knowledge about soil micro and macro-organisms functioning, carbon sequestration and plant growth and crop production is still scarce to suggest those practices that stimulate soil organisms that can contribute to both crop production and carbon sequestration. As a consequence, we have defined an experimental design and methodology in SoildiverAgro WP5 to try to partially fill these gaps.

Thus, in the following chapters we propose different methods that will be applied in SoildiverAgro to assess how management practices can contribute to improve soil structure, retain soil water and contribute to carbon sequestration as a strategy to mitigate climate change. All these data will be interrelated with soil macro and microorganisms communities to identify biological indicators that could contribute to this aim.

7.1. SOIL BULK DENSITY

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Soil bulk density is defined as soil mass per unit of volume. This volume is the sample volume in the field. Soil bulk density is interesting from the point of view of soil management, since it informs about the compaction of each horizon, and it allows the identification of difficulties for the emergency, rooting and air and water circulation. Soil bulk density is directly related to the structure and therefore it depends on the same control factors.

Soil bulk density is often determined separately for the different soil horizons due to the relative ease by which it can be determined. However, it should be noted that soil bulk density has important limitations as a soil quality indicator, since it does not provide information about the size of the spaces, about the connection between them, or about the forces that have led to a specific soil structure. These aspects are of importance when aiming to predict the movement of soil water and aggregate stability. Soils with the same values of bulk densities may have different responses to external forces. To obtain information about this, specific studies on porosity must be used (Porta et al. 1999).

The method presented here is the so-called cylinder method (Campbell and Hensall 1991). A cylinder of known volume with thin and rigid walls and with a bevelled edge towards the outside, is used. The method is to take a sample by inserting the cylinder into the horizon to be studied.

PROCEDURE

1.

Follow the indications for soil sampling included in section “2.1. Sampling for soil bulk density”

2.

In the laboratory, the contents of the cylinder or plastic bags are transferred into a beaker of known weight.

3.

Put the glass in the oven for at least 24 hours at 105 °C until constant weight.

4.

Weigh the beaker and dry soil on the analytical balance (this measure corresponds to the true bulk density), noting the exact weight.

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EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Metal cylinder of known volume (100-500 cm³)
- Bulk Density Sampler Cup and Cap
- Hammer
- Spatula
- Analytical balance (0.01 g)
- Oven

CALCULATIONS

$$\rho_b = \frac{(m_2 - m_1)}{V}$$

- ρ_b is the bulk density of the soil [g m⁻³]
- m_1 is the weight of the metal ring [g]
- m_2 is the weight of the metal ring + soil after drying [g]
- V is the volume of the metal ring [cm³]

REMARKS

In the case of soils with gravels and boulders (Regosols, Leptosols, Technosols), coarse constituents hinder sampling and increase measurement error.

In the case of soils with swelling clay minerals, correction calculation is needed related to the field volume/dry volume ratio.

7.2. COARSE FRAGMENTS DETERMINATION

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Particle size analysis of soils containing coarse fragments (particles > 2 mm) requires at least 400 g of soil material. Coarse fragments from soil have the same effect as other mulching materials in protecting the soil against the impact of raindrops (Poesen et al. 1990).

This method is based on the determination of the percentage of rock fragments and gravels in a soil through sieving (Taubner et al. 2009).

PROCEDURE

- Weight the whole soil sample (record precise weight). Sample has to be previously air-dried. If aggregates are present, you have to break aggregates by crushing them with a hammer. It is important to break all aggregates in order not to consider them as coarse fragments.
- Sieve the sample at < 2 mm (making sure that aggregates < 2mm are broken).
- Weight the sieve non-passing fraction (record precise weight).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Sieve (mesh size 2 mm).
- Balance with at least two decimals.
- Hammer

CALCULATIONS

Calculate the percentage of coarse fragments by dividing the weight retained on sieve by the original sample mass.

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7.3. PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION AND TEXTURE

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

The particle size distribution (PSD) of a soil is a characteristic that influences the soil dry bulk density, the amount of water and nutrients that the soil is able to retain and the soil structure (Mukhopadhyay and Maiti 2018). The PSD is one of the features most used by scientists to describe the distribution in the soil of mineral particles smaller than 2 mm on the basis of relative amount of clay (<0.002 mm), silt (0.05-0.002 mm) and sand (2-0.05 mm) presented by that soil (S. Mukhopadhyay et al. 2019). From PSD, soil texture can be defined (Figure 7.3.1).

Figure 7.3.1. USDA textural classification triangle (Adapted from Groenendyk et al. 2015)

The USDA system shown in Figure 7.3.1 is one of the most used for soil texture classification. The percentage of material belonging to each group (sands, silts and clays) is represented on each side of the triangle. The texture is determined by the intersection between the three lines that cut the sides of the triangle at the point corresponding to the value of each element represented. Soil texture has a major influence on soil water flow and retention. As the amounts of clays and silts increase, the water flow through the soil is reduced, improving the soil water retention capacity.

There are several methods available for determining PSD, but the idea is always to separate the different fractions (by size) and determine their quantity in each fraction. This can be achieved by sieving, by sedimentation of a soil suspension, by differences in the density of a suspension, or by laser diffraction methods (Taubner, Roth, and Tippkötter 2009). One of the most used methods for the PSD determination is the pipette method: the largest fractions (sands) are separated by sieving, using sieve meshes of 0.2 mm (for coarse sand) and 0.05 mm (for fine sand); and the finest ones (silt and clays) are determined according to their sedimentation rate calculated by Stokes law (Carter and Gregorich 2008).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Sieves (0.2 and 0.05 mm)
- Bottles
- Shaker
- Sodium hexametaphosphate, (NaPO₃)₆
- Sodium carbonate, Na₂CO₃
- Distilled water
- Hydroxide peroxide, H₂O₂
- Test tubes (1 L)
- Crucibles
- Robinson pipette
- Hand shaker
- Chronometer
- Oven (muffle)

REMARKS

It is common to destroy the carbonates in the sample using a pre-treatment with HCl. However, this acid can affect the size and structure of some soil components.

PROCEDURE

Before starting the PSD characterization, it is necessary to prepare a solution of sodium hexametaphosphate and sodium carbonate in water that will be used as dispersant. For this aim, 35.70 g of $(\text{NaPO}_3)_6$, and 7.94 g of Na_2CO_3 are diluted in one litre of distilled water, to have a solution 0.06 M of $(\text{NaPO}_3)_6$ and 0.08 M of Na_2CO_3 .

For the determination of the particle size distribution by the pipette method, 20 g of dry soil (sieved by 2 mm) are weighed. It is necessary to understand that the distribution of particle size is contributed only to the mineral material, so a previous step is necessary to eliminate the organic matter. This part can be removed from the sample by dry combustion (employing a muffle) or wet combustion (by adding H_2O_2 , carefully until the reaction is stopped).

Once the mineral part is separated, a volume of 100 mL of distilled water and 50 mL of the solution of sodium hexametaphosphate and sodium carbonate are added. This suspension is shaken for 2 hours in order to disperse aggregates.

After that step, the suspension is wet sieved using two mesh sizes, 0.2 and 0.05 mm, to separate the coarse and fine sands respectively. It is necessary to wash these sands to be sure that all materials of a smaller size end up in the effluent. It is very important to manage the use of water properly so that less than a litre is used. The sand fractions are taken to a previously tared crucible, where they are dried in an oven at 105°C until constant weight.

The effluent, which only contains silts and clays, is transferred to a one-litre test tube. With the help of a manual shaker, the content of the test tube is agitated. Samples of 20 mL are taken after 0, 4.8 minutes and 8 hours in a previously tared crucible, and dried in an oven at 105°C until constant weight. In each case, it is necessary to adjust the position of the Robinson pipette to always take the samples at ten centimetres below the surface.

In the end, all the dried samples in the crucibles are weighed and the calculations are performed to determine the proportion of each particle size in the soil.

CALCULATIONS

In the case of sands, the calculation is as follows:

$$CSa = CSa_w - CSa_c$$

$$FSa = FSa_w - FSa_c$$

Where:

- CSa is the weight of the coarse sand.
- CSaw is the weight of the coarse sand plus the crucible.
- CSac is the weight of the crucible used to dry the coarse sand.
- FSa is the weight of the fine sand.
- FSaw is the weight of the fine sand plus the crucible.
- FSac is the weight of the crucible used to dry the fine sand.

The following formulas were used for coarse silt, fine silt and clays:

$$CSi = \frac{(CSi_w - CSi_c)}{V_s} \cdot V_1$$

$$FSi = \frac{(FSi_w - FSi_c)}{V_s} \cdot (V_1 - V_s)$$

$$CL = \frac{(CL_w - CL_c)}{V_s} \cdot (V_1 - 2V_s)$$

Where:

- CSi is the weight of the coarse silt.
- CSiw is the weight of the coarse silt plus the crucible.
- CSic is the weight of the crucible used to dry the coarse silt.
- FSi is the weight of the fine silt.
- FSiw is the weight of the fine silt plus the crucible.
- FSic is the weight of the crucible used to dry the fine silt.
- CL is the weight of the clay.
- CLw is the weight of the clay plus the crucible.
- CLc is the weight of the crucible used to dry the clay.
- Vs is the volume of sample taken with the Robinson pipette.
- V1 is the volume of the test tube.

The results of this type of analysis are usually expressed as percentages with regard to the total sample. Moreover, the two types of sand and silts are added together to determine the type of texture in the USDA triangle (Figure 7.3.1.). Thus:

$$\%Sa = \frac{(CSa + FSa)}{CSa + FSa + CSi + FSi + CL} \cdot 100$$

$$\%Si = \frac{(CSi + FSi)}{CSa + FSa + CSi + FSi + CL} \cdot 100$$

$$\%CL = \frac{(CL)}{CSa + FSa + CSi + FSi + CL} \cdot 100$$

Where:

- %Sa is the percentage of sand in the sample.
- %Si is the percentage of silt in the sample.
- %CL is the percentage of clay in the sample.

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7.4. AGGREGATE STABILITY AND SIZE DISTRIBUTION

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Individual soil particles are not randomly arranged, but they form clods and lumps joined by colloidal material, which have a certain internal organization and a characteristic external shape, called aggregates. The nature and distribution of aggregate size and pore space is called soil structure and strongly affects physicochemical and biological properties of soil. The soil structure is related to the mutual arrangement of the individual soil particles, the stability of the aggregate state and the pore size. Aggregate stability refers to their ability to maintain their shape when they are subjected to artificially induced forces, in particular those derived from wetting or the impact of raindrops (Díaz et al. 1994). This method analyses the aggregate stability and size distribution based on can be determined using a wet sieving method of air-dried soil (Elliot 1986).

PROCEDURE

1.

Take 80 g subsample from air-dried soil (weigh and record precise weight).

2.

Fill up white basin with water until water level is approximately 1 cm above 2000 μm sieve-mesh.

3.

Spray soil evenly out on sieve and wait for 5 minutes.

4.

After 5 minutes, sieve the soil for two minutes by moving the sieve up and down (approx. 3 cm amplitude) 50 times with a slight angle to ensure that water and small particles pass through the mesh.

5.

Let the sieve stand for 30s in order to let small particles settle down.

6.

Aspirate off the floating litter into the flask attached to the vacuum line.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- 8 mm sieve
- Two white basins with diameter of 50 cm and height of 8 cm
- 2000 μm , 250 μm , 53 μm sieves with diameter of 30 cm
- Vacuum pump connected to a flask
- Aluminium pans for drying soil samples
- Air-forced drying oven (60°C)
- Spatula and brush
- Rinsing bottle
- Analytical balance (0.01 g)

CALCULATIONS

The results are expressed as a percentage showing the proportions of the different aggregate size classes.

7.

Take the sieve out of the water and rinse off the sides plus the bottom of the sieve with water in order to have all particles in suspension.

8.

Backwash > 2000 μm aggregates (i.e. large macroaggregates) into a pre-weighed small drying pan with sufficient water.

9.

Put the drying pan with the large macroaggregates into the 60°C forced air oven (overnight).

10.

Pour the water and particles that went through the 2000 μm sieve remaining in the white basin onto a 250 μm sieve, which is held above the second white basin, and repeat the sieving procedure (in 2 minutes the sieve is moved up and down (approx. 3 cm amplitude) 50 times with a slight angle to ensure that water and small particles pass through the mesh).

11.

Take the sieve out of the water and rinse off the sides plus the bottom of the sieve with water in order to have all particles in suspension.

12.

Backwash 250-2000 μm aggregates (i.e. small macroaggregates) into a pre-weighed small drying pan.

13.

Put the drying pan with the small macroaggregates into the 60°C forced air oven (overnight).

14.

Pour the water and particles that went through the 250 μm sieve remaining in the white basin onto a 53 μm sieve, which is held above a white basin, and repeat the sieving procedure (in 2 minutes move the sieve up and down (approx. 3 cm amplitude) 50 times with a slight angle to ensure that water and small particles pass through the mesh).

15.

Take the sieve out of the water and rinse off the sides plus the bottom of the sieve with water in order to have all particles in suspension.

16.

Backwash 53–250 μm aggregates (i.e. microaggregates) into a pre-weighed small drying pan.

17.

Put the small drying pan with microaggregates into the 105°C forced air oven (overnight).

18.

Pour the water + < 53 μm particles (i.e. silt + clay) remaining in the white basin into a pre-weighed large drying pan.

19.

Put the large drying pan with silt + clay particles into the 105°C forced air oven (overnight).

20.

The following day weigh all fractions.

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An aerial photograph of a flooded agricultural field at sunset. The water is a deep orange-brown color, reflecting the sky. The field is divided into rows of crops, and the water has inundated the spaces between them. In the background, there are trees and a utility tower under a hazy, orange sky.

7.5. WATER HOLDING CAPACITY

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Water holding capacity (WHC) is the ability of a soil to store water available for the plants (Fernández de Villarán San Juan et al. 2006), and is usually calculated as the difference between field capacity and wilting point (Valdivia-Cea et al. 2017).

In structured soil, this capacity is highly conditioned by the structure of the soil, that is, by the spatial distribution of the pores and the soil matrix. For example, macropores can store a large amount of water when the soil is saturated, but a big proportion is released with a slight suction (Fernández de Villarán San Juan et al. 2006). The amount of organic matter and texture also have a great influence on WHC. Silts and clays have physicochemical properties that are more favorable to water retention, such as a higher specific surface area. Organic matter content is also a factor that conditions WHC, and have a much more visible effect in sandy soils (Rawls et al. 2003). Moreover, it is possible to calculate the WHC using parameters related to the texture and the amount of organic matter in the soil (Blaschek et al. 2019; Fernández de Villarán San Juan et al. 2006).

PROCEDURE

The procedure to calculate the WHC (of unstructured soil) is as follows:

- A 50 µm nylon mesh is placed on the bottom of a cylindrical metal casing of 5 x 5 cm.
- The casing is filled with oven-dried (105 °C) 2 mm sieved soil and weighed (Mass of dry soil) before being placed on a tray with a water layer.
- The soil is allowed to saturate from the bottom (8 – 14 hours).
- Then, the soil is removed from the tray and allowed to drain for some minutes (until the drainage stops) (Ezenwaji, Ezenwaji, and Okoye 2015). At this point, the soil is weighed once more to obtain the Mass of drained soil.

The procedure for calculating WHC in structured soil is the same. The only difference is that the sample is taken directly using the metal casing, following the procedure described in 2.1. Sampling for soil bulk density.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Balance.
- Distilled water.
- Filter paper.
- Nylon mesh.
- Metal casing.
- Pan.
- Spatula.

CALCULATIONS

The WHC percentage is calculated with the following formula:

$$\% \text{ WHC} = \left(\frac{\text{Mass of drained soil} + \text{Mass of dry soil}}{\text{Mass of drained soil}} \right) \times 100$$

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7.6. SATURATED HYDRAULIC CONDUCTIVITY

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Water movement velocity through the soil is of great importance in terms of aspects such as agriculture. The entrance of water within the soil, its movement to the plants' roots, its evaporation from the soil surface and water flow within the wells are some of the most common situations where the water movement velocity through the soil plays an important role (Klute and Dirksen 1986). Hydraulic conductivity expresses the ability of a porous medium to transmit the water, and thus it depends on the soil structure, soil moisture and the water temperature.

Saturated hydraulic conductivity in the field provides information about the internal drainage of soils, soil structure or saturation that may influence on water flow. In agriculture, this property is used to design water application rates for drip irrigation, thus avoiding the water accumulation and runoff (Mbagwu 1995).

The method proposed here is based on the use of a simple annular ring, which is inserted into the soil (at a short depth), then the infiltration time is measured of a few small volumes of water repeatedly applied at the soil surface within the annular ring (Bagarello et al. 2012).

PROCEDURE

- Remove surface vegetation and litter.
- Insert the ring to a depth (d) of about 1 cm into the soil surface with the help of a hammer to avoid lateral loss of the pondered water at the soil surface.
- Pour a known volume of water (0.150 L) into the ring using a cylinder. Immediately when the amount of water is totally infiltrated, measure and record the elapsed infiltration time (s), and pour a second identical amount of water into the ring. Again, record the time (s) needed for the water to infiltrate (cumulative time).
- Repeat step 3. until the difference in infiltration time between five consecutive trials becomes negligible, indicating a practically steady state of infiltration.
- Record the number of water additions (N).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- A metal ring of internal radius $r = 0.075$ m (15 cm diameter). Its height can vary, but should be at least 10 cm.
- Hammer.
- Plastic measuring cylinders (150 mL).
- Plastic beakers (250 mL).
- Timer.
- Water bottle.

REAGENTS

- Water

REMARKS

According to the literature, α^* can be estimated on the basis of a general description of soil textural and structural characteristics. However, Bagarello et al., (2012) developed the explained relationship between α^* and IR, working with 149 infiltration curves collected on Burundian soils. These authors suggested that the infiltration rate contains the necessary information to estimate α^* .

CALCULATIONS

a) Calculate the experimental water infiltration “I” as follows:

$$I (\text{L m}^{-2} = \text{mm}) = \frac{\text{Poured water volume (L) at each time}}{\pi r^2 (\text{m})}$$

(Eq.1)

b) Calculate the experimental cumulative infiltration “I” as follows at each cumulative time t (s):

$$\text{Cumulative } I (\text{mm}) = \sum_{t=1}^N I$$

(Eq. 2)

c) Make a plot of the cumulative infiltration, I, vs time, t, such as that shown in Fig. 7.6.1.:

Figure 7.6.1. Cumulative infiltration plot

d) Calculate the infiltration rate, IR (mm s⁻¹) by the slope of the linearised cumulative infiltration curve (Figure 7.6.1), estimated by a linear regression analysis of the (I / √t, √t) data collected during the steady-state phase of the infiltration run. (Important to apply the linear regression with the root square of time).

e) Calculate Ks as follows:

$$K_s (\text{mm s}^{-1}) = \frac{IR}{0.467 (1 + \frac{2.92}{r \alpha^*})}$$

(Eq. 3)

where

IR (mm s⁻¹): is the infiltration rate

r (m): is the radius of the ring

$$\alpha^* (\text{mm}^{-1}) = 0.0262 + 0.0035 \times \ln(IR)$$

(Eq.4)

Table 7.6.1. Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity classes according to the Natural Resources Conservation Services of the USDA.

Ks class	Ks rate (mm s⁻¹)
Very rapid	141.14 10 ⁻³
Rapid	42.34 10 ⁻³ - 141.14 10 ⁻³
Moderately rapid	14.11 10 ⁻³ - 42.34 10 ⁻³
Moderate	4.23 10 ⁻³ - 14.11 10 ⁻³
Moderate slow	1.41 10 ⁻³ - 4.23 10 ⁻³
Slow	0.42 10 ⁻³ - 1.41 10 ⁻³
Very slow or impermeable	0.00 - 0.42 10 ⁻³

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7.7. ORGANIC MATTER AND CARBON CONTENT

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

The soil organic matter (SOM) is a complex type of natural material of crucial importance for the soil filtering function, soil aggregate stability, carbon cycling, and soil fertility (Simpson and Simpson 2012). SOM is composed of living plants, animals and microorganisms, as well as humus and residues of dead plants, animals, and microorganisms in different stages of decomposition (Hillel 2004). Humus is an important part of SOM (between 60 and 80%), it contains a large part of the nitrogen in this medium and is usually bound to inorganic materials of the matrix, so it is degraded quite slowly. SOM-content can be drastically changed by anthropogenic additions like compost, industrial organic by-products, farm yard manure, biomass of water purification systems, etc.

SOM contains a large proportion of organic carbon (around 58%), and these forms of carbon constitute the so-called soil organic carbon (SOC) (Iglesias Jiménez and Pérez García 1992). SOC is directly related to the quality of the environment, erosion resistance, water retention and plant productivity

(Han et al. 2017). SOC has a direct effect on plant growth and is the source of energy of many of the organisms that live in the soil (Anderson and Domsch 1985). Tillage can accelerate the loss of this type of carbon by favouring mineralization or oxidation as well as losses from leachate (Lal 2002).

In addition to this SOC, soil inorganic carbon (SIC) can also be found in soil, especially in the form of carbonates in high-pH soils. SIC has a lower interest from an agricultural perspective, but nevertheless constitutes an important part of the soil carbon pool (Tan et al. 2014).

SOM is usually determined by the method of loss-on-ignition (LOI) or wet oxidation (WO) (Hoogsteen et al. 2015). These methods are based on the difference in soil mass before and after oxidation (mineralization) of SOM. The difference between the two techniques (LOI and WO) rely on the way of eliminating the organic matter. SOM is more sensitive to heat than the mineral soil constituents implying that controlled SOM combustion can be carried out to eliminate organic matter without affecting the mass of remaining inorganic soil components. Another option is to use an oxidizing agent such as hydrogen peroxide to remove organic components. However, both methods have certain limitations. For example, the oxidation of organic matter by WO is usually incomplete and it is necessary to apply a correction factor that depends largely on the type of soil used. In the case of LOI, the water contained in the clays can lead to overestimation of SOM.

To determine the amount of SOC and SIC, a CHN elemental analyzer is usually employed (Duan et al. 2004). For soil carbon determination the samples are burned at high temperatures to release N₂, SO₂, O₂, NO_x, CO₂ and steam. These gases are separated using a series of columns and temperature variations, and they are passed through a thermal conductivity detector that, with the help of a series of patterns, allows to calculate the amount of carbon in the samples. In order to specifically determine SOC and SIC, total soil carbon is determined twice: i.e. before and after specific removal of organic matter.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Elemental Analyzer
- Muffle
- Porcelain crucible
- Analytical balance (0.01 g)
- Oven
- Spatulas
- Soil mill
- Tin capsules

CALCULATIONS

In order to calculate the percentage of organic matter in the sample (%O.M.) the following formula is applied:

$$\%O.M. = \frac{m_{DS} - m_{BS}}{m_{DS} - m_C} \times 100$$

Where

- mDS is the mass of the dry soil and the porcelain crucible.
- mBS is the mass of the burnt soil and the porcelain crucible.
- mC is the mass of the porcelain crucible.

The total carbon content (TCC) and the soil inorganic carbon (SIC) are obtained in percentage by weight (g of C in 100 grams of dry soil), a unit that can be converted to g of C per kilogram of dry soil by multiplying it by 10. The SOC is calculated by:

$$SOC = TCC - SIC$$

REMARKS

Flat-bottom crucibles are better suited to the determination of organic matter, since, by extending the soil sample over a larger area, soil burning is optimized.

PROCEDURE

A) Organic matter

First, it is necessary to dry the soil to prevent errors derived from moisture loss. For this, a porcelain crucible is weighed (mC). Then, about 10 grams of 2 mm sieved soil are also weighted (two replicates are made per sample). This soil is dried in an oven at 105°C until constant weight (mDS). Once the soil moisture has been removed, the soil is weighed to obtain the initial mass, and then the dried soil is introduced into a muffle at 450°C for 4 hours (LOI). When finished, the soil is reweighed (mBS). The values of organic matter are usually given as a percentage (with regard to the dry soil mass).

B) Total soil carbon

To determine the total soil carbon, it is necessary, first, to grind a few grams of 2 mm sieved soil. About 50 mg of the grinded soil are weighed in tin capsules and introduced into the Elemental Analyzer. This process must be repeated with carbon standards of known concentrations. The proportions obtained with this method have to be converted into mg of total carbon per gram of dry soil.

This process is repeated once the organic matter has been selectively removed by LOI to determine the amount of inorganic carbon present in the sample. The amount of SOC is calculated as the difference between total soil carbon and SIC.

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7.8. PARTICULATE ORGANIC CARBON AND MINERAL ASSOCIATED ORGANIC CARBON FRACTIONS

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

The interest for knowledge of the different carbon fractions and their resistance and ease of degradation, lies in their importance with respect to the characterization of the C cycle and the soil as a C sink (Forbes et al. 2006; Kuyakov et al. 2009). Soil organic matter (SOM) in part consists of particulate organic matter (POM) or particulate organic carbon (POC). POC represents the fresh or decomposing organic material (e.g. fine root fragments and other organic debris), and it serves as a readily decomposable substrate for soil microorganisms. The mineral associated organic carbon fraction (MOC) represents a more recalcitrant fraction, since it is highly resistant to microbial decomposition, and thus this fraction is linked to soil C storage and sequestration (Laganiere et al. 2010).

The method presented here is based on the soil physical fractionation, which is useful for distinguishing specific C pools responsive to agricultural soil management.

PROCEDURE

1.

Air-dry soil samples.

2.

Sieve dry soil at < 2 mm.

3.

Weigh 20 g of dry mineral soil and disperse by shaking overnight in a 100 mL solution of sodium hexametaphosphate (5 g L⁻¹).

4.

Sieve the mixture through a 0.053 mm sieve and gently wash the material retained by the sieve with deionized water (use 1 L of water). The material retained by the sieve is collected for POC determination, the soil particles passing through the 0.053 mm sieve is collected for MOC determination.

5.

Weigh the filters.

6.

Filter the retained material (> 0.053 mm) and put it in the oven at 60°C for 24 h for POC determination. Weigh the soil + filter.

7.

Put the soil particles (<0.053 mm) in the oven until the soil sample is dry for MOC determination. Weigh the dry soil.

8.

Grind the soil using a mortar and store it for carbon analysis. Concentrations of C in the isolated fractions will be determined using a C and N analyzer

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Reciprocal shaker
- 0.053mm sieve
- Porcelain crucibles 10–15 cm diameter
- Whatman filter paper 541. Hardened Ashless. CAT No. 1541-125
- Oven
- Agate mortar
- Analytical balance (0.01 g)
- Wash water bottle
- C and N analyzer

REAGENTS

- Deionised water
- Sodium hexametaphosphate (5 g L⁻¹): dissolve 5 g of sodium hexametaphosphate in deionised water, complete to 1 L and shake well.

CALCULATIONS

POC fraction (g C kg⁻¹ soil) is calculated using the following expression:

$$POC (g Kg^{-1}) = \frac{M_1 \times 100 \times c_1}{M_t \times 10}$$

Where:

- M1 is the mass of soil > 0.053 mm (g)
- Mt is total mass of soil used at the beginning of the analysis (g)
- C1 is the C concentration of the soil > 0.053 mm (%)

MOC fraction (g kg⁻¹) is calculated using the following expression:

$$MOC (g Kg^{-1}) = \frac{M_2 \times 100 \times c_2}{M_t \times 10}$$

Where:

- M2 is the mass of soil < 0.053 mm (g)
- Mt is total mass of soil used at the beginning of the analysis (g)
- C2 is the C concentration of the soil < 0.053 mm (%)

REMARKS

MOC fraction can also be determined by the formula $MOC = TOC - POC$, where TOC is total organic carbon, although this approach is less accurate.

The time in the oven will depend on the quantity of POC and MOC obtained (24 hours is the minimum).

As an alternative to removing the stones by hand, the dry soil may be sieved with a 1 mm sieve.

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8. SOIL GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSION

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PRINCIPLE AND APPLICATION

Greenhouse gases (GHG) from soil such as CO₂, N₂O and CH₄ are key compounds that affect climate change. GHG fluxes are influenced by soil variables that influence microbial activity such as pH, NO₃⁻ or NH₄⁺, which, in turn, are controlled by a combination of soil properties (soil moisture, texture or structure) and soil management (IPCC 1995).

The principle of this method is based on covering an area of soil surface with a measurement chamber and follow the change of gas concentration in the chamber during its enclosure. For this, samples are taken for laboratory analysis (static chamber method) or the concentration of each gas is determined directly using a greenhouse gas analyzer (dynamic chamber method). This method is adapted from Álvaro-Fuentes et al. (2019).

PROCEDURE

GHG determination using gas chromatograph (Static gas chamber technique)

- Insert the chamber frame into the soil at 10 cm depth to keep the roots out of the chamber area and remove all growing plants the day before the measurement. Frames should be in soil at least 24 h before taking measures to avoid the effect of soil perturbation while inserting the frame.
- Take the chambers to their positions but do not close them yet.
- Close the first chamber and start the stopwatch. Take the first sample from the air inside the chamber.
- Close the second chamber and take the sample 1 or 2 minutes after the first sampling. The time depends on the distance of the chambers and the time available before the next sampling point. Enough time must be allowed to walk between the chambers. Repeat this procedure as long as the first sample of every chamber has been taken.
- Start the second round of sampling. Proceed the same way as during the first round but mix the air in the chamber by filling and emptying the syringe 3-5 times before taking the sample (if there is no fan in the chambers).
- Proceed with all 4 rounds as above. Options for timing of sampling rounds include e.g. 0, 15, 30, 45 minutes or 0, 20, 40, 60 minutes.
- Note soil temperature and moisture close to each chamber. Also record air temperature. Remember to take the reading of frame height from the soil surface for determining the total headspace volume.
- Take the samples to the laboratory and proceed with the analysis as defined in your laboratory guidelines, using gas chromatograph or a flow-through instrument for gas analysis.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Frames for gas-tight use of chambers (at least one frame per plot, ideally three frames per plot).
- Vented chambers for gas sample collection (Figure 8.1). Vent is a 0.5–1 m long tube with a diameter of 3–4 mm. Mixing of air during sampling can optionally be achieved by a battery-operated fan or by applying a perforated sampling probe extending from the top to the bottom of the chamber.
- Soil moisture and temperature sensors and data logger.
- Sample vials (glass with rubber septa).
- Syringes with needles.
- Stopwatch.
- Gas chromatograph or a flow-through instrument for gas analysis.

REAGENTS

- Gases for the gas chromatograph as required by the measurement method.
- Reference gases of known concentration.

CALCULATIONS

A script for case-wise linear or non-linear method selection is used for calculating the results. It implements a selection algorithm using the minimum detectable flux for selecting between the linear and non-linear calculation (Hüppi et al. 2018).

Determine the minimum detectable flux of your measurement system at 95% confidence level as instructed in Appendix 3 of De Klein and Harvey (2015) or use the function in the gas fluxes R-package. Calibrate the detector (concentration vs. peak area). Use a reference gas range similar to that of the samples.

Using the calibration curve, first calculate the sample concentration as $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ (ppm). Sample concentration ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$) is divided by the volume of ideal gas (L mol^{-1}) yielding the chamber air concentration as $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$. Multiply the concentration ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) by the molar weight of the gas (g mol^{-1}) to convert the unit to $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.

The volume of ideal gas must be temperature-corrected, thus correct for the air temperature using the ideal gas law. The volume of ideal gas is calculated as

$$V=0.082056 \times (273.15+T)$$

where 0.082056 is the gas constant (R) and T is the chamber or ambient air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$).

$R=Pv/nT$; at standard temperature and pressure $R= 1 \text{ atm} \times 22.414 \text{ L/1 mol} \times 273.15 \text{ K} = 0.082056 \text{ l atm mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$.

Use the gas fluxes R-package to calculate the fluxes for each chamber from the sample concentration values. For this you will need the headspace volume, frame area and time of sampling from the start of the chamber enclosure. The script will provide both a linear and “robust” non-linear flux estimate.

Data are represented as $\text{mg CO}_2/\text{N}_2\text{O}/\text{CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$. A minimum of three time points are needed for each flux calculation.

PROCEDURE

GHG determination using a gas analyzer (Dynamic gas chamber technique)

- Insert the chamber frame into the soil at 10 cm depth. to keep the roots out of the chamber area and remove all growing plants the day before the measurement. Frames should be in soil at least 24 h before taking measures to avoid the effect of soil perturbation while inserting the frame.
- Place the chambers to their positions and lock them into their frames. Connect the chamber to the portable gas analyzer by inlet and outlet using a tube, thus permitting a continuous flow and avoiding pressure fluctuations.
- Quantify N₂O, CO₂ and CH₄ gasses every 1 min for a period of 5 min period. CO₂ emission is highly stable, so assess in the equipment a linear trend in CO₂ flux for the measured time to check proper working of the equipment and absence of leakage.
- Record soil temperature and moisture close to each chamber.

Figure 8.1. Vented chamber for gas sample collection by the static chamber method (source: Dénes Lóczy)

Figure 8.2. Chamber with one inlet and one outlet to be connected to the portable gas analyzer using the dynamic chamber method (source: Raúl Zornoza)

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Frames for gas-tight use of chambers.
- Chambers with one inlet and one outlet to be connected to the portable gas analyzer (Figure 8.2).
- Two connectors tubes to connect the chamber with the gas analyzer (approx. 0.5 m long)
- Greenhouse gas analyzer.
- Soil moisture and temperature sensors and data logger.

CALCULATIONS

N₂O, CO₂ and CH₄ emissions rates are calculated as the difference between the quantification at the end and beginning of the measure period divided by the time.

$$\text{GHG rate (mg m}^{-2}\text{ h}^{-1}) = \frac{\Delta\text{GHG (ppm)} \times \text{chamber volume (dm}^3) \times 0.001 \times \text{UC}}{\text{soil surface (m}^2) \times \text{time (h)}}$$

where,

ΔGHG = ppm of the gas measured after 5 min – ppm of the gas measured at the start

0.001 = unit conversion from dm³ to m³

UC = unit conversion from ppm to mg m⁻³:

CO₂: 1.8 mg m⁻³.

N₂O: 1.88 mg m⁻³.

CH₄: 0.656 mg m⁻³.

GHG Cumulative emissions (for both methods)

N₂O, CO₂ and CH₄ cumulative emissions are estimated by numerical integration:

$$\text{GHG cumulative emissions (g m}^{-2}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\text{GHG rate (mg m}^{-2}\text{ h}^{-1}) \times 24}{1000}$$

where,

24 = 24 hours of the day

1000 = Unit conversion (1 mg = 0.001g)

REMARKS

If it is not possible to install the frames before root growth, take into account that the trenched roots may cause overestimation of soil respiration which may require correction in the calculation phase. Respiration from living roots should be excluded but the dead roots from the previous growing season should not be taken out since they are part of the soil organic matter already. In winter, in the case of presence of snow, the chamber volume needs to be corrected for the volume of snow inside the chamber. For this, sample a known volume of snow and based on this information divide the snow mass in the chamber with the density of ice (0.9168 g cm⁻³).

Random chamber placement is recommended but in farmers' fields it is also polite and practical to plan the placement so that e.g. dimensions of spraying equipment are taken into account (so that the farmer can drive between the chamber frames during the growing season).

For experiments with different subplot areas that are expected to have different emission dynamics, it is suggested to measure in both conditions on each plot if it is relevant to the experimental treatment.

The enclosure time varies with the chamber dimensions. General advice is found in De Klein and Harvey (2015) but the quality of the results informs if the enclosure was long enough. The measurements should be taken between 9.00 and 12.00 to avoid bias by temperature. For the same reason, it is also a good practice to vary the chamber sequence between sampling days.

The intended number of samplings per year should be 25 and these can be allocated so that periods of high emissions such as fertilisation, tillage, flooding, snowmelt, harvest and other abrupt system changes are well represented. It is very important that a measurement is conducted very soon after such an abrupt system change.

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